

Digital Transformation in Real Estate:

Digital transformation in real estate: towards an application of blockchain technology for commercial real estate in Switzerland

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CERTIFICATION

I, Evgeny Exter, declare that this thesis, submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Doctor of Philosophy, in the School of Business and Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland, is wholly my own work unless otherwise acknowledged. No part of this research or document has previously been submitted for any qualification at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Evgeny Exter, 03th March 2025

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ABSTRACT

The commercial real estate industry ranks among the largest asset classes on the global. At the same time, commercial real estate transactions are notorious for their complexity, which stems from multiple property brokers, legal entities, illiquidity, and a lack of transparency. However, specific industry factors such as heterogeneity and immobility are subject to legal jurisdictions and bound to local markets. This complexity is further accentuated by the heterogeneity and immobility of the real estate market and inefficient manual processes that incur high-cost structures which places significant pressure on the real estate market. Real estate assets are the backbone of industrialized societies and a support of private wealth contribution. In this context, innovation plays a key role and depends on the viability with its driving forces behind these developments are new technology, maneuverability, organizing differently and management.

Against this background, this study was motivated to provide important insights into the transformative potential of blockchain technology and smart contracts in the commercial real estate sector. By decoding traditional processes into smart contracts and embracing tokenisation, the industry can overcome barriers, reduce transaction costs, and realize increased revenues. The findings contribute to both academic discourse and practical implementation, laying the groundwork for a more efficient and accessible global commercial real estate market.

The aim of this study is to explore a novel solution for traditional process of buying or selling of real estate assets by identifying current loopholes of the traditional paper-based method and eliminate the human-based interactions by novel, mathematical algorithms based on Ethereum blockchain technology. In doing so, this study proposes a novel approach to address these challenges using blockchain technology, which enables buyers and sellers to transact in an informationally symmetrical way within an open real-estate ecosystem. The proposed conceptual model employs tokenisation on the blockchain and is developed using the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology and Action Design Science Research (ADSR) methodology. The model underwent multiple stages of evolution, including pre-design, which is validated through expert interviews, to arrive at the final conceptual design. The study identifies six key factors that influence the application of blockchain in real estate transactions, including adoption, governance and compliance, transaction costs, transparency and immutability, security, and scalability.

The findings reveal that encoding commercial real estate processes as ERC777 smart contracts results in reduced transaction costs and drives revenue and profitability increases through tokenisation. Utilising the ADSR methodology, this research amalgamates a systematic literature study, conceptual model development, prototype creation, and empirical evidence analysis. This approach provides a robust foundation for understanding the theoretical and practical implications of integrating blockchain technology and smart contracts into commercial real estate practices. In this context, the scientific progress of this research, not only showcases the transformative potential of ERC777 smart contracts and tokenization in commercial real estate but also introduces a novel methodological approach for the exploration of this phenomenon. By advancing theoretical understanding and providing practical insights, this thesis lays the groundwork for further developments in research and applications within the commercial real estate industry. In doing so, this study provides an important platform for future scholars to contribute to the evolving discourse on tokenisation, providing a deeper understanding of its implications for commercial real estate, and uncovering new avenues for research and industry application.

DISCLAIMER

Blockchain and smart contracts are approached in this study from a business viewpoint rather than a technical engineering viewpoint. As the source code used in this study is the intellectual property of Swiss Realty, a private commercial real estate entity, the code is not disclosed in this thesis. The code base is available on the GitHub weblink and can be accessed upon permission of the founder. As such, the contribution of this doctoral study is based on its methodological contribution and its theoretical contributions to research in the form of advancing knowledge about the utility of smart contracts using blockchain in the context of commercial real estate.

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH

1.1 Background to the Project

The real estate industry ranks among the largest asset classes on the global trading markets (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019). However, the real estate industry specific factors such as heterogeneity and immobility are subject to the legal jurisdictions and bound to the local markets. This fact is further accentuated by the heterogeneity and immobility of the real estate market and manual inefficient processes with high cost structures putting the current real estate market under pressure (Breuer and Steininger, 2020). Real estate assets are the backbone of industrialised societies and a support of private wealth contribution. In this context, innovation plays a key role and depends on the viability with its driving forces behind these developments are new technology, manoeuvrability, organizing differently and management (Veuger, 2018; 2020).

Modern real estate is defined as a pool of immovable properties such as land, buildings and surrounding infrastructure (Berahim, Jaafar and Zainudin, 2015). While the business models have not significantly changed over time, today, global climate change and recent effects of pandemics have negatively affected project development in the real estate sector, sales operations of existing real estate, costs estimate, values and rates of return of existing real estate sector require a new rethinking of the real estate. (Tanrıvermiş, 2020). Nevertheless, real estate assets are distinctly different compared to other assets such as equities and bonds, as they have high transaction costs, long-term commitments, more stringent regulations and other barriers to entry (Dijkstra, 2017). Due to this complex nature of the real estate process and the multitude of players involved, a variety of contracts is required to outline the relationship among all stakeholders, including their responsibilities, liabilities and duties (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018), creating significant bureaucratic hurdles.

Today's complex real estate life cycle determines the innovation and competitiveness and thus affects current and future valuation of real estate. New disruptive technologies and various IT solutions are available in the real estate sector to adapt to the new P2P ecosystem that can touch and transform assets, communication protocols, applications, data analytics. The transformation process in the real estate industry continues to expand at a rapid pace across the real estate ecosystem by digitalising the maintenance and asset contract optimisation, optimize value chain process operations, increase operational performance, reduce administrative burden, and enable new P2P business models. *

Over the last decades, continuous technological progress has fostered digital transformation in real estate. This led to new technologies being used to connect different parties in the sector and reduce some of the barriers to productivity (Ullah, Sepasgozar and Wang, 2018). Those *smart real estate technology drivers* have become a “game-changer” for the previous human interactions process and especially the commercial real estate social paradigms (Jylhä, Remøy and Arkesteijn, 2019). Hereby, technology reflects the progress on the previous human interactions with all the related intermediaries of the real estate contract and how they have been consciously interacted with each other for each real estate transaction. It starts with creation of centralised IT platforms, mainframes and later decentralised IT platforms, clouds, etc. to automate traditional human process. Today, this is more and more frequently realised by using machine learning (Annervaz, George and Sengupta, 2016), decentralisation of nodes and P2P network process (Thilini and Wickramaarachchi, 2019), thus creating the basis for the use of Blockchain technology. The key advantage of the Blockchain technology is the fact that it enabled to translate human contract into the automated contract with special conditions and limitations into decentralized store of information and leverage the effect of crowdfunding (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018). Furthermore, the Blockchain technology allowed to store digital land rights on the decentralised ledger and enable property registration based on the cadastre digital signature (Badea, Badea and Vasilca, 2019). In this regard, the Blockchain technology allowed to program automated transaction workflow and achieve faster cash settlements being run on the digital Smart Contracts (Rahmadika and Rhee, 2018) which shortened the time of execution and resulted into the efficiency improvements (Dijkstra, 2017), transparency (Ameyaw and de Vries, 2021) and trust (Veuger, 2018; 2020). However, there are certain risks such as market risk of platform failure, credit risk of default or liquidity which new financial ecosystem called as “Decentralized Finance (DeFi)” need to consider by transforming traditional real estate assets into the Blockchain protocols that run without intermediaries (Zhang and Li, 2021). Blockchain technology there is a potential disruptor in the real estate sector. It has the potential of leading to notaries and brokers acting in a P2P (P2P) way within one ecosystem in the future, impacting the design of the current real estate contract where property owners, financiers, users, builders, brokers, notaries and the land registry could be designed on a decentralised Blockchain Smart Contract (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019).

1.2 Motivation for the Research

This thesis is motivated by the need to address four fundamental issues with the current design of commercial real estate transaction processes due to the following factors: (i) real estate market asymmetry; (ii) fintech revolution and tokenisation, (ii) high-cost transaction process, (iii) bureaucratic and slow process, (iv) restricted social interaction due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and (v) legal and regulatory constraints.

First, the real estate market asymmetry underpins the lack of transparency due to asymmetric information and puts the transactional process subject to administrative burdens which are bound by each local jurisdiction and requires a reshaping of the real estate industry (Krupa and Akhil, 2019). This asymmetric information problem is especially prevalent in high-value, low-frequency assets such as real estate market (Hoksbergen *et al.*, 2019). The decentralised Blockchain solution would enable to mitigate asymmetric information by automatic update of each P2P node within the chain and create new transparency opportunities for the financial derivatives cluster (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

Second, several technological innovations start reaching the required level of maturity to impact the real estate sector. For instance, blockchain technology has recently been identified as a potential disruptor in several industries, allowing notaries and brokers to be within a single ecosystem with impact on property owners, tenants, brokers, notaries and the land registry (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018). Consequently, fintech revolution has led to “tokenization” of real estate assets. However, tokenisation of assets doesn’t have a full cycle end-to-end implemented use case and should be handled with care and in exploration mode. However companies have been trying to implement several Proof of Concepts (PoC) to assess the potential effects such a technology could have on their business model cases which allows to “tokenise” to provide the fractional ownership to the token holder and achieve investment liquidity in a real estate market, processes can be eliminated, thus achieving digitization of real estate ownership and remove significant market barriers to enter the real estate market even for the small income investors (Arkipova, Sirotin and Buzhinsky, 2019). These tokenisation design concepts have already been translated into first practical implementation Proof of Concepts such as Blockchain-enabled Multiple Listing Service (MLS) as mentioned by Krupa and Akhil (2019). As a result, those process improvements impact on treasury, transaction workflow (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019; Thota, 2019), faster cash settlements, and auto-execution of smart contracts (Rahmadika and Rhee, 2018). This is achieved by enabling P2P digital payments on first generation Bitcoin, second generation compatibility of the Smart

contract/ Ether basis (Garcia-Teruel, 2020), and third generation Cardano, Polkadot which use the trend of the decentralised structure Web 3.0 protocol by solving the P2P interoperability. Those decentralized operations can increase process efficiency and operation excellence by sharing processes and information on a protocol level. Therefore, P2P blockchain processes can be shared from human to human, human to machine or machine to machine allowing for complex processes to be executed seamlessly for the commercial properties (DApps) (Norta, Fernandez and Hickmott, 2018). In the coming months (as of November 2021), Ethereum will complete its migration from a PoW network over to a Proof-of-Stake (PoS) project. The migration to the PoS consensus mechanism will provide instant transaction system and, improve Ethereum's scalability and reduce its carbon footprint. Additionally, it will enable users to stake their ETH and earn rewards (Buterin, 2021).

Third, the transaction process of a commercial real estate is considered challenging due to its cumbersome process structure consisting of several intermediaries, property brokers registration and cadastre structures, legal documents, and legal force (Badea, 2019). Therefore, complex dynamics of the interdependent relations between the intermediaries in the real estate models lead to non-linear increase of the all related real estate contract stakeholders, which may lead to an exponential growth of potential errors and discover how the traditional intermediaries are to be removed from the real estate process (Gkana, Zachilas and Arvanitidis, 2013). Hereby, those potential errors result into higher search and transaction costs, which could be significantly reduced by omitting the redundancy processes of the so called 'middleman' stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer and seller (Veuger, 2018) and land registration (Veuger, 2020).

Fourth, the frustrations with the notoriously slow process of the existing real estate process due to administrative burden, bureaucracies, and expensive real estate commerce (i.e. processes, verifications, validations, etc.) (Krupa and Akhil, 2019). Important changes are reported to occur related to real estate core processes like planning, construction, asset management as well supporting processes such as administration, marketing, operation, tenant's management, maintenance, facility management and practically showcased on the commercial real estate office building by (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019) which have been also reported recently in Switzerland (Proptech Switzerland, 2021).

Fifth, the long term impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the real estate ecosystem includes a stunted pace of digital transformation (Hodgson, 2020) and causing socio-economic

implications that inevitably influence the demands of actors in this ecosystem (Nicola, 2020). For example, a recent study by Mui and Ling study (2021) reported that Malaysian Millennials intend to use more frequent digital real estate platform during the COVID-19 pandemic. Further, by using blockchain technology, the real estate platform would be P2P and enable them to save time when making important decisions such as whether or not to purchase or rent real estate product or services (Mui Ling Dyana *et al.*, 2022). These changes to the users and uses of real estate imply the need to also change the industrial technology processes of the respective commercial market especially due to COVID-19 pandemic developments (Starr, Saginor and Worzala, 2021).

Sixth, the real estate market has put high regulatory burdens on launching novel and innovative investment products, which require an adequate, experienced, and specialized legal background. In Particular, since the Swiss real-estate investment is restricted by Swiss federal a law known as 'Lex Koller' (or more specifically the 'Federal Law on the Acquisition of real estate by Persons Abroad'), the commercial real estate within the building construction appears to be at a turning point (Dakhli, Lafhaj and Mossman, 2019). In the light of recent developments with Fintech, Property-tech and professional career in the real estate, the aim is to investigate the outdated process structures in the real estate market (Kumar *et al.*, 2019). The aim to research current problems such as information asymmetry and high transaction costs and find novel solutions for the potential for a blockchain shared-ledgers infrastructure where buyers and sellers could interact in an equivalent way through an open real-estate ecosystem. Consequently, the interdisciplinary research shows different research areas from engineering research or cryptography science where blockchain based property registry system is developed by enhancing the process efficiency resulting into higher transparency and trust for the investors.

1.3 Research Problem

Despite the real estate being among the largest asset classes on the global trading markets (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019), the industry belongs to the immovable asset class with its own features and applications subject to each jurisdiction which is distinctly different compared to liquid ones such as equities and bonds (Bondar *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the related transaction costs are typically higher, regulations are more stringent and market entry barriers hinder long-term sustainable investments Thus, the way real estate currently is designed can be characterised as heterogeneity and immobility, creating the challenges of complex value flows, information inefficiencies and high transaction costs (Shahab and Allam, 2020).

The initial assessment of the evidence in other studies indicates that, it can be argued that the adoption of blockchain technology in the real estate is inevitable and there are several flaws in the current design of the transaction process leading to five major issues:

- (1) intermediaries and associated trust weaknesses
- (2) asymmetric information
- (3) speed of transaction and transaction costs
- (4) market mechanisms, consensus, and complex governance structure
- (5) investment management - non-scalability, interoperability, security issues

First, traditional paper-based real estate contracts are usually prone to errors, time-consuming and involve extra difficulties to cross-border operations. (Garcia-Teruel, 2020). (Dutta *et al.*, 2020) conducted a systematic review of 178 articles that examined blockchain features associated with operations. This study showed that errors occur in various supply chain operations across the industries such as shipping, manufacturing, automotive, aviation, finance, technology, energy, healthcare, agriculture and food, e-commerce, and education among others. It has also been shown that these can be successfully revamped with blockchain based technologies through enhanced visibility and business process management (Dutta *et al.*, 2020).

Second, the asymmetric information paradigm causes misinterpretations within the real estate contractual statements which are written in a non-algorithmic way, where one party in the current design always knows more about the contract or the local knowledge than the other party. This results into the buyer or seller information asymmetry and insufficiencies which are favourable to one of the parties (i.e., buyer, seller) and results into the moral hazard and adverse selection and respective market failure (Shahab and Allam, 2020; Zavadskas, Antucheviciene and Turskis, 2021).

Third, additional intermediaries are often involved in the contract to deal with the execution of the processes (e.g. brokers, notary, lawyers, back-office). The real estate market players need to trust such intermediaries and the fact that investors must rely on them by the current design of the commercial real estate transaction process poses a challenge. This is an issue by itself, as not every investor wants to rely on an intermediary for conducting a process that is prone to error and fraudulent activities (Tilbury, De La Rey and Van Der Schyff, 2019). Moreover, it causes related issues, such as asymmetric information and the speed of transaction. The intermediaries tend to have a deeper knowledge on the contracts than the investors, leading to an inequality related to the initial situations of the contract formation. one of the parties might

withhold information from the other party, which might negatively impact those real estate transactions. Such asymmetric information is especially prevalent in high-value, low-frequency assets (Hoksbergen et al., 2019; 2020; 2021) whereas relying on the information asymmetry leads to the process being slow and inefficient, as it typically is paper-based work which delays the speed and efficiency for the real estate contracts, resulting in costly processes (Hoxha and Sadiku, 2019; Swan, 2018). These high transaction costs create barriers for the market entry (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019). Moreover, the potential cost savings from using blockchain is approximately 8.3% of the total cost of residential construction (Dakhli, Lafhaj and Mossman, 2019).

Fourth, global real estate investments account for more than twice the size of the stock market, the number of the real estate investors is still much lower due to the liquidity issues and global access (Zhang and Li, 2021). Non-fungible tokens (NFTs) are tokens issued on a blockchain, like a cryptocurrency such as Ethereum. However, unlike a cryptocurrency, they are not “fungible,” meaning that each token is unique, rather than being identical and interchangeable with each other. Currently, Ethereum’s blockchain can handle around 15 transactions per second (tps) in its current state. The Ethereum 2.0 update to PoS would provide users with from 15 transactions to 100,000 transactions per second according to company documentation (Buterin, 2021).

Fifth, real estate markets are often unstable and are exposed to a high regulation by political authorities and difficult to access for the small investors (Veuger, 2020). Therefore, the existing design (status quo) of the real estate puts a complex burden on the investor due to high market barriers to access illiquid real estate investment class product and thereby addresses the problem of shortage of real estate project finance (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018). Consequently, the risk capital to enter the high price real estate market may turn off investors due to risk diversification and illiquidity of assets, since investors search for a favourable market, tax and legal systems (Kumar, Talasila and Pasumarthy, 2021).

On the one hand, the uncertainty of the financial markets remains persistent and for years financial markets have been facing lower interest rates, thus providing potential for investors to optimize cash-on-cash return in real estate. Therefore, real estate investors find this attractive because as the demand rises, so does the possibility to charge more money for a property in the longer-term by using Ethereum Smart Contracts (Vidhyalakshmi, Geetha and Sobitha Ahila, 2019). On the other hand, due to technology advancements, changing client demand the innovation within real estate has become a key focus to verify the business model.

In this manner, the old paper-based real estate model calls for restructuring of the process, to increase the efficiency, to standardise data, to automate processes and create room for the supply chain management steering and organizing tokenisation financial structures (Chang and Chen, 2020). The question that can be raised in this context is whether Blockchain is only a technological disruption or rather a real “game changer” with the potential to impact the entire value chain of the real estate market. Most recently, blockchain is one of the technologies that has proven to improve the operational efficiency of several industries and plays a role as a potential disruptor allowing in the back office, finance, asset management and customer contracts domain to redesign the processes and deliver for possible solutions that capitalize on the blockchain characteristic. Specifically, real estate industry shows a need for a single ecosystem where multiple actors could interact with each other such as property owners, financiers, users, builders, brokers, notaries, and the land registry (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018; Hoxha and Sadiku, 2019; Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019).

1.4 Research Aim, Questions and Objectives

Research Aim: The aim of this research is “*to investigate the disruption of blockchain technology for smart contracts on commercial real estate*”. In doing so, this study identifies new opportunities with associated with blockchain technology and explore a novel solution for traditional process of buying or selling of real estate assets by identifying weaknesses of the traditional paper-based method and eliminate the human-based interactions by novel, mathematical algorithms based on Ethereum blockchain technology.

To achieve this aim, this study answers the following research questions (RQ):

RQ 1: What is the impact of the smart contracts on the blockchain technology in the context of commercial real estates? This question examines the impact on speed (fast and frictionless), transparency, security, quality (error resistance/stability), validity, utility, trust and reduction of transaction cost, and efficacy and efficiency.

RQ 2: What is the impact of the tokenized real estate investments? The question examines the impact on asset liquidity, removal of market barriers, accessibility and the generation of funding from multiple sources and to leverage the return on investment.

To answer this questions, an Action Design Science Research (ADSR) methodology is adopted. In the context of this study, ADSR:

- i. Starts with the traditional real estate process under human interactions 'as-is',
- ii. Transforms the 'as is' to a novel design 'state of the art' of automated process,
- iii. Prototypes a proof-of-concept with the smart contract by using a mathematical algorithm code (Github) and performs specific functions and user testing (stakeholder feedback),
- iv. Conducts a pilot to P2P network and reflects on lessons learned based on the quantitative market survey,
- v. Contributes to the advancement of knowledge about the use of blockchain technology for research and practice.

Research Objectives

1) Diagnosis of the traditional challenges in real estate transactions (AS-IS)

This study systematically identifies key deficiencies in the traditional, paper-based methods of real estate transactions, such as human errors, weaknesses associated with inefficiencies, high costs, susceptibility to fraud, and dependence on human intermediaries. To achieve this aim, a detailed comparison of traditional real estate transaction processes with blockchain-based approaches, supported by expert interviews, validates the practicality and significance of the proposed solution.

2) Identify the most influencing key factors (Pre-Design)

To achieve this objective, the qualitative content analysis and the insights are derived from expert interviews and the systematic literature review substantiate the identification of these factors. The systematic literature review and an evaluation of relevant theories including a determination of process and stakeholder implications related to the application of blockchain on commercial real estate transactions underpins the investigation. The processes behind commercial real estate trading include several intermediaries, trust-based decision-making, and a complex array of sub-processes, and while blockchain has already demonstrated transaction potentials, it is not clear yet what practical implications this emerging technology has and will have on the process itself. The context of this study is the traditional real estate commercial process in Switzerland, specifically determining the codification potentials of blockchain technology within the commercial real estate sub-context and investigates the transaction cost reduction for the commercial real estate investment process on the example of commercial shopping centre. The study identifies six critical factors influencing the integration of blockchain technology into commercial real estate. These factors serve as a foundation for understanding the broader implications of blockchain in this domain.

3) Design and build a new conceptual model (New Design)

To achieve this objective, a new conceptual model is designed and validated through industry expert feedback and empirical testing, supports these conclusions. By employing and adapting the ADSR methodology, this study makes a methodological contribution to blockchain research. The amalgamation of systematic literature review, conceptual model development, prototype creation, and empirical validation establishes a robust framework for future studies. To achieve this aim, a conceptual model was iteratively developed and validated using the ADSR, ensuring methodological rigor and applicability to real-world scenarios. ADSR enables the development of a conceptual model through multiple design and evaluate iterations. The research outlines each stage of the ADSR methodology, demonstrating its application and relevance for complex, interdisciplinary challenges in blockchain-based decentralised systems.

4) Explore appropriate solution architecture and build customised solution (Implementation and Prototype)

To achieve this objective, the prototype enables a secure, efficient, and transparent transactions, on the other hand, tokenization removes the barrier of the asset illiquidity due to fractional ownership of the real estate assets for the investors, facilitating transactions in an open and symmetrical ecosystem. The Ethereum blockchain technology allows to use the code of the ERC777 from Github repository and customise own code Swiss realty smart contract. The use of ERC777 smart contracts demonstrated to significantly reduce transaction costs and enhance profitability by minimizing intermediary involvement and automating processes.

5) Empirical Evidence Supporting Practical Implications (Testing)

To achieve this aim, the thesis concludes with a roadmap for future research, emphasizing areas such as governance, scalability, and user adoption within tokenized real estate ecosystems. By addressing existing gaps in blockchain and tokenization literature, it lays a robust groundwork for future studies to build upon.

6) Contributions to Research and Practice (Evolution)

DSR is a problem-solving paradigm that designs and evaluates innovative artefacts with the desire to improve an environment (Hevner *et al.*, 2004). As this study adopted an ADSR approach to develop an artefact that was tested for its utility to improve an environment (i.e., commercial real estate), the contribution of this study can be framed using the Gregor and Hevner (2013) DSR Knowledge Contribution Framework (see Figure 1-1).

Specifically, the contribution of this study fits within the ‘exaptation’ quadrant as the study adopted existing solutions (i.e., source code, blockchain, smart contracts, business model canvas). In doing so, this study provides novel results that advance knowledge about blockchain-based smart contracts, and it provides actionable insights for practitioners and policymakers. The findings of this study reveal that tokenization can streamline real estate transactions and unlock new revenue streams for stakeholders. The testing of the prototype is conducted by the empirical analysis of the prototype and expert validation provides quantitative and qualitative support.

Figure 1-1: DSR Knowledge Contribution Framework (Gregor and Hevner, 2013, p. 345)

Gregor and Jones (2007, p. 318) state that "the construction of an artifact that is sufficiently novel is seen as a significant contribution in its own right." This suggests that the present study has made a notable contribution. Specifically, this study conceptualised a novel solution for commercial real estate contracts (Artefact 1) and then a prototype (Artefact 2) was designed, by leveraging P2P networking of cryptographic tokens once consensus between the peer network nodes is achieved, and the utility of the artefact was evaluated via a quantitative market study that was analysed using descriptive and analytic statistics. Further, as this DSR study provides rigorous evidence of a ‘proof of concept/prototype’, it aligns with the view of Davis (2005, p. 18) who asserts that a thesis may demonstrate its contribution by "developing and demonstrating new or improved design of a conceptual or physical artifact".

1.5 Overview of Relevant Theories

The following sections is to introduce the reader briefly to the theory, definitions and literature that will be used in the whole thesis and that it is elaborated on in more detail during chapter 2. Several theoretical positions underpin a multidimensional Real estate transaction process which is explained from Micro and Macroeconomy perspectives. For this research purpose the theory of Transaction Cost (Williamson, 2010) was chosen as a baseline to resolve the problem of intermediaries redundancy. First, the new permissionless Smart Contract on Ethereum platform does not require an intermediary “middleman” and allows to restructure old-fashioned administrative burdens, minimize search and opportunity costs which results into lower transaction costs. Second, the Smart contract decentralized would eliminate the downtime since the Ethereum nodes are distributed around the world and replace central authority. Third, the Smart contract leverages P2P networking of cryptographic tokens and reduce searching costs and time by achieving the consensus algorithms. Fourth, since there is no central authority, the censorship and data manipulation will be eliminated and increase a higher transparency, auditability and so-called “immutability” that the blocks cannot be changed, hacked or manipulated and thus increase the data quality and create trust for the customer (Williamson, 2010). Legally, current real estate contract serve as a baseline for the investment calculation over a buildings life cycle (Latifi, Zhang and Cheng, 2019) and show lack of risk evaluation for real estate hierarchy process (Liu, Li and Zhong, 2014). Beyond the Transaction cost theory which address the issues of search costs due to asymmetric information (Williamson, 2010). Hence, traditional real estate contracts are accompanied by human interactions and are exposed to mistakes from human paper-based recording practice. Thus, the real estate contract is backed by the theory of strategic governance of underpinning record keeping and preservation of authentic records from archival science (‘mirror type’, ‘digital record type’, and ‘tokenized type’) meaning that separate ledger record keeping with multiple sign-offs are more prone to error (Lemieux *et al.*, 2020). In this sense, current real estate contract foresees intermediaries for the contract enforcement, whereas the Smart contracts could provide self-enforcement (Laarabi, Maach and Hafid, 2020).

1.6 Overview of Methodological Approach

Based on the reviewed literature, several issues with the current design process of commercial real estate transaction are identified. For instance, the process is prone to errors due to multiple data validation instances. Moreover, the process transaction costs are high due to the involvement of many intermediaries.

Thus, to address these issues with the current design of commercial real estate transaction, “Design Science Research” (DSR) methodology as proposed by (Hevner *et al.*, 2004) is supposed to be a suitable methodology. It provides the opportunity to investigate the current design issues, explore the new concepts of redesign with the active iteration cycles for the development of a proof of concept. The approach starts with the rigor analysis of the relevant literature describing both the current challenges and future potentials of the research subject, then developing Artefacts that lead to recommendations for action and an impact on business practice.

Hereby, the purpose is to redesign a new conceptual model (1) and build a novel solution a pilot/ proof of concept to verify the practical solution (2). In this regard, this research applies the ADSR research method for generating prescriptive design knowledge through building and evaluating ensemble IT artefacts in an organizational setting (Sein *et al.*, 2011).

The methodology is split into the cycles for the IT artefact based on the DSR – in the practice it is used for multi-entry points/ agile methods, where each time new sprints are defined, and complete short cycles are undergone. While the original DSR process model identifies a four-stage approach to the application of the AR paradigm in a DSR study (Sein *et al.*, 2011), the most recent ADSR is extended. It uses the iterative “elaborated DSR process” combined with four stages 1) Diagnosis, 2) Design, 3) Implementation, 4) Evolution (Hevner *et al.*, 2004). In contrast to the DSR process, these stages are now gone through in multiple, iterative intervention cycles (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019). During the ADSR process, a conceptual model (Artefact 1) and a prototype for the smart contract on ERC777 (Artefact 2) are designed.

1.7 Outline of the Thesis

To answer the research questions and objectives of this study, this study follows the DSR methodology proposed by Gregor and Hevner (2004). Thus, the structure of the thesis is built in accordance with their suggested publication scheme (see Table 1-1).

Table 1-1: Design Science Research Study

Chapter	Contents
1. Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem definition, problem significance/motivation, introduction to key concepts, research questions/objectives, scope of study, overview of methods and findings, theoretical and practical significance, structure of remainder of paper. • For DSR, the contents are similar, but the problem definition and research objectives should specify the goals that are required of the Artefact to be developed.
2. Literature Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior work that is relevant to the study, including theories, empirical research studies and findings/reports from practice. • For DSR work, the prior literature surveyed should include any prior design theory/knowledge relating to the class of problems to be addressed, including Artefacts that have already been developed to solve similar problems.
3. Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research approach that was employed. For DSR work, the specific DSR approach adopted should be explained with reference to existing authorities.
4. Artefact Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A concise description of the Artefact at the appropriate level of abstraction to make a new contribution to the knowledge base. This chapter should occupy a major part of the thesis. The format is likely to be variable but should include at least the description of the designed Artefact and, perhaps, the design search process.
5. Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence that the Artefact is useful. The Artefact is evaluated to demonstrate its worth with evidence addressing criteria such as validity, utility, quality, and efficacy.
6. Discussion and Conclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpretation of the results: what the results mean and how they relate back to the objectives stated in the Introduction section. Can include summary of what was learned, comparison with prior work, limitations, theoretical significance, practical significance, and areas requiring further work. • Research contributions are highlighted and the broad implications of the paper's results to research and practice are discussed. Concluding paragraphs that restate the important findings of the work. • Restates the main ideas in the contribution and why they are important.

A synopsis of the six chapters is represented below.

Chapter 1 provides an overview and background on the research problem, research aims, objectives, research questions and outlined relevant theory and methodological approach.

Chapter 2 continues with state-of-the-art systematic literature synthesis that expands from theoretical background theories disciplines research to a more detailed systematic literature review. Consequently, the research problem is split into a systematic search procedure and

structured into relevant key words which accommodated to a common database format (Scopus). The literature review is carried out with a specific set of inclusion and exclusion criteria to get more precise results, apply further inclusion and exclusion criteria to derive a consequent literature pool. Once the final literature pool is identified, the analysis of the key information is distilled to derive the research gaps, explore suitable methodologies, investigate results and findings, and find relevant contributions and limitations.

Chapter 3 summarises and explains the key methodology types of DSR. The chapter analysis the selection of an appropriate methodology within different types of DSR approaches – classical Design Science, strategical Design Science (strategy 1 - class of future problems vs. strategy 2 - concrete case of a real system implementation), and iterative ADSR. The decision is set to follow the iterative ADSR with multiple entry-points which are process-driven closed cycles and result into End-to-End “ensembled Artefact”. This unique approach allows to include previous learning at multiple intervention cycles of each four phases 1) Problem Formulation, (2) Building, Intervention, and Evaluation (Artefact creation), (3) Reflection and Learning, (4) Formulation of Learning and achieve the highest utility by “ensembled Artefacts” for the End-Users.

Chapter 4 details the rigorous application of the ADSR used in this study and derives the “ensembled Artefacts” beginning with diagnosis of the problem of asymmetric real estate contract, design of a conceptual model (Artefact 1) and build a prototype for the Smart Contract on ERC777 (Artefact 2). Furthermore, this chapters reflects on the application of the smart contract protocol Ethereum (ERC 777). Therefore, the research objectives are undermined by the conceptual model (Artefact 1) and proof of concept (Artefact 2) as well as architecture, entity relationship model, technical solution is provided limitations and future technical considerations as well are discussed for further work.

Chapter 5 compares the theoretical framework (Chapter 3) and research artefacts (Chapter 4 – Concept and Pilot) of this thesis and conducts a quantitative study to further elaborate on the practical usability and relevance of the developed and prototypically tested concepts. Therefore, a statistically representative sample of the population across a variety of geo-regions is used. The evolution phase in the ADSR context thus is conducted by means of a market survey carried out related to research artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) (Venable, 2006). The analytical regression is designed to empirically evaluate Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) and to identify whether the prototype can contribute to an improvement in comparison to the traditional

commercial real estate contract and determine impact on the return on investment for the investor by using tokenized investment scheme. Therefore, the analytical regression is used to show what are the relations of parameters for a crypto investment in Real estate and how strong is the impact of each parameter on the investment decision.

Chapter 6 reports the results gained from the developed and evaluated Artefacts are discussed in the context of the insights gathered from the literature study and relevant theory. First, Result 1- Self-Execution contract is demonstrated by crypto-token asset sale process by the Ethereum Smart Contract which allows to replace human manpower by automated Smart contracts. Second, Result 2- Low transaction fee of Smart contract execution allows to save transaction costs from the shared Infrastructure and unified Blockchain ledger. Third, Result 3- Permissionless deployment on the Ethereum global network allows to generate Revenue gains by reaching the global network of investors.

The chapter concludes by articulating the important findings of the work as well as highlights main ideas in the contribution, underlines limitations and why they are important. The chapter explains future implications for both the academic and business world. However, the new technology is vulnerable to certain risks and limitations where legal frameworks need to be shaped to adapt fast evolving solutions and how they could be applied into real transformation projects. It furthermore provides an overview for future research that is either already specifically planned or that could be done based on this thesis. Therefore, future research needs to address those legal frameworks for the DeFi protocols to investigate the tokenization degree and legal acceptance of various DeFis protocols for the practical implementation project such as KYC/AML, regulator, clearance, investor protection and finance regulation laws work.

2. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Chapter Introduction

This chapter provides a combination of the relevant theory to understand the scope of the research area and systematic of literature review to identify the research gaps. First, relevant theory on interdisciplinary research of micro-, macro-economics, real estate and technology are provided to put the research in context and demonstrate a deep understanding of the research topic. Second, systematic literature review (SLR) is conducted to provide a recent and comprehensive overview of the specific area of Commercial real estate and identify the gaps of the current Real estate process application. During the review process and the analysis of relevant theories, four gaps in knowledge were identified. With the rise of blockchain technology and innovative decentralized applications, these four problems incentivise the thesis motivation for the current research gap how to leverage real estate economics synergies based on the cutting-edge blockchain technology and create academical contribution for the real estate society like other industries have already showed innovation progress. Some literature examples of social sharing through technology that have resulted in significant market disruptions:

1. Worldwide biggest provider of accommodation – Airbnb without own properties (Sherwood, 2019).
2. Worldwide most profitable Retailer – Alibaba without own storage (Levy, 2019)
3. Worldwide biggest retailer after Walmart is Amazon without own sales stores (Debter, 2020).
4. Worldwide biggest Taxi Transport – Uber without own cars (Richter, 2018).
5. Worldwide famous media – Facebook and without own content and Netflix without own movie (Alba, 2018).

Previous interdisciplinary research studies engage various relevant theories at the interface between economics, real estate, and technology.

1. Economics Theories reviewed are the theories of intermediaries, asymmetric information institution and microeconomics (Coase, 1937) intermediary theories such as financial institutions under uncertainty (Pyle, 1972), macroeconomic demand and supply of commercial loans (Melitz and Pardue, 1973) and transaction costs (Williamson, 2010).
2. Real estate theories include Intermediaries, Lion, Title Theories (Freyermuth and Nelson, 2009), legal real estate mortgages (Donkor-Hyiaman and Ghartey, 2017),

theory of a title token - general concept of real estate tokenisation on blockchain and constraints (Konashevych, 2020c) and benefits of the blockchain use for real estate and property rights (Konashevych, 2020a).

3. Technology theories include the potential of blockchain technology in building and construction (Dakhli, Lafhaj and Mossman, 2019), real estate geography and spatial economics of urbanization and fragmented urban structures (Escudero Gómez, 2018), Commercial real estate development process of geographical space (Xie and Gong, 2018) theories which are reviewed at the baseline for the blockchain technology – Bitcoin Model of (Nakamoto, 2009), decentralised application platform of Ethereum Smart Contract (Buterin, 2015) combined with the DSR (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019) and technical implementation (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

2.2 Relevant Theories

2.2.1 Economic Theories

Economic theories outline the rational models of the microeconomic and macroeconomic perspectives. Economic theories include microeconomic theories (Coase, 1937), macroeconomic liquidity theories (Diamond, 1997), institutional Economics (Williamson, 2010). According to the institutional economics theory viewpoint, the characteristics of interaction are subject to the firm's business character and the organisation set-up and how the firm should organise its transactions, i.e. whether the firm should produce by integrating the vertical chain or by outsourcing its resources and focussing on the core competence (Williamson, 1981). Therefore, Institutional Theory describes three pillars of Transaction Costs (Williamson, 1981, pp. 573-574).

1. Pillar one describes *“the search and information costs are costs such as in determining that the required good is available on the market, which has the lowest price, etc.”*
2. Pillar two describes *“the bargaining costs are the costs required to come to an acceptable agreement with the other party to the transaction, drawing up an appropriate contract etc.*
3. Pillar three describes *“policing and enforcement costs are the costs of making sure the other party adheres to the terms of the contract and taking appropriate action (often through the legal system) if this turns out not to be the case.”*

From a real estate viewpoint, the financial intermediaries act as the middleman between two parties buyer/ and seller in a financial transaction (Veuger, 2018) and result into higher search and transaction costs which could be significantly reduced by omitting the redundancy processes of the so called 'middleman' stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer and seller (Veuger, 2018) and land registration (Veuger, 2020). Therefore, complex dynamics of the interdependent relations between the intermediaries in the real estate models lead to non-linear increase of the all related real estate contract stakeholders, which may lead to an exponential growth of potential errors and discover how the traditional intermediaries are to be removed from the real estate process (Gkana, Zachilas and Arvanitidis, 2013).

According to the recent institutional analysis by Frolov (2020), a modern institutional economics viewpoint, the key factor is to reduce the number of intermediation and minimise the transaction costs. Thus, the result of the research showed that modern institutional economics not only will lead to a significant reduction in transaction costs but will also reorient intermediaries toward improving the quality of transactions and expanding the offer of additional transaction services (Frolov, 2020).

In this context, the theory of institutional assemblages indicates that private and public institutions act as hybrid with the blockchain-based institutions associated exclusively with the principles of decentralization, transparency, and openness (Shahab and Allam, 2020) and achieve required level of trust as required in under classical real estate trust accounting (Secinaro, Calandra and Biancone, 2021). Further research needs to be concluded on the new institutional economics and trust mechanism such as tradeable permit schemes (TPS) of the modern blockchain-based institutions (Shahab and Allam, 2020).

2.2.2 Real Estate Problems Associated with Economic Theories

The economic theories are split into microeconomic theories (1-3) and macroeconomic theories (4-6). *First*, asymmetric information has been discussed since the microeconomic theories began with the transaction costs in the early 20th century when 'Nature of the Firm'. (Coase, 1937). The asymmetric information in commercial real estate markets is a significant cause of difficulty since the real estate contract includes asymmetric market information, where hidden characteristics and actions are not visible for the stakeholders (problem of separate ledgers record keeping). According to Coase (1937) since financial intermediaries are firms, they are subject to microeconomic approach where the market participants and their relations

represent the market for financial intermediaries. Deeper microeconomic research of the information asymmetry and explanation of the intermediary's buyer-seller was explained by Akerlof (1970) on the "Secondary-Market-Model". On the one hand, since buyers cannot trace and track the original product, the seller would tendentially try to sell "lemons" (bad products)" at the price of good products. On the other hand, buyers, tend to behave risk-averse and the feeling of being cheated, would not pay the price of good products, and this also makes sellers less willing to sell good products. Those, eventually only bad products (lemons) are available for trade, an outcome known as adverse selection as explained by (Akerlof, 1970) and applied in the liquidity and information asymmetry for the real estate market by (Wong, Yiu and Chau, 2013). *Second*, human errors are natural and are part of the manual interventions by third parties since there are central ledger systems for each stakeholder and by creating redundancies and would prevent censorship and fraud since the contract cannot be changed, hacked, or manipulated. According to Spielman (2016), more than 30% of property titles are found with an error at the time of a real estate transaction (Spielman, 2016a). The study shows a root-cause analysis of a manual paper-based transaction, where various types of real estate transaction (e.g., deeds, mortgages, leases, easements, court orders municipality protocols, bank statement) are associated with a human error (Spielman, 2016). *Third*, the traditional transaction costs of the real estate commercial contract could be reduced due to a new opportunity of the smart contract to self-execute and eliminate the problem of intermediary and the problem of high-cost of property transaction which would eliminate the redundancies and require less transaction costs (Williamson, 2010) and recent crypto economy opportunities where Bitcoin or Ethereum could foster the decentralization progress by removing the intermediaries in economic transactions and reduce the need for the government (Berg, 2019). *Fourth*, the macroeconomic approach explores the liquidity, efficiency, and accessibility parameters of real estate (Diamond 1983). *Fifth*, macroeconomic factors of Real estate explain the money market and interest rates for the market loans and liabilities with its traded customer deposits (Bernanke, Gertler and Gilchrist, 1999). Hence, the money market accessibility and liquidity problem in real estate hindered mortgage models like systematic fragility (Minsky and Hyman, 1977) the mid of 20th century. *Sixth*, volatility theories (Kindleberger and Romasco, 1979) explain the mortgage volatility for a real estate transaction. In the periods of low volatility lenders might be willing to pay higher leverage, whereas other literature sources analysed mortgage standards in relation to dampening effects of arbitrage (Fostel and Geanakoplos, 2008). Finally, recent macroeconomic theories analyse the relation between the real estate automation and human resources for the automation jobs (Redlein and Grasl, 2018). It is estimated that more than 47% of real estate jobs in facility management will be automated by machines (Redlein and Grasl, 2018).

2.2.3 Real Estate Theories

Real estate theories fall under five broad categories, namely (i) land theory, (ii) lien theory, (iii) title theory, (iv) intermediate theory (4), and (v) modern application to tokens of the title theory.

Land theories are historical as they are rooted in a time when the discovery of the ownership of lands and property took place in the United States and was organized by the deed registration under the Land Registry Act (1962) (Act 122) provided inadequate information to foster title registration under the Land Title Registration Act (1986) (P.N.D.C.L. 152). As a result, deed registration was only helpful in establishing priority of instruments and did not confer title (Sittie,2006) or guarantee security of title for mortgaging. Enforcement foreclosure over such lands in the event of mortgage default becomes difficult, prolonged and costly without certainty of success (Donkor-Hyiaman and Ghartey, 2017).

Lien theory describes mortgage as a lien (Durfee, 1912) and was defined as the “*legal lien*” called an *equitable lien*; while, if he has rights in ren, they are legal rights, of the kind which we have agreed to call “pledge” and of the variety which we have agreed to call “*hypothecation*,” but which will be sufficiently distinguished from the other alternative of *equitable lien* by the term “*legal lien*” (Durfee, 1912, p. 512) Correspondingly, the lender attains lien, and the mortgage party receives the underlying property. The security for the mortgage parties is the interest of the underlying property (Sands, 2020).

Title theory refers when a “*lender holds the actual legal title to a piece of real estate for the life of the loan while the borrower/mortgagor holds the equitable title. When the sale of the real estate goes through, the seller transfers the property to the lender, who then grants equitable title to the borrower*”. Consequently, the borrower can occupy and use the property, but the lender has legal ownership over the property title (Sands, 2020). The main difference of the Lien theory between the Title theory is that the Lien theory recognizes mortgage as a lien based on the security interest, whereas the Title theory states out that legal title is equitable to the interest of possession by the property conveyed to lender by mortgage (Enock, 2016). Since the lender already technically owns the property, the lender simply revokes the borrower’s equitable title and reclaims the property. In the praxis, a lender would simply step in and take possession of the property if a borrower defaults on the loan (Freyermuth and Nelson, 2009).

Intermediate theory was proposed by (McKinnon, 1973) and acts as a hybrid theory of both the title and lien theories. In the context of the title theory, the mortgage serves while the borrower retained the right to hold the property title. For title under intermediate theory, the mortgage institutions behold the ownership over the property on behalf of the borrower while the transfer of property was backed by the trust (Enock, 2016). In the context for real estate, the intermediate theory was applied for the real estate transfer of ownership for the specific contract for sale of land, where deeds and titles were not centrally stored and caused some problems during the transfer in relation to the respective rights and duties of the associated intermediaries (Freyermuth and Nelson, 2009).

Token title theory is more contemporary and relevant to modern society. For example, the deed of trust of the title to the third party (trustee) could be substituted by the digital record of ownership which is registered on the blockchain (Konashevych, 2020b) and achieve transferability of assets across blockchains, which prevents fraudulent activities on the cross-blockchain protocols (Bhanushali *et al.*, 2020). The title token theory is used to represent an actual conveyance of title to the mortgagee where the underlying document is usually called a “mortgage deed” and the borrower takes the digital ownership possession of the token. (Konashevych, 2020c).

2.2.4 Technology Theories

While previous research theories shed light on the relevant theories at the interface between economics and real estate, this section provides a mix of the relevant technology theories for the disruption of the real estate industry. These theories are: (i) theory of reasoned action, (ii) innovation diffusion theory, (iii) technology acceptance model, and (iv) unified theory of acceptance and use of technology.

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) examines the customer and respective user experience behaviour which is explained by social norms and attitudes. Those norms cause influence attitude and subsequently effect on the behaviour. The outcome of the theory is the analysis of the customer behaviour based on parameters personal attitude and subjective norms summed into parameter behaviour intention and results in the final behavioural outcome (Fishbein *et al.*, 1975, pp. 319-339).

Innovation Diffusion Theory examines the diffusion of innovation and measured the degree of IT uses of individuals in organizations based on ease of use, relative advantage, compatibility,

relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trial ability, and observability. It has been used in several seminal studies (e.g., Moor et. al, 1996; Rogers, 1995, 2003) that examined information technology acceptance in terms of intention measurement of individual acceptance behaviour towards technology acceptance.

Technology Acceptance model (TAM), model examines information technology and user acceptance ease within jobs individually. The model determines parameters for information technology acceptance case and rejection case and finds out that perceived usefulness and perceived ease are significant for acceptance of information technology (Davis 1989) but later adjusted for benchmark of companies use cases (Miltgen et. Al., 2003).

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) analyses the projection of values of relation on outcomes of TAM model where attitudes and norms caused intention which subsequently effects on the behaviour. The difference to the TAM model lies in the perceived behavioural control (Ajzen 1991). The TPB model has been extended on the delineating internal and external constraints by Taylor and Todd (1995).

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) consolidated the above described models and unified the parameters of attributes, norms, intentions in relation to behaviour as well extended to additional variables set such as age, gender, user experience and voluntariness of use (Venkatesh et. al., 2003, pp. 425-478). The most suitable theory for this study is the application of the UTAUT with TRA, TPB and IDT theories (See Figure 2.1).

Figure 2-1. Technology Theories for the User Experience (UTAUT)

While social theories aim to identify how social reasoned interaction of the customers (TRA) intermediaries social norms, how the technology diffusion enables to accept new technology disruptions by influencing key factors in the acceptance of suitable technology (UTAUT) - the user intention behaviour in accepting blockchain technology (Ng and Lee, 2021).

2.3 Systematic Literature Review of Blockchain in Real Estate

2.3.1 Review process

The SLR adopts the process (see Figure 2-2) proposed by (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003)) due to its comprehensiveness, transparency and validity leading to clear, replicable and verifiable results to summarise evidence of how blockchain technology is applied or researched in the real estate context. The review and synthesis of academic literature are not only important to comprehensively summarize current literature, but also to conduct a rigorous and impactful research (Kunisch *et al.*, 2018), they are also key to identify research gaps (Booth, 2012) to build future research upon. Despite it requires substantial time and resource effort (Pittaway *et al.*, 2004), a SLR is regarded to be a suitable approach for this thesis, as due to it rigorous approach to critically review blockchain assessment studies (Colomo-Palacios, Sánchez-Gordón and Arias-Aranda, 2020).

Figure 2-2. The 8-step process for conducting SLR (source: Denyer and Tranfield, 2009)

Step 1: Pre-planned methods/protocol: As “real estate” is still a broad term that can be distinguished between residential (private property market) and commercial real estate (corporate assets and buildings market). To get an initial understanding of the area and the problem, the online library of the University of the West of Scotland and Google Scholar have been first identified as potential sources for the review. Later, an access opportunity to the more comprehensive Scopus database fulfilled the need for a more structured way of data collection. Scopus is a unique and transparent database which allows to save variants and recreate the research results. The outcome of Scopus was a successful dataset with most of the key journals including relevant research relating to the aim of this thesis are identified. In order not to limit further searches to these journals, but to address a broader field here as well, the comprehensive databases of the publishers were scanned using the same set of keywords. The initial review of extant literature started with the general real estate area and blockchain technology. However, real estate is a broad term that can be distinguished between residential (private property market) and commercial real estate (corporate assets and buildings market). The focus has been set to explore real estate market, where the central product is a written contract between two parties (buyer and seller).

Step 2: Comprehensive Search: Based on the traditional real estate due-diligence process and legal aspects in Switzerland (Koller, 1983), the identification of the keywords has been carried out as an iterative process. Each keyword has been tested in the databases and relevant synonyms have been identified. This led to a specification of *real estate* towards commercial real estate. Table 2-1 lists the identified keywords and search strings used.

Table 2-1. Review Keywords and Search Strings

Identification of initial keywords
Real estate
Commercial real estate
Commercial real estate Contract
Commercial real estate Contract Transaction
Technology
Blockchain Technology
Smart Contract
Smart Contract on Ethereum
Search strings
Real estate
Real estate *Commercial* OR *Corporate*
Real estate *Commercial* OR *Corporate* AND *Contract*
Real estate *Commercial* OR *Corporate* AND *Contract* AND *Transaction*
Real estate AND *Blockchain*
Real estate AND *Blockchain* *Commercial* OR *Corporate*
Real estate AND *Blockchain* *Commercial* OR *Corporate* AND *Contract*
Real estate AND *Blockchain* *Commercial* OR *Corporate* AND *Contract* AND *Transaction*

The initial literature research was conducted in Google Scholar to preliminary verify the feasibility of the literature review with the key word combination “real estate blockchain Technology”, which resulted into the search string *real estate* AND *blockchain* leading to 7,600 results. Therefore, the initial search round has considered solely blockchain technology and the real estate. After careful analysis in line with the research aim and repeating results, the database has been changed to Scopus for recreational and stable variants for future evaluation within the commercial real estate and specifically by introducing the *Smart Contract* to provide a novel solution for the *commercial real estate contract transaction* on a global, open-source platform for decentralized applications, Ethereum platform since it is allowed to program a certain business logic, transfer digital value by to writing a function to get the Ethereum balance of a wallet address and access anytime and anywhere by the computers running the protocol (e.g. Ethereum nodes). The identified key words have resulted in various number of hits – for example real estate (22046), commercial real estate (2778), commercial “OR” corporate real estate contract “OR” real estate transaction (309), commercial “OR” corporate real estate contract real estate transaction (93), real estate blockchain (57) and commercial real estate blockchain transaction (23). Subsequently, by selecting a given research aim was the prerequisite for the identified and applied inclusion to make sure that the search criteria’s can be traced in a verifiable and reproducible way. To summarize the reasoning for these keywords linked to commercial real estate, we see that fintech is highly dependent on novel technologies. Global fintech organizations have been on the rise for the previous several decades all over the world and disrupted many industries with a traditional footprint where changes in business models, changes in financial rules or customer demand for financial products and services have been left unmet. The technologies that enabled these disruptions to the most significant degree are blockchain technology and smart contracts, therefore forming the linked keywords in the search strings.

Steps 3 and 4: Precise title and abstract screening: to derive explicit selection criteria and reduce to number o results to those that are relevant in the context of this thesis First, the following inclusion criteria are applied: 1) publications of any year, 2) peer-reviewed journals and 3) English language publications. Second, the thesis delineates certain exclusion criteria such as keywords appeared only in the reference list and for the keywords that appeared in an unconnected manner that does not relate to the aim of this research. Finally, the journals were evaluated on the quality based on criteria-based aggregation of the content and non-academic content is excluded due to poor quality or outdated articles such as informal interviews, book reviews or other non-academic formats. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are listed in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications of any years • Peer-reviewed journals • Published in the English language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keywords appeared only in the reference list • Keywords appeared in an unconnected manner that does not relate to the aim of this research • Content was either of poor quality or outdated • Articles were interviews, book reviews or other non-academic formats

Step 5: Evaluation: The remaining papers have been evaluated with regards to their quality. The remaining 51 articles were deemed highly relevant in the context of this thesis, of which 23 are published in peer-reviewed journals, dealing with the issue of the blockchain technology application in the commercial real estate. those are clustered in four areas, (i) economics (finance and investments), (ii) real estate process, (iii) technology, and (iv) legal aspects.

Steps 6 and 7: Extraction, Synthesis, and Reporting: The initial search string *real estate* has generated 22,046 literature items (articles, books, conference papers, peer-review journals) that are illustrated in Figure 2-3. The combination of real estate and blockchain showed 7,600 results and only 51 relevant journals and conference papers, where only 23 final peer-reviewed articles have been published and those appear in the final synthesis part.

Figure 2-3. Systematic Literature Review

Table 2-3 provides an overview of the results of the systematic literature review (SLR) searching database Scopus. After the completion of this process, 51 articles have been considered to be highly relevant and thus explicitly 23 final peer-reviewed articles synthesized deal with the issue of the blockchain technology application in the commercial real estate which

helped to produce a systematic literature review out from 22,046 “real estate” publications, find 1897 publications about real estate and blockchain technology, 2778 publications about the corporate and commercial real estate industry segment, reduce further down to 331 publication about the corporate and commercial real estate and blockchain technology, reduce further down to 93 publication about the corporate and commercial real estate contracts and apply the inclusion and exclusion criteria for publications of any year, peer-reviewed journals, English language publications and select a final pool of 51 relevant journals and 23 peer-reviewed journals concretely dealing with the Ph.D. Problem statements and critically appraise relevant synthesising their content of connections and patterns that have not been produced previously (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009).

Table 2-3. Key Word Analysis

Variant	Date of Search	Search String	Inclusion Criteria	Total number (Scopus)
1	10.05.2020	TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate)	publications of any year English language publications	22,046
2	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (commercial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (corporate))	publications of any year English language publications	2,778
3	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (commercial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (corporate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (contract) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (transaction))	publications of any year English language publications	309
4	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (commercial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (corporate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (contract))	publications of any year English language publications	93
5	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (technology))	publications of any year English language publications	1,897
6	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (blockchain) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (smart))	publications of any year English language publications	331
7	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (blockchain))	publications of any year English language publications	57
8	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (blocking) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (transaction))	publications of any year English language publications	33
9	10.05.2020	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (real AND estate) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (blocking) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (transaction))	publications of any year peer-reviewed journals English language publications	23

2.3.2 Synthesis – Criteria-based Aggregation

This section lays out the systematic analysis of the papers that have been identified to be of high relevance for this thesis based on the criteria set out in the previous sections of this chapter. These are summarised and categorised (see Table 2-4) as (i) business models, (ii) real estate, (iii) developments in commercial real estate processes (iv) legal aspects and (v) blockchain.

Table 2-4. Systematic Literature Review - Synthesis

ID	Authors	Year	Real estate - Research area	Diagnosis factors (Literature review)	Selection criteria	Source
1	Devaney and Scofield	2013	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate commercial investment process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
2	Grossman and Miller	1988	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate process for the investors	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
3	Bond	2007	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate transaction cost	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
4	Baum	2017	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate process for mortgage-backed securities	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
5	Börlg,Nägell	2019	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate selling process (Due-Diligence)	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
6	Montgomery, N., Squires, G., Syed, I.	2018	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate process strategy	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
7	Hoxha, V., Sad ku, S.	2019	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate - traditional process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
8	Krupa, K.S., Akhil, M.S.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Revolution of Real estate Smart Contract	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
9	Dixit et al., 2019	2018	Real estate - Future process	Real estate integration process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
10	Gilts, Combs and Yin	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process localisation concepts	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
11	Wanigarathna et al.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process of commercial and residential types	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
12	Haugbelle and Ralfsøe	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process of commercial and residential types	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
13	Bröchner, Haugen and Lindkvist	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process inspection management	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
14	Mannino, Dejaco and Re Ceconi	2021	Real estate - Future process	Building and Construction	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
15	Esoudero et al.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process urbanisation and spacial process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
16	Xie,Gong	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate geographical spatial economics	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
17	Annervaz, George	2016	Real estate - Future process	Real estate machine learning process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
18	Glock	2018	Real estate - Future process	Real estate lifecycle transformation	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
19	Thiliri and Wickramarachchi	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate analytic network process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
20	Jyhä, Remy, and Arkesteijn	2019	Real estate - Future process	Commercial Real estate (CRE) process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
21	Hoxha, V., Sad ku, S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate - Process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
22	Abdelhamid, M., Hassan, G.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate state of the art	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
23	Somi S. Thota	2019	Real estate - Future process	Modern scientific Real estate process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
24	Abdelhamid, M., Hassan, G.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate state of the art process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
25	Dramé-Malgné, S., Laurent, M., Castillo, L., Ganem, H.	2018	Real estate - Future process	Real estate Third Party Costs	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
26	Avantaggiato, M., Gallo, P.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate trust for the contracts	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
27	Awalu, I.L., Kook, P.H., Um, J.S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate election process	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
28	D Justra, M.	2017	Business Models	Business Model - Commercial Real estate	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
29	Grover, Kar, Janssen	2019	Business Models	Business Model diffusion	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
30	Ostenwalder	2019	Business Models	Business model - digital ecosystem - matrix elements	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
31	Veuger, J.	2018	Business Models	Business model - digital ecosystem - interviews viable real estate economy	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
32	Geng, Huang	2019	Business Models	Business model - digital concepts	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
33	Morkunas	2019	Business Models	Business model measurement	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
34	Shahab and Allam	2020	Business Models	Business model - tradeable permit schemes	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
35	Montecchi, Pianger	2019	Business Models	Business model - supply chain	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
36	Morkunas, Paschen, Boon	2019	Business Models	Business model value creation- high value-added activities	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
37	Chen	2017	Business Models	New business models of crypto-currency platforms and token platforms	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
38	E, S.K., Talasila, V., Pasumarthy, R.	2019	Business Models	Search for a favourable location	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
39	Montgomery, N., Squires, G., Syed, I.	2018	Business Models	Finance and Investment- Systematical Literature Review (SLR)	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
40	Nasarre-Aznar, S.	2018	Business Models	Finance and Investment- Collaborative housing and blockchain	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
41	Holsbergen, M., Chan, J., Peko, G., Sundaram, D.	2019	Business Models	Assymmetric Information	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
42	Kalyuzhnova, N.	2018	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
43	Latiff, S., Zhang, Y., Cheng, L.-C.	2019	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
44	Dramé-Malgné, S., Laurent, M., Castillo, L., Ganem, H.	2018	Business Models	Real estate Third Party Costs	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus

45	Hoksbergen, M., Chan, J., Peko, G., Sundaram, D.	2019	Business Models	Assymmetric information	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
46	Kalyuzhnova, N.	2018	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
47	Latifi, S., Zhang, Y., Cheng, L.-C.	2019	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
48	Pokrovskaja, N., Khansuvarova, T., Khansuvarov, R.	2018	Business Models	Business model and transaction costs	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
49	E, S.K., Talasila, V., Pasumarthy, R.	2019	Transaction Costs	Search for a favourable location	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
50	Baker	2016	Finance and Investment	Finance and investment models	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
51	Cumming and Johan	2019	Finance and Investment	Finance and investment and crowdfunding models	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
52	Zhang and Li	2021	Finance and Investment	Finance and investment cryptocurrence returns	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
53	Kim and Hong	2017	Finance and Investment	Finance P2P interaction	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
54	Al Shami and Kanjo	2019	Finance and Investment	Finance and Real estate asset valuation	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
55	Konashevych, 2020a	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property cross-border transactions	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
56	Konashevych, 2020b	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property rights	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
57	Konashevych, 2020c	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property constraints	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
58	Coinschedule	2021	Finance and Investment	Finance analysis of ICO and Token prices	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
59	Agarwal et al.	2020	Technology	Finance housing market	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
60	Srinivasan and Venkatraman	2018	Technology	Finance platform and market places	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
61	Hautala, Järvenpää and Puukinen	2017	Technology	Business Information Modelling (BIM)- planning and execution	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
62	Perez and Espinoza	2017	Technology	Business Information Modelling (BIM) - building construction processes	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
63	Yalcinkaya and Singh	2018	Technology	BIM-integrated search platform	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
64	Halmetoja	2019	Technology	BIM Conditions data model	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
65	Mannino, Dejaco and Re Ceconi, 2021)	2021	Technology	BIM industry applications	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
66	Nasarre-Aznar, S.	2018	Technology	Finance and Investment- Collaborative housing and blockchain	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
67	Ullah and Sepasgozar	2018	Technology	Technology digital process drivers	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
68	Zhan et al.	2019	Technology	Image classification	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
69	Wouda, H.P., Opendakker, R.	2019	Technology	Information Systems-Design of the Blockchain Systems	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
70	Aamir et. Al	2020	Technology	Smart cities technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
71	Yadav, Agrawal and Kushwaha	2021	Technology	Trusted nodes consensus mechanism	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
72	Peisl, T., Shah, B.	2019	Technology	Impact of the blockchain on the employees	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
73	Bartolomeu, P.C., Ferreira, J.	2018	Technology	Application of Wireless Real estate	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
74	Ciatto, G., Bosello, M., Mariani, S., Omicini, A.	2019	Technology	Application of Blockchain	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
75	Firica, O.	2017	Technology	Real estate transformation	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
76	Li, M., Shen, L., Huang, G.Q.	2019	Technology	Blockchain Technology, Real estate logistics service	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
77	Mehendale, D.K., Masurekar, R.S., Patil, H.V.	2019	Technology	Implications of block chain in real estate industry	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
78	Swan, M.	2018	Technology	Blockchain Information Systems- Design	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
79	Tilbury, J.L., De La Rey, E., Van Der Schyff, K.	2019	Technology	study examines two approaches to executing real estate transactions	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
80	Wouda, H.P., Opendakker, R.	2019	Technology	Information Systems-Design	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
81	Dakhli, Z., Lathaj, Z., Mossman, A.	2019	Technology	Building and Construction	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
82	Epiphaniou, G., Daly, H., Al-Khateeb, H.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
83	Janowicz, K., Regalia, B., Hitzler, P., Mai, G., De becuque, S., Fröhlich, M., Martinent, P., Lazarus, T.	2018	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
84	Krupa, K.S., Akhil, M.S.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger (1) Technologyand Smart Contracts for the Real estate	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
85	Xu, Z., Van, C.B., Jiao, T., Wen, S., Wang, Q., Xiang, Y.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
86	Yeasmin, S., Baig, A.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
87	Morkunas	2019	Technology	Modern real estate on Blockchain technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
88	Montgomery, N., Squires, G., Syed, I.	2018	Technology	Finance and Investment- Systematical Literature Review (SLR)	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
89	Karamitsos, I., Papadaki, M. and Barghuthi, N.	2019	Technology	Blockchain (1) Technologyimplementation for the Real estate Tenant model	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
90	Mashatan, A., Roberts, Z.	2017	Technology	Use cases for the decentralized applications (DApps)	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
91	Xu, Z., Jiao, T., Yang, L., Liu, D., Wen, S., Xiang, Y.	2020	Technology	Use cases for the decentralized applications (DApps)	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus

92	Ganter, M., Lützkendorf, T.	2019	Technology	Real estate "D.N.A." and "building passport"	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
93	Vidhyalakshmi, V.S., Geetha, A., Sobitha Ahila, S.	2019	Technology	Information Systems- Implementation	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
94	Soni, S., Bhushan, B.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
95	Terzi, S., Zacharaki, A., Nizamis, A., Volis, K., Ioannidis, D., Tzovaras, D., Stamelos, I.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
96	Vokerla, R.R., Shanmugam, B., Azam, S., Karim, A., Boer, F.D., Jonkman, M., Faisal, F.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
97	Ganter, M., Lützkendorf, T.	2019	Sustainability	Sustainability of the Real estate	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
98	Store-Valen/Busen	2019	Sustainability	Sustainability and climate use cases	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
99	Ploeger et al.	2019	Sustainability	Operational sustainability	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
100	Redlein and Grasl	2018	Sustainability	Smart Building Technology for sustainability	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
101	Collins	2019	Sustainability	Green buildings technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
102	Koch, Hansen, Jacobsen	2019	Sustainability	Facility management technology	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
103	Tezel and Girtli	2019	Sustainability	Environmental sustainability tools	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
104	Kaczorowska, M.	2019	Legal Aspects	Land Registry possibilities and challenges	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
105	Konashvych, O.	2019	Legal Aspects	Land Registry - titles conversion into tokens	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
106	Spielman, A.	2016	Legal Aspects	Legal aspect-recording property titles	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
107	Dobrauz	2018	Legal Aspects	Legal aspects specific country - worldwide analysis	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus
108	Garcia-Teruel, R.M.	2020	Legal Aspects	Legal aspects in line with EU legislation	Criteria-based aggregation	Scopus

Steps 8: Utilization: The systematic analysis results of in reporting the research gaps this thesis seeks to address the research gaps. The review of extant literature for blockchain real estate has shed light that the adoption of blockchain technology in the real estate is inevitable on that the real estate investment process could be translated into decentralized store of information (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018), leverage the effect of crowdfunding (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018), digital signature based on the cryptography (Morabito, 2017), transaction workflow (Thota, 2019), faster cash settlements but also auto-execution of Smart Contracts (Rahmadika and Rhee, 2018), application of blockchain improvements in efficiency, transparency and therefore trust (Veuger, 2018; 2020; Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019) and translated into the practical semantic models Blockchain-Enabled Multiple Listing Service (MLS) (Krupa and Akhil, 2019).

2.3.3 Current and Future States of Swiss Real Estate Processes

The commercial real estate is a highly specific asset: heterogeneous, indivisible and with less information transparency than most other commonly held investment assets (Devaney and Scofield, 2013). Therefore, commercial real estate is a complex process where various stakeholders cause information asymmetry which result into commercial high costs and extended time taken to transact real estate between seller and buyer, culminate to negatively affect the liquidity of the asset and results into inherent risk for the commercial real estate final investor as originally concluded by Grossman and Miller (1988). Real estate markets have the inherent asymmetries and reduce transaction risk often comes through intermediaries (brokers/agents) who work between and on behalf of investment firms. However,

intermediaries can represent a substantial transaction cost. (Bond *et al.*, 2007). The real estate consists of asset classes of residential and commercial assets – either directly, through property funds or real estate investment trusts or indirectly, through mortgage-backed securities or whole mortgages (Baum, 2017). The current Swiss commercial real estate process (is a highly complex process (See Figure 2-4). Switzerland's real estate market has been chosen due to focus of foreign investors and people moving to this country. Switzerland's central location, its desirability as a corporate headquarters location and country of residence, has caused a rise in the demand for real estate (Bürgi and Nägeli, 2019)

Figure 2-4. Swiss commercial real estate selling process (Bürgi and Nägeli, 2019)

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The criteria-based aggregation continues to determine a current real estate process based on the due diligence based on the process- modern scientific real estate process (Thota, 2019) and practical real estate process run by due-diligence simulation (Krupa and Akhil, 2019).

First, the real estate process cycles has its own integration process concepts by Dixit *et al.*, (2019) and franchise management and real estate localization concepts (Gillis, Combs and Yin, 2018) whereas the maintenance management for health-care facilities (Wanigarathna *et al.*, 2019). The real estate models for such explanatory purpose, practical examples have been given to demonstrate the product life cycle costs based on the case studies of office buildings (Haugbølle and Raffnsøe, 2019) which might lead to reorganization of real estate structures

and deploy digital facility management autonomous facility and inspection management (Bröchner, Haugen and Lindkvist, 2019).

The real estate geography transformed due to digital spatial economics such as diffuse processes of urbanization and fragmented urban structures (Escudero, 2019), commercial real estate development process of geographical space in distinct scales driven by accumulation of capital (Xie and Gong, 2019). The digitalization of spatial economics enabled to automate legal knowledge work process using machine learning (Annervaz and George, 2016). Furthermore, the digital transformation adoption happens across the whole value chain within the asset life cycle from design to operation and maintenance. The use of modern information technologies in the construction sector is demonstrably less widespread than in other industries (Glock, 2018).

Digital technologies are involved throughout the value chain and applied for planning, design, execution, supervision and maintenance constantly improving and simplifying. (Glock, 2018). The modern application of analytic network process (Thilini and Wickramaarachchi 2019) shortens real estate and construction life cycles, specifically commercial real estate (Jylhä, Remøy, and Arkesteijn, 2019). One of the modern approaches (see Figure 2-5) has shed light on a modern commercial real estate process (Krupa and Maganali, 2019, p. 20) where all the stakeholders are noted. Those stakeholders tend to have typical Real estate process between seller, buyer, Real estate agent, notary lawyer, mortgage bank, municipality land registry interact on separate ledgers as of each stakeholder (Krupa and Akhil, 2019).

Figure 2-5. Modern commercial real estate processes (Source: Krupa and Akhil, 2019)

Therefore, the real estate processes can lead to redundancies such as data collection, advertisement, agreement, property examination, contract preparation, pre-contracting, contract signing, money transfer and final registration are handled separately with generation of transaction costs for each of the stakeholder. The transaction cost start with the origination, funding and till after-sales service of the commercial real estate of sharing reference data, e.g. credit liquidity checks (Thota, 2019). Figure 2-6 illustrates the steps in commercial real estate investment process on the blockchain.

Figure 2-6. Steps in commercial real estate investment process on the blockchain (source: Thota, 2019)

In terms of business requirements of the commercial real estate contracts, a comparison between traditional and modern real state processes is provided in Table 2-5.

Table 2-5. Business Requirements of the Commercial Real Estate Contract

Step	Traditional real state process (Bürgi/Nägeli, 2019)	Modern commercial real estate Process (Krupa and Maganali, 2019)
1	Systematic Real estate market assessment is prepared prior to purchase with a letter of intent with a purpose of establishing a purchase price	Property Search
2	Property inspections and visit -Market Legal, Tax, Technical and Environmental inspections are conducted to identify potential risks and opportunities	Property Visit and Inspection
3	Risks assessments of transaction conditions customary warranty waivers require due diligence warranty and risk associated with site contamination born by buyer	Risk assessment and Negotiations
4	Corporate valuation is performed determining whether parties to the contract negotiations are in positions of strength or weakness	Due Diligence

5	Leasing agreement	Lease agreement using smart contracts
6	Decision-making process – contract is rejected, or contract is signed	Contract signature
7	Traditional asset buy-side - vendor side deal	Automated Payments using Smart Contracts

In this context, a smart contract could use codification potential and create standardisation of workflow for a property search (1) enabled by the smart contract and inspection verification process for each transaction between buyer and seller to enhance the current transaction process (2) and conduct the risk assessment (3) by communicating within the P2P network. Subsequently, the due-diligence (4) process of the property evaluation is secured periodically lease agreements (5) are assured by the blockchain smart contract where the digital signature is immutable written in the data storage on the chain. The periodical payments are possible by the leveraging crypto-currency exchange and payment terms (6). For better explanatory reasons, the pilot use case was conducted based on the example of object office building which was connected to the common blockchain database (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019). Therefore, quality of the data was outlined as the key prerequisite for the standardised data transmission of the transaction processes. Fintech has led to the growth of crowdfunding, which became a challenge to traditional banking models in terms of the innovative models. Further, recent academic research recommends applying the permissionless network to the data output to the “hashed” blocks on the chain (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018). Smart contracts would also allow to fractionalise ownership and investment liquidity in a traditionally high barrier to entry industry where Investors could purchase tokens based on fiat currencies. The most suitable model for real estate tokens has been designed by Karamitsos (2018) for the commercial real estate smart contract. The model has been divided in three parts: the logic, internal views, and storage. The three-part approach resolves the structural problem in Ethereum Smart Contracts: once you deploy a contract you can’t change anymore and stuck with hardcoded values on contract which causes serious security issue and might be hacked because of very simple coding mistakes (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

2.3.4 Business Models

The systematic aggregation analysis starts with a commercial real estate business (Dijkstra, 2017) and qualitative factors affecting the real estate market readiness and testing the diffusion of blockchain technology (Grover, Kar and Janssen, 2019). Blockchain technology is a potential disruptor where notaries and brokers will be in the future in a single ecosystem with impact on property owners, financiers, users, builders, brokers, notaries, and the land registry. The real estate world is therefore at a turning point of transition: a profound and irreversible

tilting of (real estate) systems in society, and 'technological opportunities the increasing complexity of modern hardware and software platform which might lead to generation of blockchain and Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystems (Geng and Huang, 2019). To understand new business model requirements, Morkunas (2019) has derived a logic how to measure blockchain impact on the business models that used qualitative measurement as a research methodology with nine major categories. Osterwalder (2013) concluded that there are nine essential parts of a value creation in a visual template termed the “Business Model Canvas” (see Figure 2-7). The canvas is usually printed on A0 size sheet with sections for each of the model’ elements and thus serves as a tool to explore and assess the feasibility of a business model (Osterwalder et al., 2010; Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013).

Figure 2-7. Business model canvas (source: Stragyzer.com)

The research approach of the underlying this study provides a blue-print of how each of the nine elements can be affected by blockchain technologies and illustrate the impacts with a practical use case example from real estate – commercial contract where the human-based contract will be compared with the machine based smart contract.

Key partnerships: The key partnerships are defined as *“the network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work”* (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013, p. 38). It is about the relations between the suppliers and partners such as strategic alliances such as strategic alliances, joint ventures, or buyer-supplier relationships to ensure reliable supplies. The Economy of Scale argument could be achieved if the fix costs will be reduced by deploying multiple stakeholders on the sharing infrastructure. Here is a clear example how the decentralized blockchain network could entail the disintermediation of traditional intermediaries (e.g. banks, notaries, currency exchanges, land registry, municipal bank). Additionally, the use of blockchain can also enable the addition of new partners in the Real estate such as technology companies that develop application programming interfaces (APIs) and software development kits (SDKs), and maintain the transactional algorithms, therefore strengthening and extending supply chains– in our case the Real estate supply chain (Morkunas, 2019, p. 300) (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013), (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019). Second category deals with the transaction cost value drivers – cost structure. The cost structure *“describes all costs incurred to operate a business model”* (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013, p. 40). Blockchain implementations can reduce transaction costs such as negotiation costs and search costs, and eliminate the costs of intermediaries and reducing transaction costs of tradable permit schemes using Blockchain Smart contracts (Shahab and Allam, 2020).

Distribution channels: describe *“how a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition”* (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013, p. 26). Through simplification of doing business on the blockchain-network distribution channels may be transformed on the decentralized storage such as the company’s own sales force, website, or stores, or the channels may be the stores of retailers or wholesalers and cut the “middleman”. The “middleman” are the middle parties which may become disintermediated. Within the real estate contract market, the transactions could be facilitated by smart contracts and achieved by by removing the requirement for time and personnel required to complete a validity check or a transaction. Also, new types of channels generate additional synergies in the organisation (e.g., bysharing common code to strengthen a supply chain (Montecchi, Plangger and Etter, 2019).

Customer segments: Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013, p. 20) defined customer segments as *“the different groups of people or organizations that an enterprise aims to reach and serve.”* Potential Real estate buyers or seller customers could operate on the Blockchain Platform to buy or sell Real estate and could already gain from the Blockchain Technology by testing pilot

projects to purchase or sell homes powered by Chroma Way in Sweden or Crowdhouse in Switzerland (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019)

Key resources and key activities: Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013, p. 34) defined key resources as *“the most important assets required to make a business model work.”* Resources (e.g., financial, material, intellectual, human) are the key component for the value proposition (Osterwald, 2013; Morkunas, 2019). Osterwald (2013) describes key activities as those activities which are mandatory for the value creation. This might encompass how a firm transforms the resources into high value added for the organization – so called “value creation” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013; Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019).

The first aspect of resources covers the opportunity to make resources more flexible, which allows firms to engage the resources rather flexible “on-demand” and to access resources only when required, instead of the traditional fixed cost structure ownership. One of the potential examples is the public (permissionless blockchain) is especially applicable for the public blockchain technologies regarding the P2P sharing economy can be fully realised. Any stakeholder can transact with another party in a P2P network where any transaction could be realised once two parties have agreed, and the miner has approved the immutable transaction. Similarly, as under cloud scenarios, firms could replace investments in “On-Premises” Server and IT infrastructure and rather set up a public blockchains with a shared network for shared resources and processes. Furthermore, both applications of public permissionless and private blockchains enable firms to streamline and automate processes that were previously human kind and manually executed and enabling additional capacity for human resources to focus on high value-added activities. (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019).

Several examples have been discussed in the literature review about how repetitive work such as documentation, verification, audit reporting. In this respect, the execution of human Real estate contract falls under the repetitive and human-based tasks category where manual errors might occur. By using the example of smart contracts in real estate transactions, resources such as human capital (e.g., knowledge, skills, experience) and physical capital (assets) are provided by the trans-acting parties while blockchain technologies facilitate the P2P exchange of these re-sources.

Revenue stream: this element represents: *“The cash that a company generates from each customer segment. There are two kinds of revenue streams...from ongoing payments to either deliver a value proposition to customers or provide post-purchase customer support”*

Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013, p. 30). In this regard, the revenue stream brings the idea of the initial coin offerings and respective tokens. Initially, blockchain tokens could be described as ‘digital coin shares’ and is subject to a different character such as currencies, securities, utilities, properties, loyalty points, and gift certificates (Buterin, 2014b). Blockchain tokens have been classified by the legal authority as provided below in the chapter. Furthermore, the tokens could be exchanged – buy and sell on the common platform between parties without the involvement of a central authority and can be traded globally on the digital crypto-currency platforms (Chen, 2017).

2.3.5 Finance and Investment, Risk Management and Tokenisation concepts

While the idea of crowdfunding has been already applied for the classical finance, today the trend of crowdfunding becomes more common to real estate investors. The idea of customer-centred sharing-economy has a big potential to restructure real estate investment models (Baker, 2016) and particularly type of crowdfunding that has been at the forefront of the debate for increased regulation and further analysed on cases, facts and insights (Cumming and Johan, 2019).

There are three key parties involved in the real estate crowdfunding process: (i) the project initiator (the “company” or “borrower”) who proposes the idea and/or project to be funded; (ii) individuals or groups (the “investors”) who support the idea; and (iii) a moderating organisation (the "real estate platform") that brings the parties together to launch the idea (Baker, 2016). Real estate platforms (see Figure 2.8) belong to asset-backed security platforms which pool together investors, cumulate the investment amount and finance pre-vetted projects. Ultimately, the investors could achieve secured passive income with relatively small investments.

Figure 2-8. Real estate platform (source: Baker, 2016)

The commercial real estate industry has its primary scope on the commercial investment with a high-risk and high-return economic valuation, however the liquidity risk tends to be higher of those expected cryptocurrency returns (Zhang and Li, 2021). With the expansion of real estate investing via the Internet, those with more moderate investment funds have access to deals

that have historically been reserved for those with deeper pockets. Crowdfunding removes the complexities of investing and makes the transactional contracts available to any lenders and borrowers by cutting the intermediaries that enables direct P2P interaction. A study by Kim and Hong (2017) reports that this simplifies the application process for P2P crowdfunding to the maximum extent possible and proposes a secure system with reinforced security authentication for transparent borrowers to transact with others behaviour. However, there is concern that crowdfunding might be the underlying real estate value which might appreciate or depreciate. While real estate crowdfunding is used for investing in short-term debt (three years or less) and long-term equity (over five years), the investments and precise real estate valuation due to spread of smart phones sensor technologies (Al Shami and Kanjo, 2019).

Tokens are structured for the following purposes, (i) fundraising, (ii) investing, (iii) community building, or (iv) open sourcing (Chen, 2017). Revenue streams of tokens based on blockchain technology without and with token are listed in Table 2-6.

Table 2-6. Revenue streams of tokens based on blockchain technology (Chen, 2017, p. 569)

	Without Tokens	With Tokens
Fundraising	Entrepreneurs may raise funds from angel investors or venture capitalists. Entrepreneurs may raise funds from the public through crowdfunding.	Entrepreneurs can raise funds directly from investors across the globe. Entrepreneurs can raise funds from the public through initial coin offerings.
Investing	Average investors have few opportunities to invest in promising early-stage ventures. Investors have limited liquidity with private company investments.	Average investors can have almost equal opportunities to invest in early-stage ventures across the globe through blockchain tokens. Investors enjoy almost immediate liquidity with blockchain tokens.
Community Building	Platforms may start to appeal to users when they enjoy strong network effects. Platforms may start to appeal to complementors when they enjoy strong network effects.	Platforms can reward early adopters with tokens, compensating for the lack of network effects. Platforms can reward early complementors with tokens, compensating for the lack of network effects.
Open Sourcing	Open-source projects may fund their continued development through donations. Open-source projects usually do not share their success with core developers.	Open-source projects can fund their continued development through token sales. Open-source projects can share their success with core developers through tokens.

Subsequently, those tokens are used for the real estate security property tokenisation where the titles leverage the real estate asset value as concluded by the general concept of real estate tokenisation on blockchain benefits of property rights and constraints (Konashevych, 2020c). (Konashevych, 2020a)

Fourth, previous studies have not considered the real estate finance to calculate complex commercial real estate business models such as real-time calculation of return on investment over a building's life cycle (Zhang and Li, 2014). Hence, new theories for risk management in the commercial real estate development have been identified such as analytic network process for risks assessment in commercial real estate development (Chen and Khumpaisal, 2009). The investment decisions became more precise due to analytic hierarchy process (Liu and Zhong, 2014) and calculation real estate prices based on Gaussian process regression for price predictions (Crosby and Davis 2016) as well as risk assessment of sale-leaseback-based securities (Chen and Li, 2016). The traditional legal concept of the Lien and the Title theory have its strengths and weaknesses but also opportunities and chances to integrate with the modern technology of tokens for considerable diminishing of high real estate prices market barriers and generate additional transaction cost savings.

On the one hand, a title is evidence of ownership which represents the property rights of a real estate, equivalent to a legally recognised real estate on paper (e.g. land, for example). On the other hand, a crypto-token is a technology that has the same purposes – the token could foster innovation in terms of transparent 'cadastre' – a ledger for ownership structure, transactional data such as repairs and maintenance activities and prove ownership of the token-holder. The token-integration could reduce the cycle time of the verification process, decrease administrative tasks, and reduce a potential loss of information. Furthermore, the integration of numerous third-party stakeholders and providers tends would bring simultaneous update on blockchain ledger and keep the single source of truth (Deloitte, 2019)

The mortgage loans landscape is highly diversified between the countries in the international comparison. In some countries, title deeds must be acknowledged, some other countries the title deeds must be acknowledged before a notary, in some before other authorized persons, and recorded in the public registry. Thus, the use of tokens for real estate would systematically converge the legislative changes among the countries into the new holistic system with new procedures of acknowledgement and recording on the blockchain ledger. The title can be divisible, that is, what in the language of law means co-ownership, joint ownership, community property (also known as marital property) and some other concepts that exist in different jurisdictions. The challenge for the mortgage tokens is a lack of regulation in the existing laws whereas the titles of real estate have a long tradition and legacy of regulation. That is why transactions that are made with real estate tokens will not have any legal consequences (Konashevych, 2020a), (Konashevych, 2020c). The term Security Token Offering (STO) is

commonly used for raising capital by issuing asset tokens qualifying as securities (hereinafter “securitytokens”). Security tokens may represent a share in a company or an investment fund or one or several specific (financial) claims against the issuer. STOs are therefore from a regulatory perspective more complex than a utility token offering. For example, some security tokens promise a share of future company earnings or a share in future turnover. If a token is classified as a security, this can have various regulatory implications depending on the tokenomics and the business model of the issuer (PWC, 2019)

In its “Guidelines for enquiries regarding the regulatory framework for in Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs)” (“ICO-Guidelines”) of February 2018, the Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority (FINMA) classified tokens issued in ICOs as either asset, utility or payment tokens or a combination thereof hybrid. The Blockchain revenue stream has brought a new way of finance and innovative ventures. The most common type of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is the Blockchain Technology and the recent trend of the blockchain-enabled crowdfunding in a form of Initial Coin Offering (ICO) as ‘crowdsale’ or ‘token sale’. ICOs are a very recent phenomenon whereas the first ICO was performed in July 2013 by Mastercoin, a digital cryptocurrency on the first generation of Bitcoins network (Fisch, 2019). Since the first ICO, thousands of ICOs have followed and counted as of February 2019 with started sales of 1010 Tokens and Total raise funding for the period of 2018-2019 USD 19,721,893,570.00 USD (Coinschedule, 2019). The categories by amount raised are illustrated in Figure 2-9 (Coinschedule, 2019).

Figure 2-9. Categories by amount raised.

2.3.6 Real Estate Technology Innovations

Information technology (IT) innovation has shifted old-fashioned Real estate to Internet-based, virtual real estate and systematically discussed in the digital market (Zhu and Liu, 2021). The sharing economy enabled Buyer/ Seller to have a bilateral P2P interaction and created various search platforms- information advantage in housing markets (Agarwal *et al.*, 2018), service agent marketplaces – intermediaries' platforms (Srinivasan and Venkatraman, 2018). Furthermore, shared economy allowed to have direct transaction management by registering transaction processes or even to bilaterally sign the contracts by electronic Signature – a DNA passport of a real estate object provided by Blockchain Technology and create new innovative crowdfunding real estate ecosystem (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018) and building trust (Veuger, 2018).

Special attention is put to digital platforms which changed planning and construction process, where progress is accelerated execution (Hautala, Järvenpää and Pulkkinen, 2017) such as Building Information Modelling (BIM). First, the Building Information Modelling (BIM) is not only a new technology - it's a completely new way of working, which completely change the planning and execution (Hautala, Järvenpää and Pulkkinen, 2017) pp. 340-34). Consequently, while digital platforms (e.g. BIM) provided previously architect view of 3 D with the modern additional dimension for time and costs (5D) which enabled to building and construction commercial building construction processes, segregation, and housing (Perez and Espinoza, 2017). BIM is widely becoming a common methodology used on construction projects with benefits and risks a part of day to day understanding in the built environment. In this context, BIM can be applied over set of tools and techniques that support enhanced collaboration among the project stakeholders and especially visual digitalisation as discussed in two articles: a BIM-integrated visual search and information management platform extension (Yalcinkaya and Singh, 2018). Halmetoja (2019) describe a certain case study of real estate information systems which was implemented in practice and based on a conditions data model (Halmetoja, 2019). Practical examples were given by Zhan (2019) where he displayed how the housing inspection–repair process can be supported by BIM combined with image classification recent BIM applications (Mannino, Dejacco and Re Cecconi, 2021).The result is the efficient inspection-repair management process and image classification (Zhan *et al.*, 2019), digital process drivers (Ullah and Sepasgozar, 2018) and provide new features for the smart cities (Aamir *et al.*, 2020) and future land transaction systems with trusted nodes consensus mechanism (Yadav, Agrawal and Kushwaha, 2021).

2.3.7 Fundamentals of Blockchain Technology

Blockchain is broadly described as a distributed database that records transactions shared among participating parties (Zhao et al., 2016). It operates as a decentralized digital ledger that allows transacting parties to exchange ownership of digitally represented assets in real-time through an immutable, P-2-P system without intermediaries (Morkunas et al., 2019).

Since the database is maintained by a network of computers that verify transactions in real-time before approval, blockchain provides a high level of transparency (Akram et al., 2020; Morkunas et al., 2019) and fosters trust (Schweizer et al., 2017). Additional benefits include enhanced security through end-to-end encryption (Atlam et al., 2018); improved speed and traceability (Hughes et al., 2019); as well as greater transparency, auditability (Wang et al., 2019), and data integrity (Casino et al., 2019).

Blockchain, as a distributed ledger, records ownership and tracks the full history of all past transactions, providing a transparent and comprehensive record of asset exchanges (see Figure 2-10). Figure 2-10 illustrates the process workflow where input data such as attachment documents, data entries are converted to the data output to the “hashed” blocks on the chain. By eliminating the need for intermediaries, blockchain transforms the traditional bank payment model—previously involving multiple participants—into a streamlined two-party system. Several key blockchain theories serve as foundational models for the technology, including the Bitcoin Model by Nakamoto (2008), the Ethereum Model by Buterin (2014), Blockchain Platforms 2.0 by Swan (2015), and the Big Data on Blockchain framework by Karafilovski (2017).

Figure 2-10. Blockchain technology (Source: Wouda & Opendakker, 2019)

Generally, the blockchain works on the following conditions.

- 1) Party A wants to send money to Party B.
- 2) The transaction is represented online as a “block”.
- 3) The block is broadcast to every party in the network.
- 4) Those in the network (e.g. Miners) approve the transaction is valid.
- 5) The block then can be added to the chain, which provides an indelible and transparent record of transactions.
- 6) The money moves from A to B.

Figure 2-11 provides an illustrative example of a two-party system that provides a non-technical explanation of blockchain technology.

Figure 2-11. Asset exchange between two transacting parties (Source: Morkunos et al. 2019)

Currently, there are a lot of use cases for application of digital transformation factors for the financial sector covering banking real estate industry, e-governance, insurance and reinsurance industry, digital rights and legal affairs, media, real estate (highlighted in yellow for a concrete use case), public sector, production industry, supply chains, and voting¹. The blockchain as a distributed ledger, which keeps track of who owns what, and who owned what in the past, including full history of all past transactions (see Figures 2-12 and 2-13).

Figure 2-12. Blockchain blocks

Public keys are cryptographically bitcoin protocols stored in blocks (Multiple Blocks become to Blockchain).

Figure 2-13. Blockchain protocols (Source: Own Research and Conceptualization)

- 1) Each block includes a reference to the previous block.
- 2) Blocks are chained together.
- 3) Fingerprint of previous block is part of the block verification problem.
- 4) Every modification of a previous block is detectable.

2.3.8 Tokens and Tokenization

Authorization within blockchain systems is enabled by the digital signature of a cryptographic hash. In a crypto-economy, transactions involve the exchange of coins (tokens) between Bitcoin addresses (Morabito, 2017). The Ethereum platform further empowers developers to tokenize a wide range of high-value, scarce assets—such as currencies, securities, and real estate—that can be transferred between parties without the need for a central entity (Chen, 2018). In the context of this study, the issuance of blockchain tokens as digital representations of assets has the potential to revolutionize various aspects of commercial real estate, including buying, selling, and asset management (Latifi et al., 2019; Yeoh et al., 2023). Due to their high liquidity and tradability (Sehra et al., 2017), blockchain tokens can transform the commercial real estate industry by reducing the number of intermediaries (Altynpara, 2023), securing digital property records (Wouda & Opdenakker, 2019), and enhancing due diligence processes (Altynpara, 2023).

Tokenization concepts have progressed to the proof-of-concept stage, exemplified by blockchain-enabled multiple listing services (Krupa & Akhil, 2019). Key benefits include improved process efficiency and operational excellence through shared processes and information (Morkunas et al., 2019; Thota, 2019) as well as the automation of smart contract

execution (Rahmadika & Rhee, 2018), which facilitates peer-to-peer (P2P) digital payments (Garcia-Teruel, 2020). Notably, despite their name, smart contracts are not considered legally binding contracts (Fridgen et al., 2021). Blockchain has become a cornerstone of innovation across various domains. This study builds upon foundational research by Tripathi, Ahad, and Casalino (2023), highlighting the application of public blockchains based on Ethereum’s public code.

Blockchain Architecture is shaped by two critical aspects:

- 1. **Ownership of Data Infrastructure:** This determines whether the blockchain is public or private.
- 2. **Permissions:** These define the operations for joining, reading, writing, and committing to the blockchain.

2.3.9 Types of Blockchain

Blockchain technology is broadly categorized into three types:

- 1. **Private Blockchain:** Restricted to specific participants, typically within an organization, with controlled access to read and write operations (see Figure 2-15).
- 2. **Public Blockchain:** Open to all users, allowing unrestricted participation in read and write operations (see Figure 2-16). Examples include Bitcoin and Ethereum.
- 3. **Hybrid Blockchain:** Combines features of public and private blockchains, enabling selective participation and data visibility.

Figure 2-14. Types of Blockchain technology

Private Blockchain: Are restricted and not open to all users and it has unique features (see Figure 2-15). These blockchains operate within closed systems and networks, typically for organizational or enterprise use, where only selected members can join. Private blockchains ensure security, authorization, permissions, and controlled accessibility. They are commonly deployed for applications such as voting, supply chain management, digital identity management, and asset ownership. Examples of popular private blockchain platforms include multichain, hyperledger, and corda. As these blockchains operate with authorized nodes, external users cannot access transaction-related data or information exchanged between nodes (Aithal et al., 2021).

Figure 2-15. Features of Private Blockchain

Public Blockchain: Is both open and decentralized in nature and it has unique features (see Figure 2-16). In this type of blockchain technology, computer networks are accessible to anyone interested in transactions. Validation in public blockchains reward the validated participants, using models such as Proof-of-Work (PoW) and Proof-of-Stake (PoS). Proof of work (PoW) (Vukolić, 2016), proof of stake (PoS) and delegated proof of shares (DPoS) (Liu and Xu, 2021). Public blockchains, such as Ethereum, are particularly suited for applications requiring transparency and decentralization. The Ethereum public code provides a robust foundation for implementing open public blockchain solutions, ensuring secure and immutable data storage. This approach aligns with the goals of the underlying this study, which leverages public blockchains to address challenges in decentralized systems (Aithal et al., 2021).

Figure 2-16. Features of Public Blockchain

Figure 2-17. Features of Hybrid Blockchain

1. **Open Public Blockchain:** Fully open for read and write operations.
2. **Closed Public Blockchain:** Open for reading but restricted for writing.
3. **Open Private Blockchain:** Restricted for reading but open for writing within a controlled group.
4. **Closed Private Blockchain:** Fully restricted for both reading and writing, accessible only to authorized participants.

Hybrid blockchain: Merge features of public and private blockchains, offering a balanced approach to achieve higher goals. These blockchains integrate centralized and decentralized systems, ensuring integrity, transparency, and security (Aithal *et al.*, 2021). In hybrid blockchains, maximum customization is achieved by combining private permission-based

systems with public permission-less systems. Users can access specific sections while keeping other parts secure due to the benefits of ledger-based records. Hybrid blockchains are flexible, allowing users to join private networks while maintaining security and transparency. Similarly, read permissions distinguish between public and private blockchains. Combining these criteria results in four categories for the hybrid blockchain and illustrate the versatility of blockchain technology, offering solutions that balance access and security (Aithal *et al.*, 2021).

Blockchain consists of five technological layers (see Figure 2-18) with each of these layers having different properties and characteristics. The application layer encompasses applications and smart contracts. A smart contract is a code program identified by a unique address in the network, and it consists of components that are a set of executable functions and input parameters which are a required function in the contract (Karamitsos *et al.* 2018).

Figure 2-18. Blockchain Layers (source: Karamitsos *et al.* 2018, p.181)

The significance of the design factors (e.g. structure, security, cost) is the baseline for the architecture and find the suitable technology stack (Zhang and Zhou, 2020). The adoption of public blockchains, particularly Ethereum, exemplifies the potential of conceptual artefacts in guiding the development of transparent and decentralized systems.

This study has applied Ethereum’s public code, to develop solutions that emphasize transparency and decentralization and (Tripathi, Ahad and Casalino, 2023) and Ethereum as

the most validated network within Blockchain and applies the architecture for the technology stack and its public chain features (i.e., layers of blockchain, tokenisation). After the public blockchain technology has been selected for the prototype development, the technology stack is fundamentally open, flat, and egalitarian, structured into multiple interdependent layers: 1) data layer, 2) network layer, 3) consensus layer, 4) contract layer and 5) application layer (Xu et al., 2024)

In summary, DLT technology provides significant advantages over traditional databases, such as enhanced security, speed, transparency, and reduced transaction costs. However, challenges related to scalability remain, especially for public blockchains, but ongoing innovations are addressing these limitations.

2.3.10 Feature differences Between Centralised and Decentralised Databases

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), such as blockchain, offers several benefits over traditional databases of transactions, as outlined by (Shrimali and Patel, 2022). Table 2-7 lists the differences between centralised and decentralised databases based on seven key features. Each feature is discussed in the remainder of this section.

Table 2-7: Differences between centralised and decentralised databases (Shrimali and Patel, 2022)

Feature	Traditional database	Decentralised database (Blockchain)
Structure	Centralised	Decentralised
Speed	Moderate	Frictionless
Immutability	Data can be modified	Data is immutable once recorded
Transparency	Limited transparency	Full transparency (public scenario)
Validity	Data silos and not validated	Ethereum is the most validated network on Blockchain
Scalability	Data can be scaled	The scalability is a challenge, especially for the public blockchains (Prototype Ethereum)
Transaction Cost	Vendor lock-in and high costs (e.g. SAP ERP)	The prototype on Ethereum showed significant lower of costs due to Ethereum gas fees

Structure: Traditional databases are centralized, controlled by a single authority or entity. This centralization introduces risks such as data manipulation, breaches, and corruption. In contrast, DLT operates on a decentralized network, where control is shared among multiple

participants, reducing single points of failure and enhancing data security and trust (Shrimali and Patel, 2022).

Speed: Transaction processing speeds in traditional databases depend on the system architecture and the number of intermediaries involved. By contrast, decentralized databases, such as blockchain, enable frictionless transactions across the network. This significantly boosts speed, particularly in real-time applications, by eliminating intermediaries and centralized processing (Hughes et al., 2019).

Immutability: Traditional databases permit data modifications and updates, which can lead to errors or fraudulent activities. DLT ensures immutability—once a transaction is recorded, it cannot be altered without network consensus. This guarantees data integrity and enhances system trustworthiness (Aithal et al., 2021).

Transparency: Traditional databases often restrict data access to authorized users, leading to opacity and a lack of accountability. Conversely, decentralized databases, such as public blockchains, provide full transparency, enabling all participants to view transaction histories (Tripathi, Ahad and Casalino, 2023).

Validity: Traditional databases frequently operate in silos and may lack robust validation mechanisms, resulting in inconsistencies and errors across systems. Blockchain networks, like Ethereum, achieve high levels of data validation through multiple nodes working together to verify and confirm transactions (Wouda & Opdenakker, 2019; Altynpara, 2023).

Scalability: Traditional databases are relatively easy to scale by adding hardware or upgrading resources. However, public blockchains, such as Ethereum, face scalability challenges due to limitations in transaction throughput and network congestion (Shrimali and Patel, 2022).

Transaction Costs: Centralized systems, such as SAP ERP, often incur high transaction costs due to vendor lock-ins, maintenance, and licensing fees. In contrast, DLT, particularly Ethereum's blockchain, can significantly lower transaction costs. The Ethereum prototype demonstrates this by offering transaction fees (gas fees) that are typically much lower than those associated with traditional centralized systems (Wang et al., 2019).

2.3.11 Commercial Real Estate and Smart Contract

The mortgage loan tokenization aims to revolutionize the real estate market, by offering eligible private crypto-investors access to a regulated and real estate backed asset-token on Ethereum Platform under possible Swiss favourable regulations (e.g. FINMA Regulation).

By using an Ethereum token, the real estate Asset can be transformed into tradable good for and with existing tokens and cryptocurrencies. The approach is first of its kind for Swiss tokens whose primary mission is the atomization and digitalization of banking real estate using asset-backed tokenization of high value real estate ownership. The token holders (e.g. of Ethereum's) should have direct ownership of the mortgage loans associated with the real estate behind the asset-backed investment token. Currently, the regulatory compliance and notary obligations are limited to claim the ownership of the real estate asset subject to each country financial legislation which could have consequences for regulatory compliance and notary obligations. The ownership will be tracked on behalf of the use of the Ethereum-blockchain Platform – so called Contract law 2.0: 'Smart' contracts means the beginning of the end of classic contract law characterized as 1.0.

Figure 2-19 below describes the Mortgage Loan process where multiple stakeholders (i.e., lender, buyer/borrower, seller, appraiser and third-party provider, housing authority and notary office (in blue). The mortgage process requires good faith estimate, mortgage application, purchase contract, home appraisal insurance, title and IDs personal documents (in green). Mortgage processes are timely, costly and can result in search errors, which generate transactional costs.

Figure 2-19. Traditional mortgage loan process

Source: Own Research

Existing mortgage loans have a central authority ledger (e.g. Land Registry) and require multiple signoffs of all the mortgage loan stakeholders in the supply chain which causes delays in the execution times, credit risks of time, financial reporting risks due to time lags and cash flow inefficiencies resulting into high transaction costs (see Figure 2-20).

Figure 2-20. Mortgage loan in the expensive, inefficient and vulnerable environment

Figure 2-21 describes the mortgage loan process on blockchain schematically depicted how to cut unnecessary stakeholders' "middleman" and use the smart contract code where lender and borrower can interact with each other being set on the common blockchain decentralized ledger platform (Blockchain 2.0 on Ethereum Contract) and reduce transactional costs.

Figure 2-21: Mortgage loan contract on the blockchain smart contract

Mortgage loans based on blockchain smart contract do not require a central authority ledger and could be set on the shared mutual ledger. Once the consensus is agreed between all the stakeholders, the transaction will be executed in real-time based on smart contract. Instant settlements of mortgage loans would improve traceability and data quality, faster and auditable signoffs, faster and transparent cash settlement and auto-execution of contract condition through smart contract mathematical algorithms. The unique and revolutionary use of the blockchain will disrupt the traditional real estate market by introducing an almost fully liquid real estate investment product that has significantly cheaper entry and operational costs at lower transaction costs (Savelyev, 2018, pp. 117-120).

Figure 2-22: Smart Contract on Blockchain – Example (Source: Savelyev, 2017, p. 125)

```

contract token {
    mapping (address => uint) public coinBalanceOf;
    event CoinTransfer(address sender, address receiver, uint amount);

    /* Initializes contract with initial supply tokens to the creator of the contract */
    function token(uint supply) {
        if (supply == 0) supply = 10000;
        coinBalanceOf[msg.sender] = supply;
    }

    /* Very simple trade function */
    function sendCoin(address receiver, uint amount) returns(bool sufficient) {
        if (coinBalanceOf[msg.sender] < amount) return false;
        coinBalanceOf[msg.sender] -= amount;
        coinBalanceOf[receiver] += amount;
        CoinTransfer(msg.sender, receiver, amount);
        return true;
    }
}

```

According to Wouda and Opdenakker (2019) third-party intermediaries in the commercial real estate process could be eliminated. Furthermore, the study sheds light how to reduce the odds of mortgage fraud where buyers and sellers would see lower contract closing costs and research Thesis proposes a potential use case to show how stakeholders of the transaction on the shared ledger for distributed transactional and ownership ledgers could interact more efficiently where transaction costs and process improvement by omitting the redundancy processes of the ‘middleman’ stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller. Recent studies have revealed a the steady growth of crowdfunding since the combination of the information technology factors have captured the financial innovation, digital innovation, digital transformation and digitalisation of the financial ecosystem and especially real estate industry (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018). Since the merger of finance and technology, “fintech,” has led to the growth of crowdfunding, which became a challenge to traditional banking models in terms of the innovative models which disrupted the traditional banking models.

Figure 2-23 is an example of a process workflow where input data such as attachment documents, data entries are converted to the data output to the “hashed” blocks on the chain. This process workflow proposes a smart contract transaction on the blockchain-based infrastructure to enhance the current transaction process commercial real estate object office building. during validation of the application, are decentralized and connected to the common blockchain database.

Figure 2-23: Transaction process workflow on the blockchain technology

The permissionless nature of the blockchain technology allowed in the pilot case to generate and encode information in the way that is equivalently available to buyers and sellers, removing the need for brokers as well as legal intermediaries (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019). Currently each member maintains their own credit checks and forwards changes to a central authority for credit valuation and those processes are timely, costly and can result in search errors, which generate transactional risks. Modern decentralized store of information of Blockchain technology would allow to traceability of the servicing process by tracking payments and further discussed in the (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

The need for further research is essential to present a mathematical model of property rights that matches the concept of tokens driven by smart contracts, considering the key blockchain ledger component - the immutability of records and fully-stacked audit trail on the smart contracts for designing a holistic metamodel oriented on different legal systems and jurisdictions research general concept of real estate tokenisation on blockchain and constraints

(Konashevych, 2020c) and benefits of the blockchain use for real estate and property rights (Konashevych, 2020a).

2.3.12 Real Estate Sustainability

The pioneers of real estate sustainability are Scandinavian practitioners such as Store-Valen and Busen (2019) with sustainable approaches of implementation challenges and barriers of Scandinavian real estate use cases (Støre-Valen and Buser, 2019). The real estate sustainability concept has been discussed about the responsibility and potential in the real estate industry which holds to reach climate and environmental sustainability targets. In a rapidly urbanising world, the real estate industry lies at the centre of an unprecedented level of growth and activity. Sustainable real estate processes need also to reflect on sustainability tools of circular economy which have been analysed based on the use case study of operational sustainability lease (Ploeger *et al.*, 2019). Sustainable concepts allow to leverage newest recent technologies for the application in the real estate and achieve smart building technologies first prototypes (Redlein and Grasl, 2018). Empirically, first evaluation of pro-environmental sustainability tools in regards of user perception, satisfaction and productivity have been analysed by Tezel and Giritli (Tezel and Giritli, 2019). To maintain a competitive offering in the real estate sustainability, the companies must understand the analytical and foresighted sustainability how this may impact construction projects and to be calculated with the fundamental understanding and benefit of green buildings (Collins *et al.*, 2019). However, failures of BIM implementation projects have been analysed by in two cases of FM digitalization based on hospital processes have been described (Koch, Hansen and Jacobsen, 2019).

2.3.13 Legal Aspects

It is important to check the legal aspect-recording for property titles by comparing the benefits and limitations of a blockchain with those of the current record keeping system as mentioned by Spielman research on a global scale (Spielman, 2016a). In a falling market, people/organisations are interested in storing the investment funds somewhere safe where the value will be kept more stabilized (Spielman, 2016a). In Switzerland, since the introduction of Swiss/ Liechtenstein Blockchain Law (Blockchain Act Liechtenstein,(Lennert, 2021), the Real estate enterprises are allowed to offer so called “tokens” (similar to digital equity shares) which are directly linked to the value of the underlying piece of Real estate, itself valued in the local currency of the particular country (e.g. CHF for Switzerland). The pioneer of the Blockchain regulation is the Liechtenstein Blockchain Law which has been reported in the media of

November 2018, the Financial Market Authority Liechtenstein (FMA) approved the Blockchain Law and the regulation of the 'Tokens'. The so-called Token is a digital coin that enables the transfer of certain rights (e.g. ownership) in a transaction. The tokens will be traded on the cryptocurrency exchanges. Liechtenstein thus plays a pioneering role in government regulation of the crypto-financial market. The token character can have different roles and functions dependent on the character of the token in accordance with the Blockchain Act Liechtenstein (Lennert, 2021).

- Security Token (Tokens guarantee a security e.g. debt, equity or derivatives).
- Digital Currency (Tokens represent an attributed value for buy and sell of goods).
- Asset backed Token (Tokens shape underlying exposure to real-estate assets e.g. gold, diamond, Real estate).
- Utility token (Tokens provide access to a Blockchain platform, product or service).

Furthermore, the flexible character of Blockchain token allows scarce, global, liquid, and tradable market exchange. In order to better understand the relation of the investors, various customer behaviour theories have been analysed before (TRA, TRB, UTAUT) analysed blockchain tokens and the potential democratization of entrepreneurship and innovation (Chen, 2018). Modern regulation should prevent threats and vulnerabilities in the design of the smart contract. The focus of a secure solution assures the privacy and traceability of the real estate contract and should fulfil according to (i) design of Smart Contracts and associated supply chain management applications, (ii) underlying blockchain execution environment and (iii) trust between all interconnected supply management services (Al-Farsi, Rathore and Bakiras, 2021).

In this context, the regulation is subject to local jurisdictions. As illustrated in Figure 2-25, an international regulation comparison study has been carried out by PWC Switzerland (Dobrauz, 2018) in 2018 on the raising capital using Blockchain Technology- so called Initial Coin Offering (ICOs). Mortgage loans have been considered as asset-backed tokens and undergo each country national financial legislation. Most of the International regulation frameworks are set for minimum capital adequacy and anti-cyclical capital buffer and must follow general principles of the respective regulation. For Switzerland case, the rules for Tokens apply EU legislation procedures for digital tokenisation (Garcia-Teruel and Simón-Moreno, 2021).

Figure 2-24. International blockchain technology regulation (PWC, 2018)

Yellow – favourable regulation

Orange – Wary/existing regulation

Red- Ban of Blockchain Initial Coin Offering (ICOs)

EMEA: Basel III/IV (BIS, 2018), EU regulations like EU Mortgage Credit Directive (MCD, 2018), BAFIN (BAFIN, 2018) for Germany, FSMA (FSMA 2018) for UK, FINMA for Switzerland (FINMA, 2018), Liechtenstein Financial Market Authority (FMA, 2018) and Luxembourg Commission de Surveillance du Secteur Financier (2018), Malta Financial Services Authority, Gibraltar Financial Services Commission (2018), Estonian Financial Supervision Authority (EFSA, 2018), Bank of Lithuania (2018) as most favourable regulations and Serbia – National Bank (2018) ban of Blockchain capital raising.

North America: SEC (SEC, 2018) for US financial market

South America: Securities and Exchange Commission of Brazil (CVM, 2018), Mercado de Termino de Rosario (MTR, 2018), Central Bank of Uruguay (2018),

Asia: China Banking Regulatory ban of ICOs , Commission (CBRC, 2018), Financial Services Agency of Japan (FSA, 2018), Reserve Bank of India (2018) ban

Euroasia: Central Bank of the Russian Federation (2018), National Bank of Ukraine (2018), Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2018) as the most favourable regulation in Eurasia

Pacific - Australian: Prudential Regulation Authority (APRA, 2018), Reserve Bank of New Zealand (2018).

2.4. Outline of Identified Research Problems

Based on the reviewed literature and the related, relevant theory, four important research problems have been identified.

(1) Problem of asymmetric information – hidden information of separate ledgers record keeping

Hoksbergen and Chan (2019) conducted most recent research about the market asymmetry in the Real estate and presented the results for the Annual Communications in Computer and Information Science 2019 where the conference paper identified ways how to mitigate asymmetric information, identify the bottlenecks in the current processes and suggest possible solutions that capitalize on the blockchain characteristics (Hoksbergen and Chan 2019). The asymmetric information is especially prevalent in high-value, low-frequency assets where the stakeholders have not equally fair information about the asset. The withhold of information that could negatively impact a transaction and decrease the Real estate market fairness. Currently, property records are stored at the country level, title companies have its own record keeping ledgers and must maintain their own title plants and harmonise the records geographically with the purpose of search efficiency and decrease of claims (Spielman 2016). The lending standards were also analysed in relation to volatility. Financial intermediaries have different characteristics of interaction dependent on the firm's business character and organisation and how the firm should organise its transactions, i.e. whether the firm should produce by integrating the vertical chain or by outsourcing its resources and focussing on the core competence (Williamson, 1981, pp. 573-574). Hitleman and Rauchs (2017, p. 13) studied blockchain technology in the real estate with a combination of the P2P and indicated that, "a blockchain is a type of database that is replicated over a P2P network". Dijkstra (2017) and Veuger (2017) then examined the theoretically applicability of blockchain technology in the real estate management and real estate transaction process in general. Blockchain technology could lead to improvements in efficiency, transparency, and trust (Dijkstra (2017; Veuger, 2017). Therefore, real estate industry could use blockchain to better engage with the risks associated with real estate assets (Dijkstra, 2017). Blockchain technology could provide a novel solution for the problem of decentralised property record and allows to keep the data within the cross-blockchain bundles of decentralised ledgers resulting into the transfer of the records across ledgers and thus decreasing the asymmetric information (Konashevich, 2020).

(2) Problem of mistakes from paper-based recording practice

Spielman (2016, p. 20) states that “30 percent of property titles are found defective at the time of a real estate transaction.” This causes a consequence of manual, paper-based recording (as well as decentralization), where in deeds, mortgages, leases, easements, court orders, and encumbrances associated with are exposed to human error” (Spielman, 2016). Furthermore, Brötcher (2019) pointed out that commercial contract is paper-based and executed in the old-fashioned manner whereas the transaction procedures reflect formal rules, but they are also normalized through conventions and professional codes of conduct. Big survey about commercial real estate case was performed between 2001 and 2005 by researchers mainly from university departments related to land surveying, real estate management, geo-information sciences and knowledge engineering (Zevernbergen, 2008). The study has analysed highly complex process consisting of multiple contract stakeholders and various processes between the stakeholders. For a typical real estate contract completion, various sequential steps need to be performed and could be summarised as the Real estate Due-Diligence process diagram (Just and Stapenhorst, 2018). Finally, Swan (2018) highlights the potential economic benefits of digital ledgers where these applications could be applied for the digital asset registries, blockchains as leapfrog technology for global financial inclusion, long-tail personalized economic services, and net settlement payment channels (Swan, 2018). The error-handling process is backed by the blockchain algorithms (Opendakker and Wouda 2019), Real estate title purpose (the effectiveness and automation in Building Construction industry where Blockchain Technology brings a value added for complex facilities delivered faster and at a lower cost (Dakhli and Lafhaj, 2019). The consequence of transaction cost reduction could provide access to affordable housing and leverage the effects of the 'collaborative housing' (collaborative economy applied to the funding, access, and organization of housing) arises to address a range of situations that might potentially help people to access housing, such as co-housing or the so-called 'intermediate tenures' (Nasarre and Aznar, 2018). In this sense, the gap is to find a secure architecture without mistakes from paper-based recording practice which can be digitally recorded information by using the cryptographic protocol on the decentralized ledger. The new architecture would allow to carry out the transaction without intermediaries, which means the lack of any external control and independent verification of the transactions to be recorded, which could increase trust and processing efficiency as well as reduction of costs (Kaczorowska, 2019).

(3) Problem of high cost of property transaction

Previous transaction costs models like the mid of 20th century, Minsky (1977,1986) and Kindleberger (1978) shaped mortgage loan into the lending standards and derived the

procyclical relation of country growth and recession where the growth strengthen, and recession diminish mortgage loan activity. The lending standards were also analysed in relation to volatility. For many decades, the microeconomic, macroeconomic, and real estate theories explained the real estate market of loans and liabilities with its traded customer deposits. Based on the above theories, the execution of any market transaction leads to costs between two or multiple parties of the transaction. This is especially the case in the commercial real estate. The few financial service providers that do offer flexibility often ask high fees for the flexible allocation of funds by their rightful owners and show that processes of human-based commercial real-estate contracts are high costly and inefficient (Bernanke and Gertler 1989, Kiyotaki and Moore 1997). Furthermore, Spielman (2016) analysed the high-cost structure based on the real estate industry opportunity and search costs resulting into a higher price factor for the end consumers. Spielman (2016) has compared the case with the Title insurance for the commercial real estate contract and proved that the search and transaction costs include also “fees from involving abstractors, curators, search and examination personnel, and lawyers, as well as sales and marketing professionals and “represent an estimated 75% of industry premiums” This relatively high fixed cost structure directly results in higher real estate prices for the end consumer (Spielman, 2016, p. 21). Recent research of explored from the view of buyers and sellers, the relationship between the blockchain technology and various important aspects of real estate transactions such as transparency, security, and cost reduction (Hokha and Sadiku, 2019) and subsequently comparative analysis of blockchain technologies under a coordination perspective to several different application domains ranging from supply chain and logistics to healthcare and real-estate (Ciatto and Bosello, 2019). Problem of real estate investment products - asset illiquidity and high real estate market barriers. First considerations of asset illiquidity and real estate barriers have been considering with the US Patent for home asset enhancement notes have been already discussed in 2004 by Neil Schoen in the US Patent Application paper where a method for generation of publicly traded notes backed by ownership of single-family homes has been introduced. This method allowed financial markets to provide instruments for investors and homeowners to profit from price changes in the value of single-family homes (Shoen, 2004). The real estate investment products are more applicable to the real estate investor view and present the concept for owner-occupiers to securitize (fractionise) their investment product (asset). The identification of a favorable investment asset is a key aspect influencing the real estate market in a modern real estate market, which is the baseline for asset valuation bringing such factors that influence the market price such as floor space area, crime in the locality (Talasila and Pasumathy, 2019). Basically, the idea is about the title token, which is a record of ownership, a representation of a title on blockchain, which does not require old-fashioned

property registry. A fraction of the title to the land and dwelling of many single-family homes are bundled, separately from that of the traditional mortgages, creating the equivalent of mortgage-backed-securities (fractions). A cross-blockchain protocol opens opportunities for using blockchains fraction titles in public services, i.e. land registry and other types of state-owned databases and opens new potentials to revolutionize land registration (Kaczorowska, 2019). Specifically, the idea is to introduce securitization (fraction) mechanism of title tokens for real estate, so people can choose what to use: a traditional land registry or transfer their records of ownership on blockchain and manage their property rights without bureaucracy using smart contracts (Konashevych, 2020). Blockchain technology originated from the whitepaper: Bitcoin: A P2P Electronic Cash System published in 2008 under the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto (2008), transformation with the commercial property by tokenizing the Smart Contracts of real estate Providing fractional ownership and investment liquidity in a traditionally high barriers to entry industry (Norta and Fernandez, 2019). Studies by Opdenakker (2019) and Karamitsos (2019) provided the first proof of concepts, where search and transaction cost could be minimized due to Blockchain model. Karamitsos (2019) has not considered KYC/AML validation allowing the authorization, tracking and ban of Ethereum accounts from the database.

(4) Problem of asset illiquidity

The advent and rise of Bitcoin brought public and media attention but also uncertainty and fear in the banking sector, primarily driven by the cypher punk movement when in 2009 a group of programmers known under the name of Satoshi Nakamoto presented the idea of “P2P Electronic system”: (Prinzi and Paesani, 2017, p. 4). The pioneering whitepaper behind all: Bitcoin: A P2P Electronic Cash System, that was published in 2008 under the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto (2008). Blockchain technology has been mentioned as DLT and characterized as ingenious technology that uses sophisticated cryptographic techniques and clever incentives to ensure an autonomous and “once consensus-achieved” accounting of Bitcoin transactions performed on the decentralized database (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019). Legal challenges and opportunities of blockchain technology in the real estate sector have been neglected for a long period of time and came again into the scope of the researchers with the papers (Garcia and Teruel, 2020), where the paper analyses the current intermediaries in the real estate sector in EU, their functions and how can blockchain strengthen the security of these transactions while reducing their time. Since most of the projects encounter legislative challenges and government inertia (Konashevych, 2020), the first academic proven evidence for blockchain technology trust has been evaluated based on the practical implication for the Dopo di Noi Project (After us) which goal was to deliver trust legal instrument in the Real estate

environment (Morena and Truppi, 2020). The Blockchain protocol is suitable not only for public services and governments but for many other commercial services. Real estate properties use the title tokens and land registries, especially the cross-blockchain digital identities (Know Your Customer (KYC), AML Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Counter Terrorism Financing (CTF) policy, legally binding electronic signature, etc.). This part is necessary for land registries, though it is a standalone project for multiple business needs (Konashevych, 2020). In the praxis, the pioneer of the Blockchain regulation is the Liechtenstein and Switzerland Blockchain Law established by Financial Market Authority Liechtenstein (FMA). The so-called Token is a digital coin that enables the transfer of certain rights (e.g. ownership) in a transaction and have different roles and functions dependent on the character of the token. In fact, the Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority (FINMA) has publicly declared an official stance on ICOs, where it identified four categories of tokens (FINMA, FMA, 2020). First category describes Security Token (tokens guarantee a security e.g. debt, equity, or derivatives, whereas the second category deals with digital currency (tokens represent an attributed value for buy and sell of goods). Subsequently, the third category sheds light on the real estate security token (tokens titles underlying exposure to real-estate assets e.g. gold, diamond, real estate, and the energy sector so called Utility token (tokens provide access to a Blockchain platform, product, or service). Furthermore, the flexible character of blockchain token allows scarce, global, liquid, and tradable market exchange by making them especially appealing to global investors (Massey, Dalal, and Dakshinamoorthy, 2017). The new framework by FINMA has strengthened investor protection and improved the functioning of financial markets making them more efficient, resilient and transparent (MIFID/MIFIR 2019) where DLT allows to “tokenise” – to provide the fractional ownership to the token holder and achieve investment liquidity in a Real estate market with a high traditional barrier to entry the market and more research needs to be conducted (Konashevych, 2020). Finally, the criteria-based aggregation synthesis concluded on the two most important research papers for the research – Opendankker and Wouda (2019) design of the third-party intermediaries in the commercial real estate process could be eliminated (i.e., middleman) (Research Artificat 1, Conceptual Model) Blockchain technology for the real estate by Karamitsos and Papadaki (2018) – (later Research Artificat 2, Prototype Development), the thesis finds a potential use case to show how stakeholders of the transaction on the shared ledger for distributed transactional and ownership ledgers could interact more efficiently where transaction costs and process improvement by omitting the redundancy processes of the ‘middleman’ stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller.

2.5. Outline of Identified Research Gaps

Based on the reviewed literature four concrete research gaps that have not been part of the academic debate so far can be identified. Those four problem statements provide the research gap of this study and how to efficiently replace the paper-based commercial real estate contract thus reducing the transaction costs, create more transparency, and trust (Veuger, 2018), and auditability, asset liquidity for the investors and increase the quality for the seller/buyer as a customer. The four research gaps are: (1) asymmetric information; (2) mistakes from paper-based recording practices; (3) high transactions costs, and (4) asset illiquidity and high barriers.

Table 2-8. Synthesis of literature review diagnosis factors and research gap

ID	Authors	Year	Real estate - Research area	Diagnosis factors (Literature review)	Outlined research gap
1	Abdelhamid, M., Hassan, G.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate - design concepts for state of the art	Research gap of mistakes
2	Aganwal et al.	2020	Technology	Finance housing market	Research gap of transaction cost
3	Al Shami and Kanjo	2019	Finance and Investment	Finance and Real estate asset valuation	Research gap of transaction cost
4	Arrivaz, George	2016	Real estate - Future process	Real estate machine learning process	Research gap of mistakes
5	Avantaggiato, M., Gallo, P.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate trust for the contracts	Research gap of transaction cost
6	Awari, I.L., Kook, P.H., Lim, J.S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate election process	Research gap of transaction cost
7	Baker, C.	2016	Finance and Investment	Finance and Investment models	Research gap of transaction cost
8	Baum, A.	2017	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate process for mortgage-backed securities	Research gap of asset illiquidity
9	Bond, S.	2007	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate transaction cost	Research gap of transaction cost
10	Bröchner, Haugen and Lindkvist	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process inspection management	Research gap of mistakes
11	Bürgi,Nägeli	2019	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate selling process (Due-Diligence)	Research gap of transaction cost
12	Cumming, D. J.	2019	Finance and Investment	Finance and investment and crowdfunding models	Research gap of transaction cost
13	Dixit et al	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate integration process	Research gap of mistakes
14	Dramé-Maigné, S., Laurent, M., Castillo, L., Ganem, H.	2018	Real estate - Future process	Real estate Third Party Costs	Research gap of transaction cost
15	E, S.K., Taliasla, V., Pasumarthy, R.	2019	Business Models	Search for a favourable location	Research gap of transaction cost
16	E, S.K., Taliasla, V., Pasumarthy, R.	2019	Transaction Costs	Search for a favourable location	Research gap of transaction cost
17	Escudero et al.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process urbanisation and spacial process	Research gap of mistakes
18	Gillis, Combs and Yin	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process localisation concepts	Research gap of mistakes
19	Haugbelle and Raffnsee	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process for office buildings	Research gap of asset illiquidity
20	Holsbergen, M., Chan, J., Peko, G., Sundaram, D.	2019	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Asymmetric information in high-value low-frequency transactions	Research gap of asymmetric information
21	Holsbergen, M., Chan, J., Peko, G., Sundaram, D.	2019	Business Models	Asymmetric information	Research gap of asymmetric information
22	Hoxha, V., Sadiku, S.	2019	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate - traditional process	Research gap of transaction cost
23	Hoxha, V., Sadiku, S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate - Process errors	Research gap of mistakes
24	Jytha, Remey, and Ankestejn	2019	Real estate - Future process	Commercial Real estate (CRE) process	Research gap of mistakes
25	Kalyuzhova, N.	2018	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Research gap of transaction cost
26	Kim and Hong	2017	Finance and Investment	Finance P2P interaction	Research gap of transaction cost
27	Konashvych, 2020a	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property cross-border transactions	Research gap of transaction cost
28	Konashvych, 2020b	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property rights	Research gap of transaction cost
29	Konashvych, 2020c	2020	Finance and Investment	Finance property constraints	Research gap of transaction cost
30	Krupa, K.S., Akhli, M.S.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Revolution of Real estate Smart Contract	Research gap of asymmetric information
31	Krupa, K.S., Akhli, M.S.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger (1) Technology and Smart Contracts for the Real estate	Research gap of asymmetric information
32	Latiff, S., Zhang, Y., Cheng, L.-C.	2019	Business Models	Globalization and cost cutting	Research gap of transaction cost
33	Mannino, DeJaco and Re Cecconi	2021	Real estate - Future process	Building and Construction	Research gap of mistakes
34	Montgomery, N., Squires, G., Syed, I.	2018	Real estate - Traditional / Old Process	Real estate process strategy	Research gap of asymmetric information
35	Srinivasan and Venkatraman	2018	Technology	Finance platform and market places	Research gap of transaction cost
36	Thilini and Wokramaarachchi	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate analytic network process	Research gap of mistakes
37	Wanigarathna et al.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate process of commercial and residential types	Research gap of asset illiquidity
38	Wouda, H.P., Opendakker, R.	2019	Technology	Blockchain design for the Commercial contract	Research gap of transaction cost
39	Xie, G.	2019	Real estate - Future process	Real estate geographical spatial economics	Research gap of mistakes
40	Zhang and Li	2021	Finance and Investment	Finance and Investment cryptocurrency returns	Research gap of transaction cost

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Background to Design Science Research

The DSR methodology (see Figure 3-1) proposed by Gregor and Hevner, (2004) as it enables researchers to conduct a design science study as a method of investigation to design a process on ‘an explicitly, organized, rational and wholly systematic approach to design’ (Cross, 2001, p. 53). It enables the researcher to “design an innovative artefact, solving heretofore unsolved problem of solving a known problem in a more effective or efficient manner” (Hevner et al., 2004, p. 82). The DSR methodology provides the rigor knowledge on which to evaluate the novelty of new Artefacts and knowledge resulting from the research (Hevner, 2004, p. 344). Thus, the DSR methodology has been developed for the theoretical artefact investigation to redesign a process in ‘an organized, rational, and wholly systematic approach (Cross, 2001).

Figure 3-1. Design science research methodology (Gregor and Hevner, 2004, p. 80)

Figure 3-1 emphasizes two key dimensions of academic research – rigor and relevance (Hevner et al., 2004). First, the criteria “rigor” to Gregor and Hevner (2004) provides scientific research “to identify the gap, design a concept, check the validity of the Artefact towards the defined aims and objectives based on the appropriate method” Gregor and Hevner (2004, p. 80). Second, the criteria “relevance” means that the DSR methodology is relevant to a

“business need or problem as perceived by the researcher” (Gregor and Hevner (2004, p. 79). However, livari (2015) criticises the DSR framework due to its strong focus on theoretical “scientific design” knowledge base “scientific knowledge” between the academic rigor knowledge base (Foundations, Methodologies) and less practical application in the relevant environment (Organisation, People, Technology, Processes). Thus, livari (2015) recommends extending the DSR model to more “IT technology domain Artefact (1), IS application domain (2), IS social interorganizational domain (3), domain of systems development processes (4) and (5) practical IS applications (livari, 2015, p.763)”. Hence, this study redesigns commercial real estate transaction processes – as well as transactional components (i.e. parties in the transaction) and on the process (value flows within the transaction cycle). Thus, the consequence is to identify the DSR foundations for the Thesis (1) and extend with complimentary arguments of transactional nature research for a more practical action-oriented design science methodology (livari, 2015).

However, the DSR methodology by Gregor and Hevner (2004) does not explicitly cover the practical implementation of real-world artefacts in complex scenarios such as commercial real estate transactions. For that reason, this research applies the Action Design Science Research (ADSR), which has been specifically developed for practice-based applications. The ADSR was developed by Sein et al (2011) and is an amalgamation of action research and design science research for the practical problem-solving. In essence, the ADSR provides a framework to develop an unknown artefact through iterative cycles to build an operational artefact applicable to the practical problem (Peffer, 2018). In this context, Mullarkey and Hevner (2018) developed ADSR for the multi-disciplinary iterative phases of “unknown outcome”. In this study, the approaches by Peffer (2007), Venable (2016) and Baskerville (2015) have been adopted in the Action Design Science Research to make it “more approachable” and “less confusing” (Baskerville, 2015, p. 560). In addition, this overcomes deficiencies such as the unrealistic evaluation of practical applicability (De Sordi, 2020) where the ADSR suits its multi-disciplinary purpose (Peffer et al., 2018). The ADSR is based on the iterative step-by-step cycles-based approach – from understanding the problem, analyse the literature, to articulate/ formulate the problem based on previous as-of-today solutions to reflect in the next cycles on the previous learnings. The re-design is thus iteratively conceptualised to arrive at the prototype, which is then finally critically reviewed based on the empirical market survey and professional experience.

3.2 Guidelines for Conducting DSR

Gregor and Hevner (2004) highlight that there might be trade-offs between relevance and rigor – at certain point the business relevance might not pass the validity criteria, and they recommend finding “an acceptable balance between the two is very difficult” (Hevner, 2004, p. 79). Hence, the balance of rigor and relevance creates utility which defined as “quality and efficacy of a design Artefact must be rigorously demonstrated via well-executed evaluation guidelines” (Gregor and Hevner, 2004, p. 83). This implies that the research quality and efficacy of a design Artefact must be rigorously demonstrated via well-executed evaluation guidelines. This study follows the prescribed guidelines (see Table 3-1) proposed by Gregor and Hevner (2004, p. 83).

Table 3-1. Design-Science Research Guidelines

Guideline	Description
Guideline 1: Design as an Artifact	Design-science research must produce a viable artifact in the form of a construct, a model, a method, or an instantiation.
Guideline 2: Problem Relevance	The objective of design-science research is to develop technology-based solutions to important and relevant business problems.
Guideline 3: Design Evaluation	The utility, quality, and efficacy of a design artifact must be rigorously demonstrated via well-executed evaluation methods.
Guideline 4: Research Contributions	Effective design-science research must provide clear and verifiable contributions in the areas of the design artifact, design foundations, and/or design methodologies.
Guideline 5: Research Rigor	Design-science research relies upon the application of rigorous methods in both the construction and evaluation of the design artifact.
Guideline 6: Design as a Search Process	The search for an effective artifact requires utilizing available means to reach desired ends while satisfying laws in the problem environment.
Guideline 7: Communication of Research	Design-science research must be presented effectively both to technology-oriented as well as management-oriented audiences.

Guideline 1: Design as an Artefact

It starts with a comprehensive literature review. The theoretical background literature helps to identify the domains real estate, business model, technology, legal framework and further distil on the further key inclusion/ exclusion criteria to diagnosis the research problem. Gregor and Hevner (2004) distinguishes the process by four phases “construct, model, method, and instantiation”. Kauffman (2008, p. 780) identified already five types of Artefacts, the four of

Hevner et al. (2004) plus “IT Artefacts” “Design science research involves the construction and evaluation of IT Artefacts, constructs, models, methods, and instantiations.” In our case, those gained knowledge helps to produce the viable Artefacts: Conceptual model (design phase) and build the Prototype (implementation phase) and develop the IT-Artefact - IT-based / Blockchain based Smart Contract. Hence, the commercial real estate business model is transactional by nature and processual by design and requires designing of an improved Artefact.

Guideline 2: Problem Relevance

In this study, the problem relevance is the development of a technology-based solution for the traditional Commercial real estate contract. As stated previously, commercial real estate business model is transactional by nature and processual by design. As of today, design of real estate contract is not efficient since it requires several intermediaries who are extra time-consuming and cost-consuming elements in every transaction (Norta, Fernandez and Hickmott, 2018). Therefore, the interaction between the intermediary parties in the transaction like seller and buyer through a third-party (e.g. broker/bank) currently is organised by the human interaction either in paper-based form or electronic database. Hence, the trust problem due to data manipulation is assured in case of the P2P connection between buyer and seller (algorithmic code mechanism). The problem relevance trust needs to be addressed by an algorithmic mechanism which will assure immutability, auditability and encryption whilst providing decentralised mechanism of transparency amongst anonymous intermediaries (Kendzierskyj and Jahankhani, 2020).

Guideline 3: Design Evaluation

DSR has been explored in several studies on the process how to evaluate the Artefacts of unreal systems, how to resolve problems and achieve user acceptance (Sun and Kantor, 2016, p. 616). Furthermore, Venable/Pries-Heje (2016) added key criteria for the Framework for Evaluation in Design Science (FEDS) as a “special strategy” technique. Hence, the FEDS strategy considers why, when, how, and what to evaluate. The FEDS includes two dimensions for the evaluation of Artefact evaluation - formative or summative and the other dimension artificial or naturalistic Venable and Pries-Heje (2016). According to Venable (2016), the artificial evaluation involves reductionist abstraction from the natural setting (dimension formative and rigour) and assures concrete principles of relevance and rigor regarding the practical implication for the Artefact development (dimension naturalistic and relevance) by Venable and Pries-Heje (2016).

Guideline 4: Research Contributions (Conceptual Model and Prototype)

The fourth guideline provides research contribution of the newly designed Artefact. The goal of an improved design is to ultimately introduce the latest IT solutions to streamline and improve the existing design (as of today) and prototype development/ The prototyping development works in step-by-step iterative process with multiple cycles of abstraction of knowledge and gaining insights, findings and learn from reflections. During the prototype development stage, there are multiple sources that contribute to the development of the ensembled Artefact starting from problem identification (1), diagnosis of existing knowledge (literature 2), external feedback (exploratory interviews (3), personal experience (4) and empirical data analysis (5) The original ADR process model identifies a four-stage approach to the application of the AR paradigm in a DSR study and will be extended with the and extended by Sen for the sequential phases – Diagnosis, Design, Implementation and Evolution (Sein et al., 2011).

Guideline 5: Research Rigor and Relevance

The Design Science Research (DSR) is aimed to provide a disciplined rigor and relevance in research. According to Gregor and Hevner (2004), the prototyping process is the underlying activity to provide theoretical knowledge (rigour) and explore practical application for those theoretical developments (relevance). In this thesis, the principles of rigor and relevance start from problems that come from the field (relevance) and to attempt to provide an Artefact (solution) and to rigorously develop what amounts to prescriptive knowledge, while meeting the standards and norms of scientific research (rigor) Gregor and Hevner (2004). On the one hand, the knowledge rigor aims to help researchers (1) appreciate the levels of Artefact abstractions that may be DSR contributions, (2) identify appropriate ways of consuming and producing knowledge (3) understand and position the knowledge contributions of the research projects, and (4) structure a DSR article so that it emphasizes significant contributions to the knowledge base (Gregor and Hevner, 2004). On the other hand, the environment is characterised by people (buyer, seller), organizations (municipality, land registry, banks, notary, lawyer, further broker intermediaries) and technology (variety of information technologies as they apply to the process) which represent various business needs and relevance. Innovation within real estate depends on the viability with technology, manoeuvrability, organizing differently and management, the key driving forces behind these developments (Veuger, 2018, p. 103).

Guideline 6: Design as a Search Process

The DSR framework applied due to the transactional nature of the real estate transaction by nature and processual by design. Therefore, the DSR provides a suitable approach, where the Search Process starts with literature review (diagnosis) helps to (i) analyse systematic literature review, (ii) continues with qualitative expert interviews, (iii) redesign the old process - as of today to the new design improvements, (iv) develop a new Artefact- proof of concept/ prototype including buyers, sellers and intermediaries in an iterative way, and (v) to reflect on learnings and double-validate by the triangulation / market survey the solution validity.

Guideline 7: Communication of Research

The final guideline is to demonstrate and communicate usefulness of the design and presenting within the information system research. Since the Design Science Research has been further developed by (Peffer, 2007), (Venable, 2016) and Baskerville (2015) to make it “more approachable” and “less confusing” (Baskerville, 2015, p. 560) and to overcome deficiencies such as the unrealistic evaluation, the communication of research requires a clear and effective structure (De Sordi, 2020). Subsequently, the DSRM has been explored in several studies on the process how to evaluate the Artefacts of unreal systems, how to resolve problems and achieve user acceptance (Sun and Kantor, 2016, p. 616). Hence, the communication of research will be presented in an effective way to both practitioners and academics.

3.3 General Design Science - Research Strategies

The DSR framework is a broad term within IS and has two main strategy focuses. as formulated by livari (2015) proposes two strategies for IS design science research, (1) designing an IT meta-artefact as a solution to a class of problems and (2) solving a specific problem for a specific client and generalising a packaged general solution for a class of problems. The researcher might want to demonstrate that the design properties of the artefact allow for solving the business problem or even the class of problems of which the concrete business problem represents an instance livari (2012; 2015; 2017).

DSR distinguishes various strategies as outlined by livari (2012; 2015; 2017) and illustrated in Figure 22. livari (2015) proposed two main strategies for distinguishing and contrasting for

design science research. The IS Artefact is problematic as a unit of design because of the great differences in the designability of its constituent parts (Iivari, 2015; Lee and Baskerville, 2015). Instead, the thesis maintains that an IS application (strategy 2) is more appropriate as a unit of design, but an IS Artefact may be fruitful as an analytical concept (strategy 1) to be used in behavioural science research on the interplay of IT Artefact, information Artefact and social Artefact, or – especially if including IS application design – in action research-oriented design science research (Iivari, p. 753, 2017).

Figure 3-2. Information Systems Research Framework (Iivari, 2005, p. 110)

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Strategy 1</i>	<i>Strategy 2</i>
1. Researcher–client relationship	A client may be involved, but not necessarily	Client involvement is inevitable
2. Major problems to be addressed	1. A general problem (a class of problem), more or less informed by specific problems in practice	1. A specific problem encountered by a client (or a set of clients) 2. The general problem (the DSR problem) to be figured out during the DSR project
3. Typical uncertainty of a DSR project	1. Uncertainty about the new, innovative general solution concept to the class of problem 2. Uncertainty about the total complexity of specific problems and their solutions in practice	1. Uncertainty about the specific solution to the specific problem encountered by the client (or a set of clients) 2. Uncertainty about the possible DSR contribution
<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Strategy 1</i>	<i>Strategy 2</i>
4. Artefacts built	1. Conceptual IT meta-artefact as a DSR contribution 2. Possibly a real system implementation (instantiation) of the conceptual IT meta-artefact	1. A real system implementation as a specific solution to a problem encountered in practice 2. Conceptual IT meta-artefact as a DSR contribution 3. Possibly a real system implementation (instantiation) of the conceptual IT meta-artefact
5. Primary role of the real system implementation	Instantiation as a proof of concept and possibly used in the evaluation	The real system as a specific solution to a problem encountered in practice implemented primarily as a source of inspiration Instantiation as a proof of concept and possibly used in the evaluation
6. Nature of the target IT artefacts	<i>A priori</i> designable system	Emergent system
7. Typical nature of the IT meta-artefact	A new, innovative concept for a software-hardware system or a new innovative systems development approach, method, technique	New, innovative design principles
8. Innovativeness	Innovativeness of the IT meta-artefacts as the DSR contribution varies greatly	Mixed tendencies + if an interdisciplinary research team, it may foster creativity + practical problems may challenge existing solutions, knowledge and wisdoms – easily focused on client’s current problems – clients may be reluctant to experiment with cutting-edge technology
9. Practical relevance	Varies greatly	<i>A priori</i> better equipped to address immediate practical problems

DSR can have two strategy directions - strategy 1 (conceptual IS Artefact) and strategy 2 (a real system implementation) are reviewed by (Iivari, 2005, p. 110). However, the thesis focuses on the conceptual design development rather than on a single technological solution for a specific enterprise and provides both insights for the academic community and practical solutions for the real estate industry. The remainder of this sections outlines the strategy relevant for this study.

1. **Research-client relationship** has been set in a collaborative manner to develop the common Artefact between Steiner AG (real estate company) and Swiss Realty AG (1-Research-Client Relationship).
2. **Major Problems to be addressed:** On behalf of the agreement, conceptual design requirements have been set. The evaluation is not alone limited during the DSR project, but rather will be used to address major problems in the whole real estate industry.
3. **Typical Uncertainty of a DSR Project:** The beginning of the DSR-Project suffers typical uncertainty – the innovative solution is far away and no concept is yet done for the class problem.
4. **Artefact built:** Subsequently, the two Artefacts are built Artefacts: conceptual Model and Prototype, whereas Conceptual IT meta-Artefact is conceptualized for the commercial real estate asset sale based on the P2P digital contract by algorithmic code. The process of real implementation (instantiation) of Conceptual IT meta-Artefact is followed based on behalf of a real shopping center near Villeneuve Canton Vaude, Switzerland.
5. **Primary role of the real system implementation:** The Prototype is chosen for a commercial real estate as asset type to avoid legal aspects of LexKollar law in Switzerland and focus on the low investment volume in order not to bridge investment scheme protection. The evaluation is supported by the rigor qualitative content analysis by semi-structured interviews and quantitative real estate market survey.
6. **Typical nature of the IT meta-Artefact:** The nature of the target is to redesign a paper-based real estate contract shopping center ACCAS Villeneuve Canton Vaude, Switzerland by a Smart Contract in comparison to the legacy traditional Real estate Contract (6- Nature of the target IT Artefact, ERC20 on the rinkeby test chain. The typical development nature was applied to solve the general problem, demonstrated based on one example -ACCAS Commercial Shopping Center in Switzerland and used for the evaluation of DSRM Model criterias and opportunity to roll out for the whole industry.
7. **Nature of the IT meta-Artefact:** the innovativeness of the “ensembled Artefact” is evaluated based on analytical and descriptive methods: architecture analysis, optimization, static and dynamic analysis, informed argument, scenarios, limitation and communication which involves investigation of a particular contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context (Real estate Commercial Contract) using multiple sources of evidence.
8. **Innovation:** The technological rigor is then achieved at the cost of organizational relevance and fails to recognize that the Artefact emerges from interaction with the organizational context even when its initial design is guided by the researchers’ intent. (Sein et al., 2011). In this context, the innovation comes with an integrated software framework (ADSR) which allows to create an algorithmic-based Smart contract in multiple iterations. However, the

dominant DSR thinking takes a technological view of the IT Artefact, paying scant attention to its shaping by the organizational context (Sein et al., 2011).

9. *Practical relevance:* As stated previously, the aim of this thesis is to address a real-world organizational problem which considers concretely the research client involvement and identifies the business problems in a conceptual manner. Typically, a DSR project provides uncertainty, as neither the concept, nor the practical solution are clear from the beginning. Since the existing DSR methods focus on building the Artefact and relegate evaluation to a subsequent and separate phase, here will be a general lack of practical relevance to the potential applications of the solution in practice.

3.4 General Design Science - Research Process

DSR gives a structured way for the research process. The Gregor and Hevner (2004) approach have been modified by Peffers et al. (2007, p. 54) which shows explicitly how to design the Artefact (1) and explains how to prototype development (2) within the DSR framework (see Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3. Process model for Design Science Research within Information Science (source: Peffers et al., 2007).

In the remainder of this section, the six steps as illustrated in Figure 3-3 are explained.

1. Identify Problem/Business Need

The traditional Real estate model based on the original Transaction Cost Model (Williamson, 1981) forms the basis of the problem identification. According to the literature (see Chapter

2), cutting the transaction costs and simplifying the paper-based contracts represent the key business needs.

Presently, the commercial real estate business problem relies on the complex paper-based contract execution where there might be potential for cost reduction and cutting the middleman to achieve the efficient transactions are proposed for the support of development. In this context, the thesis research is to analyse the asymmetric real estate contract due to its intermediary-driven loose of information (1), human error mistakes /data manipulations (2), increased administrative burden transaction costs (3) and finally its heavy illiquidity (4)

2. Define Objectives

The objectives of the Artefact are clearly specified through the above business needs. The key aim is to find a novel solution for paper-based Real estate contracts addressing the human-based mistakes and ideally solving the previously identified issues of human mistakes, asymmetric information of decentralized property record keeping, administrative burden of search and negotiation transaction costs and finally to transform the illiquid asset class into the liquidity investment product. An important step is to specify the requirements for the Artefact, which can be business, architectural, functional, and non-functional requirements - in our cases it is to analyze the traditional Real estate commercial process in Switzerland, determine the codification potentials within the commercial real estate context and investigates the transaction cost reduction for the commercial real estate investment process on the example of Commercial shopping center.

3. Design and Development

The actual design and development of the Artefact is a significant sub-process itself and can be achieved in numerous ways, depending on the nature of the Artefact. For example, human bias can be avoided through algorithms and the shared Infrastructure. In this context, the thesis research is to analyse the asymmetric real estate contract due to its intermediary-driven loose of information (1), human error mistakes /data manipulations (2), increased administrative burden transaction costs (3) and finally its heavy illiquidity (4) and provide via DSRM guided approach problem formulation, design and build new design (1) and develop new prototype (2) consistent with problem identification and motivation, prior literature, objectives for a solution, design and development, evaluation, and communication.

4. Demonstration

Demonstrating the viability of the Artefact in a certain form helps to justify the research effort and that the solution delivers the intended results. This is the initial test of the finished Artefact

in its native environment. This study focuses on extracting key insights from industry experts as to which parameters were crucial to address. Subsequently, the prototype development will be presented to address the new design – decentralized structure / master data (1) and demonstration of a real-life example which has been recorded on the Blockchain Ethereum transaction process over the Ethereum MetaMask Wallet (2) *

5. Evaluation

Evaluation is the rigorous assessment of the Artefact and builds upon the findings from the demonstration. It shall be shown that the Artefact provides the sought-after utility for the target stakeholders. The evaluation is based on criteria that determine utility of the new design when contrasted with the original paper-based contract by human third-party intermediary. The evaluation validity is further empirically proven by the statistical market survey.

6. Communicate

Once the Artefact has been tested and finished, it is ready to be go to the user acceptance and a find the distribution channel through various inter- and intra-organizational channels although premature diffusion is possible. Final step is to communicate the solution by providing the tutorials on how to get, manage and invest cryptos and achieve the long-term education for the Real estate stakeholders to show and explain the new utility which embraces the new inclusive design of P2P interaction (1) and development of the algorithmic-based decentralized Smart Contract prototype (2) to the community. *

Figure 3-4. ADR method stages and principles (Source: Sein et al., 2011)

3.5 ADSR – Organization and Guidelines

Sein et al (2011, p.37) proposed “action design research (ADR) as a new DSR method to address the asymmetric real estate contract due to (i) its intermediary-driven loose of information, (ii) human error mistakes /data manipulations, (iii) increased administrative burden transaction costs, and (iv) its heavy illiquidity. The ADR Method proposes four stages with the respective design principles and links to the Ph.D.

To provide an understanding of how the ADR process links to the concrete research problem, the step-by-step implementation in the thesis is described.

1. Problem Formulation
2. Building, Intervention and Evaluation
3. Reflection and Learning
4. Formalisation of Learning

To build and assess a new Artefact, one needs to establish the reciprocal shaping of a desired Artefact within the context of the Real estate industry rooted in the practical implementations of the ADRS method. There are four ADRS guidelines are robustly managed through the iterative “elaborated ADR process” with four stages and respective design principles will continue to move through multiple intervention cycles that shift among stages of diagnosing, design, implementation, and evolution and forms the baseline for the interactive ADR process beginning with diagnosis of the problem of asymmetric real estate contract , design of the novel solution based on Blockchain Ethereum, deployment of the Smart Contract on ERC777, connection with Web Application server and connection with interexchange Online Browser metamask for transaction operations (implementation) phase where the solution is build and final lessons learned observation outcome evolution for old-fashioned Commercial real estate business model improvement (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2018, p. 3-4).

Figure 3-5. Combination of ADR principles with the project stages (adopted from Mullarkey and Hevner, 2018)

The initial diagnosis stage deals with the problem formulation and the research gaps (e.g. asymmetric information, separate record keeping (ledger) problem of mistakes from paper-based recording practice resulting into higher burden of legal requirement and transaction costs). The second stage Building, Intervention, and Evaluation (BIE) form an iterative cycle with the research implication and foster the elaborated Artefact creation. The restructure the of BIE stage into artefact creation in the ADSR was informed from the seminal work (i.e., Mullarkey and Hevner, 2015; 2018; Mullarkey et al., 2013). The four stages are: (i) problem formulation, (ii) design, building, intervention, and evaluation, (iii) reflection and learning, and (iv) formulation of learning. The original ADSR process model identifies a four-stage approach to the application of the AR paradigm in a ADSR study (Sein et al., 2011) and will be extended with the sequential phases, namely (i) diagnosis, (2) design, (3) implementation, (4) evolution.

The key innovation driver is the combination of stages with the outlined phases (1) intervention is a core concept in the ADR process and should occur with each ADR cycle and (2) the activities of evaluation (E), reflection (R), and learning (L) occur in each ADR intervention cycle.

3.6 ADSR – Problem formulation

ADR has an iterative approach strategy with a step-by-step iterative phase from diagnosis, design, implementation to evolution and runs a cycle wise stage such as problem formulation, Artefact creation, design, build, reflect and learning of each phase. The starts with problem formulation. In this case, the research has been focusing on two main angles: a deep literature analysis to understand the general state of the related research and identification of problem coming from practical experience in the industry. To analyze the literature, the background literature review and a systematic literature review have been conducted to address the following identified research gaps.

Problem formulation (Proactive-inspired research, Theory-ingrained Artefact)

First, the main driver of the problem formulation was the aim to resolve the asymmetric information where apparent asymmetric information in the real estate industry is omnipresent in any transaction and represents a risk for all parties and stakeholders involved. Hidden characteristics, actions and hidden intentions can lead to information failure and as such represent a risk of additional financial cost and project failure (Asymmetric information).

Second, the problem of keeping separated ledgers represents a risk as to where is the central Source of Truth. Having a centralized source of truth is essential to limit potential discrepancies, liabilities and further legal trouble that might happen down the road. It is essential for complex transactions, like Real estate transactions, to make sure the information is shared and symmetrical between parties. In that sense, the literature shows that the current situation does not satisfy the practical needs (Separated ledgers and record keeping).

Third, the problem of using traditional paper-based and digital record keeping on separated stakeholder systems can provide an additional risk. Paper-based record keeping is difficult to maintain, research and dig into when needing to retrieve information. While digital record keeping mitigates this issue, faulty systems can prove to be an intermediate liability for businesses and ultimately bankrupt companies or prove to be a severe liability (Mistakes due to faulty record keeping).

Fourth, those mistakes and separate record databases accompanied by the asymmetric information results into additional intermediaries which cause transaction costs. Those transaction costs are caused due to those deficiencies of intermediaries (middlemen) which are involved in those transactions. A stronger, encrypted, and automated system would systematically decrease such related costs and ultimately provide stakeholders a cheaper way of making business which ultimately should reflect on higher returns for investors and sellers (Transaction Costs).

Building/Intervention/Evaluation (authentic and concurrent evaluation)

The building of the Artefact is subject to the IS Artefact. Hence, the thesis establishes the reciprocal shaping of the target desired system / prototype development compared to the Real estate industry rooted in the practical implementations. The traditional real estate market shows the transactional structure by its nature and subsequently, the user interaction and respective reciprocity principles need to be followed (Know Your Customer/KYC and Anti-Money Laundering AML).

The reporting of the verified users and proof of fund provenance is essential in any financial system. As in real life, companies have the responsibility to ensure that the provenance of funds is compliant with financial regulations, in this case a MIFID II regulation for Switzerland. Hence, the reporting is essential for any financial project that involves investors and performances. The seller of the asset and investors have the right to have access to reports detailing performances and potential risks. Previous points of user authentication, reciprocal

shaping and mutually influential roles provide the required security for the user. However, not only system security is important, but we need to implement recovery mechanisms and user protection processes to make sure no value is lost during transactions, due to hacking or bad actors in the system. Finally, it is crucial to consider in the conceptual design (1) and later subsequent prototype development (2) that any asset can be exchanged between parties, representing a digital value – single or multiple pieces of digital coins (tokens).

Reflection and Learning (Guided emergency)

Conceptual Artefact implementation around an asset sale of a Ethereum-Test Network (Rinkeby) piece of Commercial real estate of Commercial real estate asset sale shopping center ACCAS Villeneuve Canton Vaude, Switzerland has been transferred in an Ethereum Smart Contract ERC20 token on the rinkeby test chain and evaluate the benefit of the Target-model in comparison to the legacy traditional real estate contract. A reflection upon the results which will confirm or disprove our initial assumptions upon the benefit of a Blockchain focused commercial real estate process will be presented.

Formalization of Learning (Generalized outcome)

The learning phase will be achieved by multi- reflection and results, through multiple intervention cycles that shift among stages of diagnosing, design, implementation, and evolution. According to Mullarkey and Hevner (2018), the agile iteration happens step by step with each new ADR cycle until the ensemble Artefact is developed. In this context, the ADR research process helps to resolve the class problem where the objective and goals are set straight from the beginning of the project. The problem class (Strategy1- Ivori, 2015) of generic problem can be intervened at any ADR cycle with the agile changes. Hence, it connects the bridge with the practical real estate domain being created and evaluated within each cycle by multiple entry points. The outcome of such a study will then be used and disseminated back to our industry experts, organizational entities involved in the process and the relevant academical papers and institutions which take into account perceived benefits but also rely on empirical data and measurable data points (speed, cost). Perceived benefits will be provided by our pool of industry experts. They will provide us with insights on the industry, general feeling towards such initiatives and implementations and general lessons on the ecosystem such as important actors, timelines and estimated implementation time.

3.7 Application of the Action Design Science Research (ADSR) Phases

3.7.1 ADSR Phase 1 - Diagnosis

This section provides an overview of how the elaborated ADSR process is applied in the context of this thesis in concrete terms, including the Diagnosis, Design, Implementation and Evolution stages. Figure 25 illustrates the five elements of the ADSR Cycle for the diagnosis. The related contents to this stage of the process are part of Chapter 1 and Chapter 2 of this thesis.

Figure 3-6. ADR principles with the project stages - Diagnosis

Problem formulation

During this initial stage of the research, the *problem formulation* relates to the identification of an overall aim for the research. Theoretical thematic literature and systematic literature review as well as long year practical experience in the commercial real estate business and related knowledge of the day-to-day operations at Steiner AG and the academic literature have been used to inform the formulation of a research problem as set out in Chapter 1.

Literature review (Artefact 1)

The *Artefact* of the *Diagnosis* stage is the systematic literature review following Tranfield et al. (2003) undertaken during this thesis. Information on the used methodological approach are laid out in detail in Chapter 2 and the point is only taken up here for a complete description of the ADR process. The literature review showed four most important problems. First, the main problem is the asymmetric information where apparent asymmetric information which might lead to information failure and as such represent a risk of additional financial cost and project failure. Second, the problem of keeping separated ledgers often leads to data redundancies and data manipulation of the separate record keeping which impose a risk on the reporting trust to the investor. Third, the problem of using traditional human intervention systems

assumes that human people are not machines and there is a risk of data mistakes due to faulty record keeping. Third, those mistakes and separate record databases accompanied by the asymmetric information results into additional effort of search and correction costs which cause transaction costs. Those transaction costs are caused due to those deficiencies of intermediaries (middlemen) which are involved in those transactions. A stronger, encrypted, and automated system would systematically decrease such related costs and ultimately provide stakeholders a cheaper way of making business which ultimately should reflect on higher returns for investors and sellers.

Evaluation and Reflection

During the *evaluation*, the results of the systematic literature review are assessed to identify their suitability to provide the necessary theoretical basis for this thesis. The literature analysed in the systematic review is therefore placed in the context of the relevant theories for this thesis. The subsequent *reflection* leads to the insight that to get a comprehensive overview of the subject, a wider body of literature would need to be considered. Thus, Chapter 2 adds an overview of relevant theory in the context of this thesis.

Next to the systematic review of the literature, an explorative survey investigating the customers' acceptance towards digital real estate has been conducted to assess the suitability of the identified topic and research aim and to make an informed choice of the related technological foundations. The survey has applied the empirical methodology based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology - UTAUT (Venkatesch, 2016). The remaining output is concerned with checking the model assumptions of normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and independence of the residuals. Residuals are the differences between the observed and predicted responses. The quantitative survey has applied the OLS Regression method to identify the relevant independent variables explaining the residuals of the OLS Regression function as outlined below.

OLS Regression Function:

$$y_i = \mathbf{x}_i\boldsymbol{\beta} + \varepsilon_i$$

Y Customer behaviour = 1.283 + 0.2 gender + 0.331 blockchain technology + 0.302 technology innovation –0.369 income and price + 0.18 data security.

Figure 3-7. ADR – Previous quantitative results based on OLS Regression

Learning

Previous reflection on the regression testing has determined by both OLS Regression (Ordinary Least Squares) and determination of Auxiliary regression (Hackl, 2013; Poddig, 2008) which are presented in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2. ADR Evolution – Survey Approach, Mapping variables

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.283	0.193		6.652	0.000***
gender of respondent	0.382	0.052	0.2	7.337	0.000***
age of respondent	0.007	0.014	0.01	0.509	0.611
bank divisions	0.028	0.021	0.041	1.329	0.184
blockchain technology	0.243	0.016	0.331	14.742	0.000***
technology and innovation	0.189	0.019	0.302	9.719	0.000***
Income and price	-0.386	0.022	-0.369	-17.302	0.000***
regulation georegion	0.027	0.019	0.032	1.472	0.141
data security	-0.021	0.019	-0.035	-1.114	0.266
	0.134	0.021	0.18	6.292	0.000***

Previous analytical statistics have proved the most valuable parameters to explore the digital transformation of banking models. For that reason, the customer behavior has been chosen as dependent variable, whereas the yellow highlighted variables were identified as

independent variables such as gender, blockchain technology, technology innovation, income and price and security.

The *learning* phase of the *diagnosis* cycle makes use of the information gathered from both, the systematic review and relevant theory to derive the relevant research gaps for this thesis that build the foundation for the next step in the ADSR process.

- *Normality*: the residuals should be normally distributed about the predicted responses.
- *Linearity*: the residuals should have a straight-line relationship with the predicted responses.
- *Homoscedasticity*: the variance of the residuals about predicted responses should be the same for all predicted responses.
- *Histogram*: shows the frequencies / probability per expression of a continuous variable and allows to check potential asymmetries in the distribution of the residuals.
- *Symmetry*: tends to indicate a normal distribution.
- *Scatterplot*: shows the relationship of residuals between standardized Predicted Value and Standardized Residual by checking the relationship on linearity assumptions. The points should have the same dispersion about this line over the predicted value range.

3.7.2 ADSR Phase 2 - Design

The figure below illustrates the five elements of the ADSR Cycle for the Design. The related contents to this stage of the process are part of Chapter 4 of this thesis.

Figure 3-8. ADSR principles with the project stages - Design

Problem formulation

After completing the diagnosis phase, this study provides the design and analysis of the best suitable methods how to design and create an Artefact as a solution for the identified problem and research aim, first in a conceptual way and then, during the implementation phase, produced a prototype.

The problem of the old design has been resolved by many researchers in the past. However, a most suitable conceptual model is based on the previous literature review from the DSR within the real estate technology models. On the one hand, the design concept of real estate commercial contract has been drafted by the Opendankker/Wouda, (2019). First, the study showed a redesign conceptual model based on the Grounded Theory study for the current transaction process of an shopping building under classical contract as status quo and the design from the current real estate contract as of today's situation which is accompanied by buyer, seller and the third party- human intermediaries to the new design by algorithmic mechanism / coded-based design. Second, the design science has also been applied to transform the commercial real estate leasing as described by Karamitsos (2019). The research used a conceptual model to present the blockchain and smart contract for a specific domain for renting residential and business buildings is examined which were compared before the and after the conceptual prototype to determine the effect of smart contract with the various components for the real estate industry implementation.

Artefact Creation (New Design)

First, the Thesis diagnosed the literature review for most viable factors, (i) real estate models, (ii) business transaction costs, (iii) decentralised / blockchain technology and (iv) legal aspects. *Second*, multiple factors were structured into key drivers – adoption, process, business skills, transaction costs, security, governance, and compliance. *Third*, the new approach follows the principles of – fast/frictionless, transparent, inclusive, error resistant and results into lower transaction cost. *Fourth*, the key factors/ drivers are considered in the value flow model new approach where buyer and seller are P2P connected – buyer/seller as well all other real estate contract stakeholders (investors, real estate owner, property information, security protection aml/kyc) as P2P nodes are integrated over the decentralized algorithmic code.

Figure 3-9. ADSR – New Design

Evaluation

To tackle the design phase, and the production of our conceptual design, we have decided to take the route of interviewing industry experts in order and nuance our findings from empirical experience and literature review. Formally, twenty industry experts from real estate and with experience of blockchain in Middle East, Europe and the USA was interviewed (see Table 3-3). Subsequently, the interviews were transcribed, coded and common factors that would ultimately influence the design of the artefact were extracted. The design phase has been informed by the results of the semi-structured interviews (Saunders et al., 2012).

Table 3-3. Interview Questions

#	Questions
1	How is your interaction with block-chain and what projects have you worked on with regards tool blockchain/smart contracts?
2	Are smart contracts a feasible substitute to the legacy system which includes paperwork, bank transfer and series of interest rates and commissions?
3	If Smart contracts are a feasible option and negate heavy fee structure, why do we still rely on the legacy system? What are the roadblocks?
4	Will smart contracts be customizable for real estate contracts?
5	Conflict resolution responsibilities generally fall on the broker or the legal court (after transaction). Will Lawyers be equipped to handle disputes once it's implemented through smart contracts? Or will a part of legality still not be under the control of smart contracts?
6	Scalability has always been an issue with block-chain. Do you think Smart Contracts will face scalability issues if Real estate incorporates this.
7	What would be the challenges of having an end-to-end seamless blockchain based escrow with respect to real estate finance?
8	What will be the legal issues while implementing smart contracts? As real estate is heavily regulated, and smart contracts will have less regulation.
9	Smart Contracts will replace the agent in the agent-centric transactions as the agent will no more be the middle of this ecosystem. How will this affect brokerage? (Pros/Cons)
10	Though transparency increases with Smart Contracts about the lender's payment history etc., will It be trustworthy as it heavily relies on Programmed code and a bug could potentially be disastrous?

Reflection

The reflection of the design phase is to explore options based on the initial research problem and reflect the design knowledge of what is feasible for the following implementation of prototype. Depending on the course of the Interview, the order of the questions may have varied and questions arising from the context of the Interview may have been added (Saunders et al., 2012).

This study applied the qualitative content analysis to discover thoughts based on experience of experts from potential areas of improvement in the commercial real estate industry. For this purpose, we have designed a ten questions questionnaire that will be used in our twenty Skype interviews with subject matter experts related to the industry. The interviews were conducted not in physical person due to COVID-19 impacts and to reach global network of respondents. The reflection helped to change the initial conceptual model for this research and allowed to discover trends and potential high impact areas in which blockchain will play a significant role.

Learning

The lessons from the qualitative content analysis provided a foundation of discovering from the thoughts and experience of domain experts in industry. In this regard, lessons learned were addressed to improve the conceptual model based on the semi-structure interviews and improve the basis conceptual model with those gained expert industry insights and develop the design principles for the most suitable architecture and solution design to build a prototype in the ADSR implementation process stage.

3.7.3 ADSR Phase 3 - Implementation

Figure 3-10 below illustrates the five elements of the ADSR cycle for the design. The related contents to this stage of the process are part of Chapter 4.1 of this thesis.

Figure 3-10. ADR principles with the project stages - Implementation

Problem formulation

After completing the diagnosis phase, the thesis provides the implementation phase of the best suitable methods how to develop and create an Artefact as a solution for the identified problem and research aim, first in a conceptual way and then, during the implementation phase, produced a prototype. In the implementation phase, the problem formulation relates to the transformation of the developed conceptual model (i.e. the Artefact of the design phase) into a prototype. In this context, the implementation is the proof of concept/ prototype development by algorithmic mechanism / code based.

Artefact testing

Figure 3-11. Smart contract - workflow diagram

Evaluation

The evaluation of the Research Framework - Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM) is conducted based on the recommended criteria to evaluate the goodness of the solution (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2018). The “ensembled Artefact” is evaluated on criteria’s such as architecture analysis, optimization, static and dynamic analysis, informed argument, scenarios, limitation and communication which involves investigation of a particular contemporary phenomenon (blockchain technology) within its real-world context using multiple sources of evidence (Smart Contract ERC 777, 820).

Reflection

The reflection covers the application of the blockchain technology and explores the limitations. the blockchain technology itself does not provide ownership rights and purely the use of the blockchain enables the User to use the Title rights. Blockchain technology is also purely code-based algorithm and does not imply the social topics such as cultural background for land registration (e.g. land registration of high-conflict areas). Beyond technical assessment, also legal side of blockchain law has been introduced in Liechtenstein and the standard for blockchain technology was officially released in the regulatory framework. Hence the implementation of the proposed model is quite complex under real circumstances such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller.

Learning

The learning of this proof of concept to investigate and demonstrate a real implementation scenario and show that the development of the running system may require substantial resources. Therefore, broader independent evaluation among researchers may rise questions how to consider developing prototypes. The real implementation would only be possible if the data, such as reports, attachment and frameworks are standardized. Once the data harmonisation has been achieved, the record-keeping application could be linked to external databases by application programming interface (API) for the purpose of automatically data validation. Data protection is a separate limitation topic where need to be distinguished which data can and should be stored on blockchain, for cases when blockchain must become a reliable source of information, and which data must store and protected (for example, as per EU protection GDPR framework), therefore, cannot be disclosed on blockchain and may have issues with storing this data in third party servers.

3.7.4 ADSR Phase 4 - Evolution

Evaluation approaches may include observational methods (case studies, field studies); analytical methods (static analysis, dynamic analysis); experimental methods (controlled experiments, simulations); testing (functional, structural); or descriptive methods (informed arguments, scenarios) (Hevner et al, 2004).

Figure 3-12. ADSR principles with the project stages - Evolution

Problem formulation

A common distinction for research approaches is between a deductive approach that refers to testing theory or hypothesis and an inductive approach that refers to building theory or hypothesis (Saunders et al., 2012). The research design explains the chosen research strategy, choice of research methods and the subsequent process of data collection and data analysis as well as the time horizon of the research project. It constitutes a general plan of how the research question will be answered (Saunders et al., 2012) and clarifies the process of how the research project is conducted (Robson, 2002).

Previous analytical statistics have proved the most valuable parameters to explore the digital transformation of banking models. For that reason, the customer behaviour has been chosen as dependent variable, whereas the yellow highlighted variables were identified as independent variables such as gender, blockchain technology, technology innovation, income and price and security. The survey has applied the empirical methodology based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology - UTAUT (Venkatesch, 2016) to verify the utility / satisfaction for the customer behaviour. The utility is shown in yellow marked fields (1) sharing economy, technological improvements in user experience (2), innovation and smart coded on Blockchain technology (3) and social aspects- gender inclusion (4).

Artefact (market survey and interview questions)

The Artefact of the evolution stage is a large-scale survey used to evaluate the developed prototype (i.e. the Artefact of the implementation stage). A survey was chosen to gain insights from the real estate market by carrying out an empirical quantitative study and to validate the prototype solution on the willingness to accept the new design real estate contract (1) and prototype development (2).

Table 3-4. ADSR Evolution – Market Survey Questions

Survey Question	Survey answer items	SPSS Variables items
1. What is your gender?	Female	1.00
	Male	2.00
	Other	3.00
	prefer not to say	4.00
2. How old are you?	younger than 20 (1)	1.00
	20 to 29 (2)	4.00
	30 to 39 (3)	2.00
	40 to 49 (4)	3.00
	50 to 59 (5)	5.00
	60 to 69 (5)	6.00
	70 or older	7.00
	prefer not to say	8.00
3. What region are you currently living in?	Europe / Middle East	1.00
	Africa	2.00
	Asia	3.00
	North America	4.00
	South America	5.00
	prefer not to say	6.00
4. How would you rate your level of experience in dealing with Blockchain Technology? 5. How are you related to the real estate industry?	no experience	1.00
	basic experience	2.00
	advanced experience	3.00
	proficient experience	4.00
	have no experience in the real estate industry	0.00
	I own a piece of property (apartment / house)	1.00
	I am currently working in the industry (broker, builder, etc.)	1.00
	I am investing in real estate	1.00
5. How are you related to the finance industry?	I have no experience in the finance industry	0.00
	I have personnel experience with the finance	1.00
	I am currently working in the finance industry (broker, builder, etc.)	1.00
	I am investing in financial instruments	1.00
6. Have you already participated in ICOs, STOs, or other token sales?	Yes	1.00
	No	0.00
8. Do you have investments in stocks, bonds, or other financial products?	Yes	1.00
	No	0.00
9. Do you find it difficult to invest online?	Yes	1.00
	No	0.00
10. How attractive would it be to invest in Real estate Digitally	I don't care	0.00
	Not attractive	1.00
	Somewhat attractive	2.00
	Very attractive	3.00
11. What is your average monthly income (in USD)?	Less than 100 (1)	
	100 to 999	1.00
	1000 to 1999	2.00
	2000 to 2999	3.00
	3000 to 3999	4.00
	4000 to 4999	5.00
	More than 5000 (7)	6.00
	prefer not to say	7.00
12. How important investing a part of monthly income?	Very Important	
	Important (1)	
	Moderately Important (2)	
	Slightly Important (3)	
	Unimportant (4)	
13. How much of your monthly income do you invest?	nothing	0.00
	up to 10%	1.00
	up to 20%	2.00
	up to 30%	3.00

	over 30%	4.00
14. What kind of returns would expect by digitally investing into Real estate?	<4%	0.00
	4-7%	1.00
	7-10%	2.00
	10-15%	3.00
	>15%	4.00
	not applicable	5.00
15. How would you describe your stance towards cryptocurrencies?	very negative	1.00
	rather negative	2.00
	neutral	3.00
	rather positive	4.00
	very positive	5.00
	not applicable	6.00
16. What would you say is the most difficult while investing?	Nothing is difficult	1.00
	Finding the right tool	2.00
	Finding the right investments	3.00
	General lack of knowledge	4.00
	Difficulty to pass compliance checks	5.00
	Lack of income	6.00
	>> other, please specify	7.00

The access to data and sampling was initially identified in line with literature gaps and current separate models, a survey is carried out to empirically evaluate factors which confirm or reject the initial assumptions from the thematic analysis – the transformation of the of traditional real estate commercial contract into the digital smart contract on the blockchain Ethereum technology. The foundation for the questions is framed in the systematic literature review, relevant literature background and general knowledge from conferences and practical real estate industry.

- First, the questionnaire has been prepared for the quantitative data collection.
- Second, the questions are designed to build the variables for the statistical analysis which will be tested in the statistical tool.
- Third, the questions have been mapped into the statistical tool variables (e.g. SPSS).
- Fourth, the data collection for the survey has been distributed worldwide (six georegions described in the Legal Section (regional sampling - EMEA, North America, South America, -Asia, Euroasia, Pacific).
- Fifth, the scale for questions is mapping with the respondents' possible answers items.
- Sixth, the survey raw data will be imported into the statistical tool for the descriptive and analytical statistics purpose.

Table 3-5. Action Design Research (ADR) Evolution – Quantitative survey and variables description

Survey answer items	Testing Scenario
1. Gender	This variable will be used to test if gender can be a significant factor in being more inclined or not to invest in Real estate through crypto currencies. Our assumption would be that males, because of sociological factors, would be more prone to invest in Real estate and even more inclined to do so with crypto currencies as the Thesis can already see in existing statistics.
2. Crypto_Actif	This variable would check if respondents are already active or not in the field of cryptocurrencies, this would most likely be a significant factor in their involvement with a project like the one described in our Artefacts
4. Financiai involvement	The Thesis would like to check if our respondents are already involved in the Financial Industry. the Thesis believe that respondents already involved in the Financial Industry will have a higher interest in this kind of products, or in the contrary may have a stronger opinion against this kind of alternative finances.
4. Investments	The Thesis purposes to check if our respondents are currently involved in any kind of other investment activities to check if people that have already crossed the path from non-investor to investors would be interested in our concept and the kind of products the Thesis could offer.
5. Age	With this variable the Thesis purposes to check if age has an impact on the crypto awareness but also on how people will perceive our project and its capabilities.
6. Region	It is our belief that crypto currencies and even more investing in crypto currencies is a geographical phenomenon. the Thesis believe interest in our project will be correlated to regional factors as the Thesisll.
7. Literacy	The Thesis will check whether our respondents are knowledgeable in blockchain or are not to see if this concept is only attractable to people with a strong knowledge of the core technology, this variable will be able to tell us if our concept can ultimately touch a large enough part of the population to be interesting to other companies. In other words, the Thesis are testing scalability.
8. Real_Estate_Literracy	With this variable the Thesis check the knowledge level of our respondents regarding the real estate industry.
9. Inv_Difficult y	The Thesis purposes to check how difficult, if at all, it is for people to invest online in the Real estate industry. In fact, our concept directly addresses this issue and it could be a good factor to see if such a concept makes sense in the first place.
10. Inv_Digital_Attractivity	The Thesis purposes to check the feeling of our respondents regarding the attractiveness of investing digitally. Would they feel secure? Would they feel trust towards such a platform? Those are all questions that will have an impact on this variable.
11. Income	The Thesis purposes to check the level of income of our respondents
12. Portion_Invested	The Thesis purposes to see how financially organized our respondents are by checking what amount they invest in proportion to their income.
13. Return_Expected	the Thesis purposes to check if the return expected from this kind of investment is aligned to the kind of return investing in Real estate can provide. the Thesis have been aware that most crypto investors do it because they believe Blockchain will provide them with higher return. Although this is true, it would never bring more than a few percent more than in REITs or other investment vehicles.
14. Crypto_Favorable	The Thesis purposes to check the opinion on crypto currencies of our respondents to see if it could have an impact on our project adoption.
15. Difficulty_to_Invest	The Thesis purposes to check our respondent's opinion on the difficulty to invest in Real estate and see if they believe easier processes would ultimately unlock their investments.

3.5.2. Evaluation (mapping of survey variables with SPSS parameters)

Since the literature review does not provide a comprehensive empirical study on the willingness to accept the smart contract in the real estate industry, the thesis goes into the primary – field research with the descriptive statistics. the statistics help to investigate the central trends, deviations and gaussian distribution of the data. In addition, analytical statistics are applied to find potential relationships among those Items (see Table 3-6).

Table 3-6: ADSR Evolution – Quantitative survey and mapping variables

Variable	Name	Type	Width	Decimal	Label	Value Labels	Missing Values	Columns	Align	Measure	Role
1	Gender	Numeric ...	2	0	Respondent's gender	{1, Male}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
2	Age	Numeric ...	3	0	Respondent's age	None	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
3	Region	Numeric ...	8	0	Respondent's region	{1, Europe / Middle East ...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
4	Literacy	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's literacy i	{1,00, Never heard of it} ...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
5	Real_Estate_Li	Numeric ...	8	0	Respondent's literacy ii	{1, I own a piece of prop ...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
6	Crypto_Actif	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's activity wi	{1,00, Yes}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
7	Financial_invo	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's involvme	{1,00, Yes}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
8	Investments	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent has investr	{1,00, Yes}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
9	Inv_Difficulty	Numeric ...	8	2	Evaluation of the online	{1,00, Yes}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
10	Inv_Digital_At	Numeric ...	8	2	Investing in Real Estate c	{1,00, I don't care}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
11	Income	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's income	{1,00, Less than 100}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
12	Portion_Invest	Numeric ...	8	2	Portion of income inves	{1,00, 0%}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
13	Return_Expect	Numeric ...	8	2	Return expected from a	{1,00, <4%}...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
14	Crypto_Favora	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's opinion o	{1,00, I don't have an op ...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
15	Difficulty_to_i	Numeric ...	8	2	Respondent's opinion o	{1,00, Nothing is difficul ...	None	8	Right	Scale	Input

The empirical market survey is to explore public opinion the biggest Geo-Regions and decide on the representative sample (n 1000) and reflect on the previous identified correlated factors. In the current version of the study, where the factors have been identified from the semi-structured content analysis and following 15 variables might be set into the general Multiple Regression Testing (MRT):

- Descriptive statistics of the variables
- Correlations (Pearson, Kendal-Tau)
- Linear and Multivariate Regression
- Tests on Normality (Shapiro Wilk)
- Linearity (RESET)
- Multicollinearity Diagnostics (VIF)
- Homo vs. Heteroscedasticity (Breusch Pagan, White Test)
- Autocorrelation (Durbin Watson)

Since the literature review does not provide a comprehensive empirical study on the willingness to accept the smart contract in the real estate industry, the thesis goes into the primary – field research with the descriptive statistics. The statistics helped to investigate the central trends, deviations and gaussian distribution of the data. The results are explained on the details level in the Chapter 5 and customer acceptance factors of the most viable parameters of the novel prototype solution.

3.5.3. Reflection (regression equation to reflect each variable relation)

The reflection of the evaluation phase is to derive the key learnings from the quantitative data analysis of the large-scale online questionnaire. In this regard, the learning is to explore opinion from the general audience in the Real estate market by conducting a survey for specific regions and decide on the representative sample (n 1000) and describe what has been learned from the survey outcomes and refer to Chapter 4 for more details and how this may change your prototype/the future product. As outlined lessons learned of OLS Regression method (Hackl, 2013, pp. 190-194 and Poddig, 2008, p. 328), the Thesis will iteratively identify new factors which are relevant for Commercial real estate Smart Contract. For this reason, the OLS Regression will be applied to identify the relevant independent variables explaining the residuals of the OLS Regression function as outlined below:

OLS Regression Function:

$$y_i = \mathbf{x}_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \varepsilon_i$$

Y Smart Contract acceptance = E (Residum) + Beta factors (X) multiplied each of the variable
Y Smart Contract Acceptance = Gender+ Crypto_Actif+ Financial_involvement+
Investments+Age + Region+ Literacy + Real_Estate_Literacy+ Investment Difficulty+
Investment digital attractiveness +Income
+ Portion_Invested+ Return_Expected+Crypto_Favorable+ Difficulty_to_Invest

The Ramsey Regression Specification Error Test (RESET test) is testing generally to a misspecification of a regression model. The reasons for a misspecification can either be missing important explanatory variables or a non-linear relationship between dependent and independent variables. Ramsey could show that the fitted values y is in a potentiated form (y^2, y^3, \dots) represent a suitable approximation for a misspecification, where a potentiation up to the fourth power is considered sufficient (Ramsey, 1969, pp. 350-371). The Ramsey regression test analyses the first four powers of the fitted values extended regression model. If those recorded independent variables y^2, y^3, y^4 make a significant contribution to the explanation of a misspecification, the Null hypothesis (H_0) must be accepted. In this case, the sum of the squared residuals SSE (Error Sum of Squares) for the extended model is smaller than for the original model, i.e. $SSE(e) < SSE(u)$. The questions are designed to identify the Smart Contract acceptance as the dependent variable and each question as independent variable such as 15 variables. Each of the independent variables indicates different classes and the calculation of mean with standard deviation. Next step is to evaluate linearity and normal distribution with the F-Test and to provide significance of the independent variables with T-Test. Anova F-Test is a test of whether R^2 is significantly greater than zero. If the P-Value

(Sig.) is less than 0.05, then is our test is significant, and the regression model is significant. The T-Test compares multiple averages (means) and describes whether the means differences are different from each other. Furthermore, the T-Test explains how significant the differences are and proves if those differences could have happened by chance If $p < 0.05$ - Variance in the two conditions is not significantly different If $p > 0.05$ statistically significant difference between the mean number of independent predictors. In this case, R2 is significantly greater than zero and therefore our predictors can account for a significant amount of variance of the Variable: Customer behaviour $F(\text{Regression, Residual}) = F \text{ Value}$. The F-Statistic Test purposes to analyse deeper analysis of variances whereas the F-Critical Test shows Nonparametric alternatives (Kelley and Sawilowski, pp. 343-359). The Chi-Squared Test measures the deviation between observed and expected values. The Chi square test is a statistical test which measures the association between two categorical variables (Ugoni and Walker, 1995, pp. 61-64). In this context, the statistical independence of the survey data sets will be assured by the Chi-Square Test (Ugoni and Walker, 1995)

$$X^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

To decide if this value is big enough (and the observed deviation is statistically significant) we control the p-value. The SPSS tool provides the p-value is represented by a column asymptotic significance and indicates a p value of 0.000 which is less than alpha of 0.05. Our deviation is statistically significant. Earlier the hypotheses were formulated as: Autocorrelation can be measured with Durbin Watson Test (Least Square Method) and Dickie Fuller Tests (Time Series analysis). Dickie Fuller test measures values of the past that have an impact on the current values when the value of the previous year has a great impact on the current value (e.g. share prices). Durbin Watson (DW) investigates autocorrelation coefficients and can be measured by the distance between the positive and negative series of data points of the linear equation based on the least square model and indicates the closeness of the randomly distributed points to the linear trend equation (Durbin and Watson, 1950, pp. 409-428). In this context, the evolution of the of Artefacts (Conceptual model and Prototype) is built and for triangulation reasons to take further route of empirical survey in the public space to confirm the prototype findings from empirical experience and literature review.

Further research needs to be conducted to evaluate a better characterization and structuring of the Artefact evaluation process analysing the field data, we inferred a precedence hierarchy for different Artefact types, as well as nine new opportunities for entry points for the continuity of DSR studies. Recommendation for Researchers: The four attributes identified for analysing

evaluation processes Future Research: proposes even nine entry points to be identified serve as an inspiration for researchers to give continuity to DSR projects. Therefore, the ADSRM research is the data cannot be taken for granted when deriving findings to mirror the artefacts with the Real estate practical industry.

Learning (verified triangulation for the End-to-End- Process of ADSRM)

This study uses the “triangulation” strategy and rolls out quantitative survey analysis of (Saunders, 2012; Creswell, 2014) to explore empirically by applying statistical descriptive and analytical tests, if a full digitize real estate investment crypto-based blockchain process would be regarded as transaction costs reduction and process improvement (e.g. transparency, immutability, decentralised consensus mechanism) resulting into a higher trust for the investor and potential transaction costs by cutting the third party. The Thesis uses the multi-entry ADR research process to contend that this elaborated ADR process model significantly improves the facility with which ADR researchers and ADR adds to the DR process of Gregor and Hevner (2014) and Peffers (2017). In this instance, the thesis provides a novel conceptual design (1), prototype development (2) and empirical market survey for the commercial real estate industry rather than one single development use case, and (3), it connects the bridge in the intervention domain, and the innovative artefacts being created and evaluated within each cycle.

Figure 3-13. Multi-level entry points for the strategy – modified model

3.5.4. Ethical Considerations

In the context of the entire thesis in general and in the context of data collection in particular, transparent, and comprehensible procedures as well as ethically correct conduct form the basis of the adopted procedure. Some of the measures that have been taken to ensure compliance with ethical standards:

- 1) Provision of detailed information to all participants in the data collection process on the use of the collected data, anonymisation and citation

- 2) Blacking out all passages containing identifying, personal or company information in transcripts and the thesis, including disguising the clear names of all participants.
- 3) Keep data records from our quantitative study confidential and for the strict use of this thesis. In that sense we have been focusing on keeping the data we have collected private and anonymised at every level of our study.

3.5.5. Limitations

Although the ADSR approach of this thesis is based on a comprehensive perspective on the potential design science problems in the practice. However, recent criticisms of the application of the DSR approach have pointed out the need to make it more approachable and less confusing to overcome deficiencies such as the unrealistic evaluation. Empirical evidence was found of a precedence hierarchy among different types of artefacts, as well as nine new opportunities for entry points for the continuity of DSR studies. Only 14% of the DSR Artefacts underwent an evaluation by typical end users, characterizing a tenth type of entry point. Regarding the evaluation process, four aspects were identified, which demonstrated that 86% of DSR Artefact evaluations are unrealistic (De Sordi, 2020). Further research needs to be conducted to evaluate a better characterization and structuring of the Artefact evaluation process analysing the field data, we inferred a precedence hierarchy for different Artefact types, as well as nine new opportunities for entry points for the continuity of DSR studies.

4. ADSR: ARTEFACTS, CONCEPTUAL MODEL, AND PROTOTYPE

4.1 Justification for the ADSR

The ADSR is a cyclical four-stage approach (see Figure 4-1) to solve scientific problems with a key focus on practice through a design lens (Sein *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 4-1. Combination ADR principles with the project stages

livari (2015) proposes two strategies for ADSR design science research: (1) designing an IT meta-artefact in response to a set of problems (class), which can then be tested in a specific context and (2) solving a specific problem for a client through a concrete artefact, which then provides the basis to distil a generalised solution for a class of problems from the experience of its implementation (Strategy 2). As stated previously, ADSR does not intend to solve a problem within a specific organisational context, but rather to derive a meta-artefact that can be applied to a wider class of real estate transaction problems (Sein *et al.* 2011). Subsequently, the ADSR design guiding principles are built following Sein *et al.*'s (2011) recommendations to apply a) design principles; (b) these principles should address a class of problem (i.e. generalisation of the problem instance and the solution instance – Strategy 1), and (c) achieve an innovative outcome solution.

4.2. Summary of the Application of the ADSR Methodology

In this study, the ADSR approach (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019) is adopted, describing the four phases: (1) Diagnosis, (2) Design, (3) Implementation, (4) Evolution and four stages for each phase: Problem formulation (i), Artefact development (ii), Reflection and evaluation (iii) and Formulation of learning (iv). Consequently, the ADSR methodology results in theory ingrained Artefacts in each Phase under the Stage: Artefact development as shown below (see Table 4-1 below).

Table 4-1. ADSR Methodology – Phases and Stages as applicable to the scope of this research (source: Mullarkey and Hevner, 2018, p. 4)

Artefact Group	ADSR - Methodology - Phases and Stages	ADSR – Application
Group 1 – Diagnosis (Literature Review)	Diagnosis Phase	
	Stage 1: Problem formulation	Problem is formulated based on the traditional design of the contract
	Stage 2: Artefact development (Artefact 1 “as is” model)	Diagnosis of the weaknesses of the traditional contract based on the comprehensive (thematic) and systematic literature review
	Stage 3: Reflection and evaluation	During the ongoing diagnosis, important issues were discovered, reflected and evaluated
	Stage 4: Formalization of learning	A set of design principles was articulated, positioning the case problem as an instance of a class of traditional contracts within the Real estate industry
Group 2 - Conceptual Model	Design Phase	
	Stage 1: Problem formulation	Problem was formulated based on the design of the AS-IS-Concept for pre-concept before actual implementation deployment.
	Stage 2: Artefact development (Artefact 2a Pre-design and 2b Conceptual model design based on expert interviews)	Pre-design of the new conceptual model final design (our second Artefact)
	Stage 3: Reflection and evaluation	By means of qualitative content analysis, the TARGET design model is added with synthesis interview categories during the reflection and evaluation phase.
	Stage 4: Formalization of learning	Final design of the new conceptual model TARGET (our second Artefact)
Group 3- Prototype solution	Implementation Phase	
	Stage 1: Problem formulation	Problem is formulated based on the new conceptual model TARGET for the actual deployment
	Stage 2: Artefact development (Artefact 3a solution architecture and prototype development 3b)	Development of the new prototype solution based on the diagnosis, qualitative content analysis and practice sensemaking activities
	Stage 3: Reflection and evaluation	Reflection stage is characterized by multiple rounds of elaboration and iteration.
	Stage 4: Formalization of learning	Learning lessons from implementation are taken for the future research discussion.
Group 4- Prototype market validation	Evolution	
	Stage 1: Problem formulation	Evaluate the prototype solution (testing) and the evolution of Artefacts (in-use) over time (empirical survey)
	Stage 2: Artefact development (Artefact 4a prototype validation supported by an empirical market survey and final evaluation 4b)	Problem is formulated based on systematic review of the literature, an explorative survey investigating the customers' acceptance towards previous empirical study of digital real estate to assess the suitability of the prototype solution
	Stage 3: Reflection and evaluation	Market survey - empirical survey for evaluation the utility effectiveness comparison between the existing and new design.
	Stage 4: Formalization of learning	The final evaluation confirmed the utility and effectiveness of the blockchain system and captured several benefits to different type of supply chain stakeholders.
		The final evaluation confirmed the utility of the artefact and captured several benefits (i.e., speed, transparency, security, quality, validity, trust, cost)

As stated earlier, the aim here is to apply ADSR design principles to address a class of problems of a real estate industry (Iivari, 2015) with the aim to provide a state-of-the-art “as is” design model, taking into account the key theories, models, and previous research on the research subject – commercial real estate contract (Peppers *et al.*, 2012). The diagnosis has thus been underpinned by the literature review (thematic and systematic review) to depict the “as is” model (Artefact 1 “as is” model; see Figure 4-2). Consequently, following from the “as-is” modelling as part of the diagnosis, the design phase is based on the problem formulation that includes findings from the diagnosis-related literature review. The commercial real estate transaction (Artefact 2a: pre-design of a full conceptual model) is therefore built by addressing its current weaknesses (i.e. information asymmetries, process inefficiencies). These have been identified through the literature review as well as by considering professional experience. This yields an unvalidated pre-design that sets the foundation of the new conceptual model, which is then externally validated through the content analysis of expert interviews (Artefact 2b: validated conceptual design).

Once the conceptual design has been validated through the expert interviews, the conceptual model is transformed into the technical implementation model by mapping of all factor categories to a proof-of-concept model in line with the practice-based concept evaluation of usefulness as recommended by (Prat, Comyn-Wattiau and Akoka, 2015). The technical implementation model entails the prototype design (model 3a prototype design) and solution architecture (model 3b prototype architecture) as well as demonstration of the functional feasibility of the research pilot solution (model 3c prototype development).

As shown in the logic of the ADSR model (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019), the evaluation itself entails prototype testing (4a) and prototype statistics (4b). In this sense, the prototype smart contract is developed on the Ethereum Blockchain (Github) and tested on various operational scenarios (sender-receiver relations) to determine the proof-of-use and demonstrate the prototype utility and process efficiencies (4a prototype testing). Parallely, the prototype proof of value is determined by the analytical statistics which is carried out by empirical market survey (N=700) participants to investigate whether a prototype solution can create value (4b prototype statistics - proof of value). The research ends only when practitioners routinely use a solution in the field and should be covered beyond this PhD research by future research (Nunamaker *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 4-2. Big Picture – Application of the ADSR Methodology – project stages with Artefacts

4.3. Application of the ADSR Methodology – Diagnosis, Artefact 1 – “As IS” model (old design)

The Ph.D. methodology has a structured research approach aligned on ADSR by Mullarkey and Hevner (2019). The iterative cycle undergoes each phase – diagnosis, design, implementation, and evolution as shown in the Figure 4-3. In these terms, the ADSR research iterates Market Knowledge between development/creation and evaluation phases rather than flowing linearly from one phase into the next.

Figure 4-3: Phase Diagnosis - Artefact 1- “As Is” model (old design)

The ADSR begins with the diagnosis phase – a comprehensive state of the art literature research to understand the structure of the traditional old design commercial real estate transaction, specifically the components such as real estate models, business and transaction cost models as well as legal aspects. As with other ADSR projects, this research process consists of iterative cycle - problem formulation (1), Artefact development (2), reflection and evaluation (3) and formalization of learnings (4).

Figure 4-4: Artefact 1- “As Is” model (old design) - Stages of the Diagnosis Phase

The ADSR research cycle (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019) starts with problem formulation of the traditional real estate contract (old model), iterative Artefact development – “AS-IS” model based on the driving forces / factors underpinned in the literature review. Once the comprehensive literature review is completed, the systematic literature review helps to focus on the research question by distilling the peer-reviewed journals which are relevant for this research topic (reflection and evaluation of the comprehensive literature review (3)). The systematic research helps to make a structured search string of a reproductive set of parameters by including and excluding entry criteria’s due to poor quality or outdated articles such as informal interviews, book reviews or other non-academic formats and learning of the distilled results of the systematic literature review (4). Furthermore, the synthesis is thus applied in conjunction with the qualitative content analysis to determine the most critical problems of the traditional contracts. Following from the systematic literature review and thematic content analysis, the following main problems are depicted as shown in Figure 4-5.

Problem formulation

During this initial stage of the PhD project, the *problem formulation* relates to the identification of an overall aim for the research. Both long year practical experience in the commercial real estate business and related knowledge of the day-to-day operations at Steiner AG and the academic literature have been used to inform the formulation of a research problem as set out in Chapter 1. Traditional commercial real estate process is a high complex process (see Figure 4-5) with the main components – actors/roles (buyer/seller), business processes and manual intervention steps for each stage (search, due-diligences, inspection, negotiation, payment, contract signature).)

Figure 4-5: Swiss Commercial real estate selling process (adapted from Bürgi and Nägeli, 2019)

Based on the identified thematic constructs, the transaction process of a Commercial real estate is considered challenging due to its cumbersome process structure consisting of several property brokers and legal structures, its illiquidity and heterogeneity and the lack of market transparency (Bürgi and Nägeli, 2019). In this sense, the identified thematic constructs (real estate, business transaction, technology and legal): Artefact Development – Artefact 1 “As is» model (old design) the research determines the key-driver factors for the traditional real estate contract (“As-is” model).

Artefact Creation

The *Artefact* of the *Diagnosis* phase is the systematic literature review following Tranfield et al. (2003) undertaken during this thesis. Information on the used methodological approach is laid out in detail in Chapter 2 and the point is only taken up here for a complete description of the ADR process. During the *evaluation*, the results of the systematic literature review are assessed to identify their suitability to provide the necessary theoretical basis for this thesis. The subsequent *reflection* leads to the insight that to get a comprehensive overview of the subject, a wider body of literature would need to be considered.

The Artefact “AS IS” (see Figure 4-6) – Model (Technology and database layer). Fourth, requirements on the legal aspects create problem of asset liquidity and barriers to scalable project finance (Morena et al., 2020; Konashevych, 2020c), legal market entry problems (Saul, Baum and Braesemann, 2020), legal environment has also influence on the bad investment climate, non-scalable finance, risk diversification and complex legal set-up for micro-investments (Kumar, Talasila and Pasumarthy, 2021; Gupta et al., 2020; Petukhina et al., 2021) Artefact “AS IS” – Model (Market regulations, later KYC/AML under Blockchain)

Figure 4-6: Artefact Development – Artefact 1 “As is» model (old design)

Evaluation and Reflection

The evaluation of traditional real estate model is conducted by the comprehensive literature research (thematic analysis) and systematic literature review where Karamitsos model (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018) peer-review-journal supported by various other

journals as provided below. First, the real estate model : the most important real estate models conclude on the problems between intermediaries (Krupa and Akhil, 2019), and associated trust weaknesses (Secinaro, Calandra and Biancone, 2021). In this, sense, real estate contract shows a high asymmetric information : one party in the current design always knows more about the contract than the other party (Krupa and Akhil, 2019; Duta, 2020; Shahab and Allam, 2020; Hoksbergen et al., 2021). Artefact “AS IS” – Model (Buyer and Seller - Actors and Roles) Second, business models explain process due diligence model (Just and Stapenhorst, 2018), problem of mistakes from paper-based recording practice (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018), well as high transaction costs speed of transaction (Hoxha, 2019; Sladić et al., 2021). Artefact “AS IS” – Model (i.e., business process and process layer) Third, the recurring breaks between intermediaries implicitly arise weaknesses associated with centralized trust: intermediaries as a centralized trust mechanism prone to errors prone to errors (Veuger, 2018) time-consuming and involve extra difficulties to cross-border operations (Garcia-Teruel, 2020), low efficiency and transparency resulting problem of speed of transaction (Hoxha, 2019; Sladić *et al.*, 2021).

Learning

The learning of the diagnosis phase generates scientific progress from previous state-of the art literature review helped to evaluate the biggest weaknesses of the traditional real estate model: Traditional paper-based real estate contracts are usually prone to errors, are time-consuming and involve extra difficulties to cross-border operations (Garcia-Teruel, 2020). It is worth to acknowledge that it can be argued that there are several flaws in the current design of the transaction process leading to six major learning effects for the design:

- (1) intermediaries (Krupa and Akhil, 2019; Morena *et al.*, 2020) and associated trust weaknesses (Secinaro, Calandra and Biancone, 2021; (Zavadskas, Antuheviciene and Turskis, 2021).
- (2) asymmetric information (Duta, 2020; Shahab and Allam, 2020; Zavadskas, Antuheviciene and Turskis, 2021).
- (3) speed of transaction (Hoxha, 2019; Sladić *et al.*, 2021).
- (4) transaction costs (Dakhli, Lafhaj and Mossman, 2019; Kalyuzhnova, 2018; Frolov, 2020; Mashatan and Roberts, 2017).
- (5) market entry (Saull, Baum and Braesemann, 2020),
- (6) investment management, non-scalable finance, risk diversification and complex legal set-up for micro-investments (Kumar, Talasila and Pasumarthy, 2021; Gupta *et al.*, 2020; Petukhina *et al.*, 2021)

Finally, the *learning* phase of the *diagnosis* cycle makes use of the information gathered from both, the systematic review and relevant theory to derive the relevant research gaps for this thesis that build the foundation for the next step in the ADSR process step as previous outlined.

4.4. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Design, Artefact 2 concept (2a Pre-Design and 2b New Design)

As this study follows the structured ADSR research approach by (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019), the next iterative cycle continues with the Design Phase.

Figure 4-7. Phase Design - Artefact 2- “To-Be” model

The aim of the design phase is to explore design options based on literature review (pre-design) and verify the design principles what is feasible for the optimised solution. In this sense, the problem statement of the commercial real estate transaction weaknesses are verified on the qualitative content analysis to critically evaluate previous literature-findings which undergoes an iterative cycle of problem formulation (1), artefact development (2), reflection and evaluation (3) and formalization of learnings (4) as illustrated in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8: Artefact 2- “To-Be” model (old design) - Stages of the Design Phase

4.4.1. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Design, Artefact 2 concept (2a Pre-Design)

Problem formulation

The problem formulation of the pre-analysis connects with the diagnosis phase where the comprehensive literature and systematic literature review derive the hypothesis for the relevant business context supported by the empirical statistical analysis. The pre-design helps to develop technology-based solution addressing existing drawbacks within the commercial real estate contracting. The pre-design is a baseline for the future target conceptual model where the hypothesis factors are set and tested by the control variable pre-exploratory experts interviews are conducted by means of qualitative content analysis technique (Saunders, 2012) According to Saunders (2012, p. 573) the “Content analysis is a specific analytical technique of categorising and coding text, voice and visual data using a systematic coding scheme to enable quantitative analysis. and “technique for the objective, systematic and quantitative description of the manifest content of communication and process of categorizing verbal or behavioural data to classify, summarize and tabulate the data” The questions are designed in accordance with the UWS Research Ethics Committee guidelines and primarily conceived for qualitative interviews with a certain target audience, professional industry experts from Real estate, those are adults from non-vulnerable populations and dealing with non-sensitive topics (Research Ethics Committee Platform, UWS, 2020). It is based on those criteria and in line with the theoretical DSR discussion in Section 2.2 that we design our research and claim our contributions. The Conceptual model represents the artefact of the ADR design phase. It takes the insights gained during the diagnosis phase, i.e. the literature review, and builds the foundation for the implementation stage, i.e. the development of a prototype solution. Therefore, it uses both, existing models identified in the context of the literature review and qualitative data gathered from a pre-study with 20 structured interviews. Industry experts provide information on which aspects beyond those identified during the diagnosis would need to be considered in the context of this thesis.

Subsequently, the pre-analysis design of the Conceptual Model is based on the key findings from the literature and the authors industry experience, the literature review synthesis concluded on the two most important research papers for the research design of conceptual model and the development of prototype solution. While the Opendankker and Wouda (2019) design of the third-party intermediaries in the commercial real estate process could be eliminated (“cut middleman”), the thesis finds a potential use case to show how stakeholders of the transaction on the shared ledger for distributed transactional and ownership ledgers

could interact more efficiently. Previous, the Artefact 1 (As-IS Concept), Artefact 2 (New Concept) have been designed based on the Action Design Research methodology during which the Artefacts undergo various intervention cycles. The evaluation approaches may include observational methods (case studies, field studies); analytical methods (static analysis, dynamic analysis); experimental methods (controlled experiments, simulations); testing (functional, structural); or descriptive methods (informed arguments, scenarios) (Hevner et al, 2004). To address the identified challenges, a triangulation approach combining qualitative and quantitative data collection methods is used. Depending on the course of the Interview, the order of the questions may have varied and questions arising from the context of the Interview may have been added (Saunders et al., 2012). In this specific case, the “To-Be” model – pre-analysis (Artefact 2a) was developed from around responses of 20 industry experts based on the qualitative content analysis in NVIVO.

Artefact Creation

The thesis outlines hypothesis factors as a baseline for the new target model which are derived from the literature review (diagnosis). The *Artefact 2a* of the *Design* phase is the pre-design of the conceptual model, identified from the literature and theory, requires an empirical validation. In this sense, the qualitative content analysis is conducted where structured interviews are applied to the business owners within the Real estate, Business, Technology and Legal industry.

Figure 4-9: Artefact 2 - “To-Be” model (new design) – Artefact Pre-Design (2a)

During the qualitative content analysis, the experts interviewed have been asked about recent trends, strengths, weaknesses, risks, and opportunities (SWAT-analysis). Those expert interviews were aimed at collecting business insights from experts to derive design principles towards the prototype development of smart contracts in the real estate industry. Final qualitative content analysis helped to identify the gaps and insert additional parameters for the conceptual model to develop the proof of concept/prototype to modernise the commercial real estate contract. It is based on those criteria and in line with the theoretical ADSR discussion in the conceptual model represents the artefact of the ADSR design phase. It takes the insights gained during the diagnosis phase, i.e. the literature review, and builds the foundation for the implementation stage, i.e. the development of a prototype solution. Therefore, it uses both, existing models identified in the context of the literature review and qualitative data gathered from a pre-study with 20 structured interviews. Industry experts provide information on which aspects beyond those identified during the diagnosis would need to be considered in the context of this thesis.

According to previous literature-findings “as-is” model (Artefact 1) and pre-design (Artefact 2a), a higher technology readiness level allows to create new value potentials, automate the process, improve the inefficiencies, error handling resulting into lower transaction cost. In this sense, the guiding principles for the design model are crafted based on the new technology opportunities (Blockchain technology). As discussed, the ADSR research is characterised by multiple intervention cycles that shift among stages of diagnosing, design, implementation, and evolution (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019). In this sense, the ADSR pre-design is built and needs to be evaluated within the ADR cycle (Problem, Artefact, Evaluation, Learning). For the research uses structured template for the elaborated ADSR process stages. In this sense, the ADSR uses the content analysis to develop a new pre-design conceptual model based on findings from the diagnosis-related literature (Artefact 2a: pre-design of a full conceptual model). The objective of the Pre-Design (Artefact 2a) to build a new conceptual model addressing its current weaknesses (i.e. information asymmetries, process inefficiencies). These have been identified through the literature review both comprehensive (thematic) as well as systematic literature review synthesis as well as by considering professional experience.

The creation (Artefact creation) the interviews is analysed by the qualitative content analysis is based on the guiding principles from the ADSR and supported by the expert interview synthesised which were prepared based on the literature review derived during diagnosis stage. To design the conceptual model, identified from the literature and theory, the Thesis

has conducted 20 structured interviews with industry experts (see Table 4-2) from the real estate, blockchain and financial services industry. The interviews were aimed at getting deeper insights and ultimately deriving macro factors that the Thesis would need to integrate into its solution to solve the initial problems. In this context, this study uses the coding scheme containing participant ID, position level, company size and region as provided below. The questions are aimed on recent Real estate trends, policy, finance, legal and personal practice decisions. Each interview was conducted in 45 minutes and the interview notes are recorded in a written transcript. All the expert interviews are presented with guidance for publishing the questionnaire and explicitly informed about this study purpose as well as authors and reviewers. The interviewees come from a variety of different backgrounds and location for the study. Most of the respondents occupy leadership positions in their industries and as such were able to provide a longer-term vision on the Blockchain technology within the Real estate industry. The experts are identified as most expert leaders from their industry through RICS (global Real estate community), social platforms such as Linked In and the researcher’s connections. The table below describes the expert interview participants and provides Participant ID, Position Level, Company Size and Region. All the names and personal data have been encoded via the NVIVO Tool for anonymity reasons to fulfil the ethical standards. Depending on the course of the Interview, the order of the questions may have varied and questions arising from the context of the Interview may have been added (Saunders et al., 2012).

Table 4-2: Interviewee Profile

	Participant ID	Position Level	Company Size	Region
1	IP1	Manager	Large Enterprise	EMEA
2	IP2	Top Manager	SMB	North-America
3	IP3	Top Manager	Large Enterprise	North-America
4	IP4	Top Manager	Enterprise	North-America
5	IP5	Top Manager	SMB	North-America
6	IP6	Manager	Enterprise	South-America
7	IP7	Top Manager	SMB	North-America
8	IP8	Top Manager	Large Enterprise	North-America
9	IP9	Top Manager	SMB	EMEA
10	IP10	Manager	Large Enterprise	EMEA
11	IP11	Top Manager	Enterprise	EMEA
12	IP12	Top Manager	Enterprise	North-America
13	IP13	Top Manager	Enterprise	EMEA
14	IP14	Manager	SMB	South-America
15	IP15	Top Manager	Enterprise	North-America
16	IP16	Manager	Large Enterprise	EMEA
17	IP17	Manager	SMB	North-America
18	IP18	Top Manager	SMB	South-America
19	IP19	Top Manager	SMB	EMEA
20	IP20	Top Manager	Enterprise	EMEA

The interview questions used in this study are listed in Table 4-3 below.

Table 4.3. Semi-structured interview questions

#	Questions
1	How is your interaction with block-chain and what projects have you worked on with regards too blockchain/smart contracts?
2	Is Smart Contracts a feasible substitute to the legacy system which includes paperwork, bank transfer and series of interest rates and commissions?
3	If Smart contracts is a feasible option and negates heavy fee structure, why do we still rely on the legacy system? What are the roadblocks?
4	Will Smart Contracts be customizable for real estate contracts?
5	Conflict resolution responsibilities generally fall on the broker or the legal court (after transaction). Will Lawyers be equipped to handle disputes once it's implemented through smart contracts? Or will a part of legality still not be under the control of smart contracts?
6	Scalability has always been an issue with block-chain. Do you think Smart Contracts will face scalability issues if Real estate incorporates this.
7	What would be the challenges of having an end-to-end seamless blockchain based escrow with respect to real estate finance?
8	What will be the legal issues while implementing smart contracts? As real estate is heavily regulated and smart contracts will have less regulation.
9	Smart Contracts will replace the agent in the agent-centric transactions as the agent will no more be the middle of this ecosystem. How will this affect brokerage. (Pros/Cons)
10	Though transparency increases with Smart Contracts about the lender's payment history etc., will It be trustworthy as it heavily relies on Programmed code and a bug could potentially be disastrous?

The qualitative content analysis is applied to determine the presence of certain words, themes, or concepts within some given qualitative data clustered into factors. By using content analysis, this study can quantify and analyse the presence, meanings, and relationships of the factors from the literature review (secondary data) and collected from the qualitative expert interviews (primary data). According to Saunders (2012), it is useful to develop a codebook with the categories and sub-categories. Once the data is collected, it is recommended to devise a hierarchical coding scheme based on what the respondents provide as individual answers and extract from coding scheme used to classify responses (see Table 4-4). Table 4-4 describes the mapping of the literature review authors, year of publication, research gap, diagnosis factors based on literature review and support evidence mapping with the qualitative content analysis factors, made in NVIVO Tool (nodes) and interview Participant ID.

Table 4-4. Mapping of diagnosis factors, expert interviews factors and participant responses coding

Citation source	Year	Research gap	Diagnosis factors (Literature review)	Categories	Participant responses (NVIVO Coding)
Li, M., Shen, L., Huang, G.Q.	2019	Technology	Blockchain Technology, Real estate logistics service	Adoption	IP6
Mehendale, D.K., Masurekar, R.S., Patil, H.V.	2019	Technology	Implications of block chain in real estate industry		IP19
Swan, M.	2018	Technology	Blockchain Information Systems-Design		IP14
Tilbury, J.L., De La Rey, E., Van Der Schyff, K.	2019	Technology	study examines two approaches to executing real estate transactions		IP2
Wouda, H.P., Opdenakker, R.	2019	Technology	Information Systems-Design		IP15
Dakhli, Z., Lafhaj, Z., Mossman, A.	2019	Technology	Building and Construction		IP7
					IP5
				IP8	
				IP17	
				IP10	
				IP1	
				IP11	

Krupa, K.S., Akhil, M.S.	2019	Technology	Revolution of Real estate Smart Contract		IP4 IP12 IP16 IP13 IP18 IP9 IP3
Epiphaniou, G., Daly, H., Al-Khateeb, H.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Bartolomeu, P.C., Ferreira, J.	2018	Real estate Process	Application of Wireless Real estate		
Ciatto, G., Bosello, M., Mariani, S., Omicini, A.	2019	Real estate Process	Application of Blockchain		
Firica, O.	2017	Real estate Process	Real estate transformation		
Janowicz, K., Regalia, B., Hitzler, P., Mai, G., Delbecque, S., Fröhlich, M., Martinent, P., Lazarus, T.	2018	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Krupa, K.S., Akhil, M.S.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology and Smart Contracts for the Real estate		
Peisl, T., Shah, B.	2019	Real estate Process	Impact of the blockchain on the employees		
Xu, Z., Van, C.B., Jiao, T., Wen, S., Wang, Q., Xiang, Y.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Yeasmin, S., Baig, A.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Morkunas	2019	Technology	Modern real estate on Blockchain technology		
Osterwalder	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate Blockchain - matrix elements		
Veuger, J.	2018	Transaction Costs	Real estate - qualitative study - interviews viable real estate economy		
Karamitsos, I., Papadaki, M. and Barghuthi, N.	2019	Technology	Blockchain Technology implementation for the Real estate Tenant model		
Kaczorowska, M.	2019	Legal Aspects	Land Registry possibilities and challenges	Governance and Compliance	IP6 IP2 IP15 IP7 IP8 IP17 IP10 IP1 IP11 IP4 IP12 IP16 IP13 IP18
Konashevych, O.	2019	Legal Aspects	Land Registry - titles conversion into tokens		
Spielman, A.	2016	Legal Aspects	Legal aspect-recording property titles- by comparing the benefits and limitations of a blockchain with those of the current record keeping system		
Morena, M., Truppi, T., Pavesi, A.S., Cia, G., Giannelli, J., Tavoni, M.	2020	Legal Aspects	Legal aspects specific country - Dopo Di noi project		
Garcia-Teruel, R.M.	2020	Legal Aspects	Legal aspects in line with EU legislation		
Mashatan, A., Roberts, Z.	2017	Technology	Use cases for the decentralized applications (DApps)	Security	IP6 IP19 IP14 IP15 IP7 IP5 IP8 IP17 IP10 IP1 IP11 IP4 IP12 IP16 IP13 IP18 IP9 IP3 IP2
Xu, Z., Jiao, T., Yang, L., Liu, D., Wen, S., Xiang, Y.	2020	Technology	Use cases for the decentralized applications (DApps)		
Ganter, M., Lützkendorf, T.	2019	Technology	Real estate "D.N.A." and "building passport"		
Vidhyalakshmi, V.S., Geetha, A., Sobitha Ahila, S.	2019	Technology	Information Systems- Implementation		
Avantaggiato, M., Gallo, P.	2019	Real estate Models	Real estate trust for the contracts		
Awalu, I.L., Kook, P.H., Lim, J.S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate election process		
Ganter, M., Lützkendorf, T.	2019	Real estate Process	Sustainability of the Real estate		
Soni, S., Bhushan, B.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Terzi, S., Zacharaki, A., Nizamis, A., Votis, K., Ioannidis, D., Tzovaras, D., Stamelos, I.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		
Kostin G.A., Pokrovskaia N.N., Ababkova M.U.	2017	Real estate Process	Distributed Ledger technology	Skills	IP5 IP8 IP17 IP10 IP4 IP16 IP13
Pokrovskaia, N., Khansuvarova, T., Khansuvarov, R.	2018	Transaction Costs	Decent		
Vokerla, R.R., Shanmugam, B., Azam, S., Karim, A.	2019	Technology	Distributed Ledger technology		

Boer, F.D., Jonkman, M., Faisal, F.					IP18 IP3 IP20
Somi S. Thota	2019	Technology	Process- modern scientific Real estate process	Costs	IP6 IP19 IP14 IP2 IP15 IP7 IP17 IP1 IP11 IP4 IP12 IP16 IP13 IP9 IP3
Hoxha, V., Sadiku, S.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate - Process		
Abdelhamid, M., Hassan, G.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate state of the art		
E, S.K., Talasila, V., Pasumarthy, R.	2019	Transaction Costs	Search for a favorable location		
Montgomery, N., Squires, G., Syed, I.	2018	Real estate Process	Finance and Investment-Systematical Literature Review (SLR)		
Nasarre-Aznar, S.	2018	Real estate Process	Finance and Investment-Collaborative housing and blockchain		
Dramé-Maigné, S., Laurent, M., Castillo, L., Ganem, H.	2018	Transaction Costs	Real estate Third Party Costs		
Hoksbergen, M., Chan, J., Peko, G., Sundaram	2019	Transaction Costs	Asymmetric information		
Kalyuzhnova, N.	2018	Transaction Costs	Globalization and cost cutting		
Latifi, S., Zhang, Y., Cheng, L.-C.	2019	Transaction Costs	Globalization and cost cutting		
Dijkstra, M.	2017	Real estate Process	Real estate - Business Models		
Grover, P., Kar, A.K., Janssen, M.	2019	Real estate Process	Real estate - qualitative study diffusion of blockchain technology		

4.4.2. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Design, Artefact 2 concept (2b New Design)

Problem formulation

The problem of the new design identified that the industry has a problem when it comes to establishing secured and compliant commercial real estate transactions in a economically and timely interesting way. There is a large optimization opportunity both on the process side and cost side. In the following sub-chapters, we will see how we will tackle the implementation and design of such a system that could, ultimately, increase the overall industry efficiency.

Based on the qualitative content analysis, the expert interviews seemed fair to suggest that further improvement toward the application of Smart contracts in the Real estate industry to modernise the commercial real estate Contract provided additional pillars for the conceptual model. The thesis thus aspires for a transition from the status quo to a new approach for the acquisition process in commercial real estate that is summarised in the development of the conceptual model (see Figure 4-10).

Figure 4-10: Design of the Conceptual Model (verified factors) – old design vs. new design

Artefact Creation:

In this context, the diagnosis phase (unvalidated pre-design) and qualitative content analysis sets the foundation of the new conceptual model, which is then externally validated through the qualitative content analysis of expert interviews (Artefact 2b: validated conceptual design, (see Figure 4-11).

Figure 4-11: Design of the Conceptual Model (verified factors) – old design vs. new design

Evaluation and Reflection

The *Artefact 2b* is the *design* phase is the design of the conceptual model, identified from the literature and qualitative content analysis which was conducted where structured interviews are applied to the business owners within the real estate, business, technology and legal industry. Most of the key design principles are verified by the experts, however some new, additional aspects are discovered during the carrying out of qualitative Content Analysis as outlined above has identified clearly defined interview / distilled categories on the additional points brought by the industry leaders: (1) adoption, (2) costs, (3) governance, (4) compliance, (5) security and (6) transparency and immutability.

Adoption: The factor adoption factors were mentioned as one of the most crucial parameters during the expert interviews since it will ultimately define our ability to distribute efficiently an asset to multiple parties. Furthermore, adoption is an important parameter that really affect how such Blockchain based systems will be implemented within the Blockchain technology revolution. Second, the cumbersome Real estate contract imposed a problem of the asymmetric information –research gap of asymmetric information and process (Krupa and Akhil, 2019) (2) Research gap of mistakes (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018). and the proposed application is designed to resolve the problem of decentralized property record keeping by codification potentials of Blockchain Technology. The redesign of the old Real estate process demonstrates that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract.

Governance and Compliance: Research gap of asset illiquidity and high barrier where people/organizations are interested in storing the investment funds somewhere safe where the value will be kept more stabilized (Baum, 2017) and consider the new uprising Blockchain Technology which brings new potentials and especially the way forward for the Real estate industry real estate tokenization on blockchain and constraints (Konashevych, 2020c) and benefits of the blockchain use for real estate and property rights (Konashevych, 2020a). With the help of smart contracts, a “computerized transaction protocol that executes the terms of a contract”, the Smart Contract can enforce the conditions of a contract digitally with no middleman required (Vidhyalakshmi/Geetha, 2019, p. 616). Within the thesis interviews respondents mentioned the Blockchain Technology functionality to cover the Governance dimension to manage a complex governance process with gatekeepers, votes, and escrow. Compliance is another large factor discussed in the interviews. Respondents feel that a project needs to gain speed in the market, it will need to have the support of an appropriate legal framework.

The focus is on addressing those parameters in a way that will still be compliant towards recent blockchain standards. With Blockchain industry standards such as ERC 777 and ERC 20 which are until today the most adopted protocols to interact with fungible products let it be shares, currencies or any other fungible products. However, Ethereum's standards are not built with specific use cases in mind such as specific regulations or industries and as such only provide basic data and system structures that we can leverage, but not entirely rely on, in our Blockchain prototype. We have therefore decided to avoid bug fixes for existing tokens and meet the needs of the newest industry ERC Standards (in our PhD solution - ERC 20, ERC 777) and used for our pilot prototype ERC777 ([ERC-777 Token Standard | ethereum.org](https://erc777.tokenstandard.io/)).

Transaction costs In the review of literature, Tilbury, De La Rey, (2019) specifically find that blockchain has the potential to bring about more efficiency and reduce reliance on third parties and manual processes. The literature in chapter X (e.g. ...) linked with research gap of high-cost of property transaction, (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019) which is clear also on the prolonging of the property transaction completion times, increasing the possibility for errors and fraudulent activities. Blockchain technology presents an opportunity for the Real estate sector as it provides the basis for redesign of the traditional approach. The decentralised Smart Real estate contract gives the potential to reduce the transaction costs by transparently automating the so called 'middleman', including land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller. Third, The Blockchain Technology through the Smart Contract self-executes the transaction with the terms of the agreement between buyer and seller who are directly P2P connected to all the P2P nodes on the decentralized blockchain network without any intermediaries. This decentralised mechanism connects the buyer and seller directly without any intermediary by eliminating the problem of intermediary "Third-Party middleman" which would eliminate the redundancies and require less transaction costs. The existing system consists of employing a broker or a middleman to perform transaction of assets. The proposed conceptual model is designed in the way where the buyer and seller being are directly written into lines of algorithmic code which is distributed to all the P2P nodes on the decentralized blockchain network and logically from this argument by design itself abolish the intermediate layer between the buyer and seller.

Transparency and Immutability: The proposed application provides a higher skill for the auditability, immutability and transparency where specific assets mistakes will be encoded on the Smart Contract and decrease the chance of mistake from paper-based recording practice by increasing the quality of the data. Smart contracts address asymmetric information through

automation, transparency and security that underpin the symmetry in the consensus between parties in the process. The traditional real estate purchasing process has been described as inefficient due to extensive manual review and verification of financial and legal documents as well as manually updating multiple systems with redundant information or heavy reliance on multiple third parties which results in high.

Skills: The main roadblock is the human factor, people not willing to change and embrace the technology. There is a lot of fear with a lot of people who do not understand technology and as for any new technology, the availability of a skilled workforce is scarce and expensive. As a result, the transaction costs for the Real estate contract might reduce since there is a diminished need for human-operated tasks. Fourth, the application of the Blockchain technology brings new possibilities of mutual delusion and concealment during the sale, rental, and lease processes can be eliminated, thus achieving digitization of real estate ownership (Krupa/Maganalli, 2019) and achieve efficiency gains for the Real estate and keeping security (Hoxha/ Sadiku, 2019).

Security: Is paramount in financial transactions. Ethereum is considered a secured system because of the high amount of cryptography and the cost associated with trying to perform various attacks that could change the state of a transaction and show that decentralization through algorithm-based consensus providing a reliable ecosystem in which Real estate transactions can be safely preserved on the Blockchain protocol for all the Real estate lifecycle. The redesign of the Real estate contract is subject to economics, financial, technological favourable conditions, however the legal aspects such as Governance and Compliance need to be assured by the algorithm-based security of the Smart Contract ERC 777. The Real estate asset tokenisation is backed on the consensus mechanism by the fractional ownership to the token holder and achieve investment liquidity in a Real estate market and remove significant market barriers to enter the Real estate market even for the small income investors. The security of asset illiquidity and high market barriers hindered people/organisations for Real estate investments. Tokens on the blockchain as a technological concept is the closest solution to the legal concept of titles because it provides for evidence of ownership and can be transferred from one address to another, while giving exclusive access to such an address to the owner (Konashevych, 2019). As a result, the decentralised Blockchain technology can foster investment and entrepreneurship, while reducing investor risk appetite by storing the investment funds more secured in asset-backed regulated “Security Tokens”.

Learning: During the qualitative content analysis, the experts interviewed have been asked about recent trends, strengths, weaknesses, risks, and opportunities (SWAT-analysis). Those expert interviews were aimed at collecting business insights from experts to derive design principles towards the Prototype development of Smart contracts in the real estate industry. Final qualitative content analysis helped to identify the gaps and insert additional parameters for the conceptual model to develop the proof of concept/prototype to modernise the commercial real estate contract. After the exhaustive literature review the industry is still dominated by ineffective and often outdated processes established decades ago. The respondents also stated that the leadership style is very old fashion, and that innovation is not at the centre of the efforts. Although, on a positive note, the respondent also gave a look inside the most recent efforts such as using video-conferencing tools. Such efforts show that the industry is willing to move forward, although the rate of adoption is low with new technologies and the state of the commercial real estate transactions. The apparent inefficiency, gradualness and costly structures that must be put in place to perform an actual transaction are a concern for the industry. Consequently, the Thesis identified that the industry has a problem when it comes to establishing secured and compliant commercial real estate transactions in a economically and timely interesting way. There is a large optimization opportunity both on the process side and cost side. In the following sub-chapters, we will see how we will tackle the implementation and design of such a system that could, ultimately, increase the overall industry efficiency.

4.5. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Implementation Artefact 3

Since the research follows the structured research approach ADSR (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019), the next iterative cycle is to find a solution for the prototype. The aim of the implementation phase is to develop an ensemble instantiated artefact. In this sense, the implementation is to transform the conceptual model into the technical prototype, select an appropriate architecture (Artefact 3a) and build prototype development (Artefact 3b) system to address research problem of the commercial real estate transaction weaknesses. As this study follows the structured ADSR research approach aligned proposed by (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019), the next iterative cycle continues with the design phase (see Figure 4-12).

Figure 4-12: Combination of ADR principles with the project stages

The implementation phase undergoes an iterative cycle of problem formulation (1), artefact development (2), reflection and evaluation (3) and formalization of learnings (4) as illustrated in Figure 4-13.

Figure 4-13: Artefact 2- “To-Be” model (old design) - Stages of the Design Phase

4.5.1. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Implementation (3a Proof of Concept for Prototype)

Problem formulation

The prototype solution is developed on the Blockchain technology where further information need to be explained. The Blockchain protocol, on a highest level, come in two forms: public and private or to follow the industry vocabulary permissioned and permissionless. Public blockchains are blockchains with a decentralized architecture, participants are free to join and mine transactions and nobody fully controls the blockchain once it is deployed. Private blockchains, on the other hand, provide an environment in which only invited parties can join and participate in mining or as actors of the ecosystem. We can see examples of private

blockchains with the Hyperledger project, that effectively distributes ledgers and records across various actors of a private blockchain. This can be useful in use-cases around financial institutions or inside large enterprises to share data in a trust less manner. On the other hand, famous public blockchain can be seen in bitcoin and Ethereum blockchains. Those are 100% decentralized and actors from all types of companies/individuals can join and establish new nodes, publish smart contracts and use their related cryptocurrencies. Private and public blockchains also present different characteristics in terms of costs, speed, and security. Overall, public blockchains present slower transactions speed, higher costs of transactions and weaker securities since the smart contracts can be abused by hackers easily as they are publicly available. On the other hand, private blockchains are usually quicker to process transactions, are less costly (basically zero fees as the consensus happens within a small group of actors) and provide higher security as they are permissioned and usually actors will not be hackers in a system that serve them.

According to Verma, Dhanda, and Nagar (2022), recommends a structured and simple pre-configured development library of the decentralised the ecosystem of a P2P network to automatise the rapid development for contracts and testing scenarios framework. The Truffle framework is standardised Ethereum script runner that executes scripts within a pre-configured environment with support for tight integration. The Truffle framework has three constituents that are completing the truffle suite are truffle, drizzle. Wei-Meng Lee, the founder of Developer Learning Solutions, Lee, W. M. (2019) crafted the methodology in his book “In Beginning Ethereum smart contracts programming” (pp. 147–167)” how efficiently to test ganache for the Ethereum Smart Contracts. Furthermore, the largest Ethereum community, Github-Community, recommends using Built-in smart contract compilation, linking, deployment and binary management by a wide-accepted “Truffle Framework” which allows to run blockchains on a local computer for our research purpose and test standardised Solidity script on the local machine by using the local desktop Truffle Suite studio instead of global Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM).

The research project selected to develop under the ERC protocol and showcase the prototype development. In the Ethereum community, ERC stands for Ethereum Requests for Comments, and are crowd-developed standards that, when applied, guarantee compatibility and interactivity between certain types of smart contracts. For example, ERC20 was one of the first standards adopted by the community and provided a simple, easy to use interface for developing fungible tokens that could then be traded on exchanges. Those trades where made possible by the implementation of standardized functions and variables that allowed for easy integration on token exchanges. Those tokens could then have a value in ETH and be

converted back to FIAT currencies. As said previously, ERC20 is one of the first ERCs to have been accepted. ERC777 is an extension that is backwards compatible with ERC20, offering all the fungibility and integration with existing solutions around ERC20, but it additionally provides functionalities to protect users of smart contract of failures and mistakes resulting in enormous value being lost. For example, the ERC777 standard proposes to use the ERC820 standard that acts as a central registry of smart contract to make sure, before proceeding with a transaction, that the contract our ERC777 will interact with is compatible resulting in a successful transaction and no loss in capital. On top of this contract, some logic to validate transactions based on our compliance needs has been added. As discussed with the experts, legislative framework is critical for the development of the prototype. Laws heavily regulate the financial industry and who can invest in certain types of products, it is needed to check if the people participating in the transactions are authorized on KYC/AML smart contracts meaning that there is control over who invests and trades the tokens.

Artefact development

The *Artefact* of the *Prototype implementation* phase is the transformation to techno prototype model (Artefact 3a), architecture options (Artefact 3b) and build the prototype solution (Artefact 3c). After Blockchain technology and its two options (private and public) have been explained, the research selects private blockchain would be the obvious choice for this project. However, two important factors should be considered: transfer of value and adoption. In the case of private blockchains, there is no preestablished currency of choice and a trading value associated to it. Consequently, the problem of performing Real estate transactions for actors worldwide that then could have the opportunity to liquidate those investments is present. Secondly, adoption in private blockchains is inexistent while in public blockchains it is already there. Major efforts would have to be deployed to amass on a private blockchain enough actors to make the system worth the try in an industry with low innovation rate. For this project, only public blockchains would make sense for the two previous factors. The choice went towards the Ethereum public chain as it provides adoption and a currency (Ethereum) with trading pairs in almost all FIAT currencies worldwide as well as providing an easy-to-use smart contract platform with a wealth of libraries and tools. In this context, the prototype mock-up consists of three tier architecture actors and roles, business services and databases as suggested by blockchain technology pioneers in the real estate sector (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018) and outlined in Figure 4-14.

Figure 4-14: Artefact 3a- Prototype mock-up design (Implementation phase)

To favour mass adoption, as stated earlier, the blockchain application cannot be offered solely on the blockchain as a backend application. Developing a front-end application that allows people and companies to work seamlessly with the prototype to perform the blockchain transactions will be needed. For this reason, it was decided to program a JavaScript application that will serve as a front-end. Conceptually, it is important to understand that blockchain applications do not present potential users a front-end, this means there is no URL that one can hit and get a user interface with buttons, fields, and graphs to see how much of this building they own and how many transitions were performed. However, as the tools to connect to different blockchains are increasingly being developed by the community, there is now ways to build User Interfaces and deploy them on the web that allow connection to blockchains by users and let them perform transactions. As such, it was decided to build the front-end part in Angular (an industry standard JavaScript framework) and use a third-party chrome plugin named Metamask allowing for blockchain connectivity on the Ethereum blockchain. The web application will be deployed on Google Cloud and the other databases (when needed) will also be in Google Cloud.

Evaluation and Reflection

The research evaluates the architecture options and reflects on the basic architecture of the prototype, it is important to first define the functionalities, external factors and legal pressures that the project need to factor to be a feasible implementation. From the interviews and literature reviews, a precise idea of some of the common principles the prototype will need to respect has been derived. For example, to foster adoption, the prototype will need to be based on a Blockchain that already has a great adoption within society and the media as adoption of Blockchain technologies is already low and pushing a new blockchain without the basic ecosystem (miners, nodes, etc.) will probably mean failure from start.

Apart from the adoption aspect that the solution should be built upon, the interviews also showed us that legal compliance is of paramount importance. Each jurisdiction probably has some laws and regulations that would need to be integrated to be able to make blockchain real estate transactions a reality. Consequently, public audits will also be required, and permissioned availability of data will be key. The blockchain application is the backbone of the prototype, essentially it consists of two parts: the asset specific part and the compliance one. Those two parts fulfil different goals but work together to provide a seamless transaction service to resell large real estate commercial projects. For those reasons, it was decided to base the prototype on the public Ethereum blockchain. The public Ethereum blockchain presents several advantages. It works using ETH, a cryptocurrency adopted worldwide and that is known by people and businesses. Many other alternative cryptocurrencies and token are based on this blockchain and that would render adoption easier by major players within the industry. Ethereum is also a Blockchain that presents a wealth of tools and libraries that make working with it and its protocols especially easy compared to more complex blockchains. For example, the web3.js Javascript library allows to easily connect to the Ethereum blockchain and run transactions on it with a very low cost of integration.

Learning

The first part, the asset one, is designed to represent a specific commercial real estate parcel, track fractional ownership, and allow transactions on it in the form of balances on ledgers being updated on this specific real estate asset. The common currency in transactions is ETH, which can be purchased by users easily using major public exchanges and serves to transfer value from users/purchasers to the seller/real estate owners. Each asset part is composed of a set of three smart contracts, each fulfilling specific functionalities. The smart contracts are: Asset Storage, Asset Logic and Asset Sale. It is not uncommon that one or more of those smart contracts would implement a variety of different protocols and as such would be fractioned into

further smaller smart contracts chained together. The Asset Storage contract is a smart contract built to hold the variables of the Real estate asset. One can think of it as a database to which we can read or write data. This specific smart contract does not hold any logic. By logic it is meant pieces of code that will transform or perform calculations based on user input and then write this data to the database. This separation between logic and storage is important when one works with blockchain because it is needed to understand that a smart contract deployed is deployed for “eternity “. One can never upgrade a smart contract or alter its code. Consequently, if a bug has been introduced in a smart contract, a developer will literally never be able to update it without deploying a new contract and therefore losing any variable state present on the old one. This is important to the thesis as, in Real estate, variable state should be held in our smart contracts for long time to be able to distribute yields and other crucial actions. Therefore, it is needed to have separated our database like smart contract, that will hold as said before the balances and accounts authorized to perform operations on this specific asset, and the logic smart contract that holds the business processes and deep logic that will shift and change over time. As every smart contract has a specific address on the Ethereum blockchain, it is easy to authorize and remove a specific logic smart contract from writing on the database smart contract and authorize a new one when an update is needed. One can then guarantee a consistent and durable database of real estate owners and transactions while updating the different logics and add extra layers of security. The Asset Logic contract is, as stated before, a smart contract that will hold the business logic of the asset side part. This smart contract holds the logic, for example, managing transactions between users, transfer of values from users to sellers or manage what kind of AML checks should be in place. As stated before, this smart contract can be updated. It means that old iterations can be unlinked from the Asset Storage contract and be replaced by more recent iteration of the asset logic that will manage bug fixing, vulnerability tackling and more. The Asset Sale contract will hold the logic and variable on the sale side of this specific asset such as price per token (share), sales end, sales start, and other values such as sales opened or closed. Those three contracts together form the asset side of the blockchain implementations and must be deployed for each different assets that will be sold on the platform. This could cause issues with scale as costs of deployments could start to minimize the benefit from a blockchain based process if the mining cost starts to grow too high meaning higher cost of transaction mining compared to benefits of blockchain based transactions would render the operation profitable.

The second part of the blockchain process is the compliance part. The compliance is essentially the blockchain structure that will guarantee that specific users (through their ETH account) are cleared to invest in certain assets. Those rules can be custom built in the

JavaScript application in order, for example, to prevent people with an IP located in Iraq to invest in European assets (assuming there is a specific legislation preventing such transactions). The compliance part will do the following: first it will register accounts that passed the KYC/AML process on the JavaScript app as authorized to invest on the platform with a blockchain transaction originated from the account owning all the blockchain infrastructure, second it will provide, on call, the authorization for specific accounts to invest on specific assets in the form of a Boolean (true, false). If true, the account will be authorized to perform transactions and receive shares of the real estate. If false, the transaction will be closed and the user/system trying to perform it will be notified. The Compliance part is, as well as the Asset Part, based on the Storage/Logic system guaranteeing updatability of the logic without losing data and important records.

4.5.2. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Implementation (3b solution architecture)

Problem formulation

The solution architecture for this research focused on the single asset buildings shopping name “Les Accacias” for simplicity reasons to demonstrate the artefact proof of concept / prototype utility. Since the scenario for the PhD was clearly chosen to take one building for the tokenisation, the “Les Accacias” shopping mall is deployed on the Ethereum Smart Contract and named as Token “ACCAS” (token name).

To support the local prototype testing with a global blockchain network, a fully functioning version of the smart contracts will be deployed on the Ethereum Rinkeby test chain. The Rinkeby testnet is mainly used for blockchain testing before deployment on the Ethereum mainnet which means that each transaction can be tested in real-time and anywhere available for transparency. The Etherscan allows us to explore and search the Rinkeby blockchain for transactions, addresses, tokens, prices and other activities. The PhD Prototype solution is using a world leading Ethereum protocol which leverages the technology already known Smart Contract Ethereum which is supported by local desktop Truffle Suite and ganache for testing.

Since it is a widespread Github community, the white labelled solution is open-sourced protocol and expands the local building “Le Accacias” to the international investors within the testing peers and nodes. The Prototype solution is fully ERC-20 compliant and its code is open-sourced and extensively peer reviewed on Github by making it accessible for transactions and testing all around the world. The protocol is stored at the Ethereum Rinkeby network database. For convenience and to avoid convergence with real world projects, fictional real estate will be

used. The scenarios are designed for the prototype testing and are subject to the relation between buildings and tokens (scenario with one asset building and multiple buildings as a portfolio).

While the tokenized real estate uses security token offerings (STOs), which are explicitly securities in accordance with the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), this research study goes for the non-fungible tokens (NFTs) which are real estate ownership but are not the same as STOs. The non-fungibility of NFTs means that every NFT (i.e., every property) has only one owner. In this study, the Token ACCA is used as Security Token Offering (fungible token). The property should be open for all investors. The result is the principle of fungibility- making the previous impossible investment in partial illiquid assets to a game-changer of fungible liquid stocks. The NFT (non-fungible token) is a unique digital title (tokens) to property, either real or virtual, that are stored on a blockchain ledger) help to allocate efficiently the funds of the property.

Each token represents a share in the property and will be fully fungible with another token and this improves the way of asymmetric information and resolved the problem of decentralized property record keeping by codification potentials of Blockchain Technology. The results demonstrate that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract. Furthermore, the possibility of linking a voting right to the ACCAS token will be considered, which investors can use to communicate their investment preferences to the rest of the network in a frictionless and transparent way. Using this functionality, by us of these 'voting tokens' the prototype solution allows to develop the Asset-backed Token Offering (ATO) and freeze the tokens for each real-estate lifecycle (example 5-10 years). This can be used to determine future reinvestment and other corporate actions relative to the token holders' investments and potential liquidation proceeds.

Second, this approach proposes a market-driven solution of transaction cost reduction based Smart Contract Ethereum for all the real estate contract stakeholders- seller, buyer, Real estate agent, notary lawyer, mortgage bank, municipality land registry. On the other hand, the approach proposes how to abolish high barrier entries for the Real estate market and leverage flexible allocation of funds for the illiquid asset class and generate global revenue gains for investors, token holders.

Third, the proposed application provides a higher auditability, immutability, and transparency where specific assets mistakes will be encoded on the Smart Contract and decrease the

chance of mistake from paper-based recording practice by increasing the quality of the data. Smart contracts address asymmetric information through automation, transparency and security that underpin the symmetry in the consensus between parties in the process.

Fourth, the transaction cost problem “search and transaction costs” may be significantly reduced by omitting the redundancy processes of the so called ‘middleman’ stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller. Fourth, asset tokenisation allows to “tokenise” to provide the fractional ownership to the token holder and achieve investment liquidity in a Real estate market and remove significant market barriers to enter the Real estate market even for the small income investors.

Fifth, the underlying asset value of the token may reduce negative consequences of price volatility on business by letting end-user flexibly transfer their assets from blockchain to blockchain to fit the asset price distortions and allow to make the price adjustments in real-time by using the smart contract Ethereum

In these terms, the architecture needs to focus on addressing those parameters in a way that will still be compliant with blockchain industry standards such as ERC 777 and ERC 20 which are until today the most adopted protocols to interact with fungible products let it be shares, currencies or any other fungible products. However, Ethereum’s standards are not built with specific use cases in mind such as specific regulations or industries and as such only provide basic data and system structures that we can leverage, but not entirely rely on, in our Blockchain prototype. We have therefore decided to shift and remodel those existing standards to include essential parts such as law compliance and necessary controls to make sure our system would hold water when tested.

Artefact creation

Our research model comprises three layers that are actors and roles (1), business process (2) and databases (3) (3-Tier Architecture) that are explained as laid out in Chapter 2, systematic literature synthesis has been identified in the “Transaction Process Workflow on the Blockchain Technology”, by the Opendakker and Wouda (2019) and extended by the model of Karamitsos (2019).

The application of blockchain technology for the real estate as stated by Karamitsos and Papadaki (2018) allows it to run decentralised real estate contracts by omitting the redundancy processes of the ‘middleman’ stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser

and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller, reduce the transaction costs and provide trust to the stakeholders (see Figure 4-15).

Figure 4-15: Artefact 3b- Prototype solution architecture (Implementation phase)

Source: Adapted prototype architecture from Karamitsos (2019) and Opendakker (2019)

The solution architecture of the research prototype is based on the practical example of commercial real estate contract which tries to address the issue of multi-layer connection between actors, roles, business processes. This section on the third research Artefact, the Prototype, discusses how to use the codification potential of blockchain technology into technical information system architecture

Evaluation and Reflection:

According to ADSR research, evaluation approaches may include observational methods (case studies, field studies); analytical methods (static analysis, dynamic analysis); experimental methods (controlled experiments, simulations); testing (functional, structural); or

descriptive methods (informed arguments, scenarios) (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019). During the ongoing reflection and evaluation, important issues were discovered, reflected, and acted upon during the pilot, such as decisions about the actors and roles, business processes and use case scenarios to understand the underneath database solutions.

The development of the prototype application layer was realised based on the real estate investment platform (Swiss Realty) on the 3-Tier Architecture as recommended by (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018) allowing investors to invest in commercial Real estate both in the form of cryptocurrencies and FIAT currencies (see Figure 4-16).

Figure 4-16: Three-Layers/Implementation model for the commercial real estate smart contract

(1) Actors and Roles

Property owners are the entities or physical people owning a particular Real estate being sold partially or entirely on the blockchain. A property owner only interacts with the property buyer and will receive the entirety of the funds raised through the model. Property buyer is an entity or a physical person that would like to purchase the property on sale by the Property owner. The property buyer is the person raising the funds through the blockchain system. This entity or person is the actor that “tokenizes” the property which means it must handle the smart contracts development as well as the marketing of its fund-raising actions. Investors are entities or physical persons that have been granted the right to invest through the blockchain system in the various pieces of Real estate proposed. Investors will not become owners of the physical assets, instead, they will own a share in a derivative linked to the physical assets and rewarding them returns based on the physical asset’s performance. The blockchain system in

this case could be any of the blockchain that let their users produce and operate their own smart contracts. Decentralized Blockchain system is run on Ethereum for our research thesis which allows property buyer to effectively raise resources through a zero-trust environment with low transaction fees and extremely quick execution time. The reader needs to understand that blockchain systems are in themselves complex systems composed of nodes, miners and other components that have only limited influence on the model, and thus, are kept aside from it for the time being.

(2) Business Processes: Refer to the diagram 3-Tier Architecture

The following business and KYC processes are included in the smart contract-based prototype design:

Business Processes

1. First, investors buy the token (“ACCAS”) with fiat or other cryptocurrencies. The synthetic derivative swap will separate ownership of the real estate from the token holders
2. Second, the investor sends money and receives the token as proportional rights to most of the Real estate ownership certificate
3. Third, the fund property Swiss Realty S.A receives money raised to fund Real estate portfolio
4. Fourth, Real estate is split up in tokens Le Accacia shopping mall which is split to ACCAS tokens. The terms of agreement that Swiss Realty S.A. will uphold will be embedded in the Investment Note
5. Fifth, the Investors are rewarded with ownership tokens of the Real estate Token ownership and will be registered real-time on the Ethereum Blockchain

KYC Processes

1. First, our PhD Thesis ensures that KYC- and AML-procedures and operations remain feasible and controllable where KYC/AML registration needs to be performed.
2. Second, it only takes on regulatory responsibilities for the limited number of initial investors. Once traded on the secondary market the regulatory burden in terms of financial and KYC/AML obligations, the token is traded the automatic KYC/AML decision matrix, which is customised in the way that either an approval or rejection is issued to the investor.
3. Third, for the verification reasons, the KYC/AML operators are essential elements of our Prototype solution on Ethereum Smart Contract since abilities investors that registered through our platform to interact with existing properties being sold on it. In

the case of the approval, the data entry can continue until the investor confirms the process.

4. The transaction is successfully executed, and the property gets a true sale.
5. The transaction in the secondary market is characterised by the derivative sale where the cross-legal entity sales of tokens pre-requisite of a legal entity set up at the individual jurisdictions.

(3) Database Processes: Refer to the diagram 3-Tier Architecture

Application and presentation server Smart Contract on Ethereum Blockchain that ensures the use of common tools for further development of blockchain-based applications (see Figure 4-17).

1. Presentation Server: Blockchain layer
2. Application Server: Live web application layer
3. Database Server: Google cloud environment

Figure 4-17: Architecture of the smart real estate contract

Source: Steiner AG/Swiss Realty Model based on Dafflon, (Github, 2020)

Learnings for the solution architecture:

First layer is about the data storage part (1), the Github community advises to store the valuable information. The first layer of data storage is covered with the efficient usage of database, where the use tokens to automate Database management, Ownership and Tradability of investors' participation. The storage part will tackle the task of storing its databases, variables and any other value that will be used in the future and that should not be strictly local. Second layer is the application logic layer (2), the logic contains all the flow part

of the contract (buying a token, validating an address, etc.). The logic part will handle all the process and business logic, meaning that it will hold functions, succession of actions and the ability to write on the storage part. The logic part will see a similar division between smart contracts related specifically to assets being sold and a smart contract handling the central variable storage. It is also important to mention that on top of each logic contract sits an asset sale smart contract, that allows for seamless purchase of given assets. Finally, the Artefact will also consist of one overarching smart contract holding variables shared by all asset sales. Such variables could be permissions given to Ethereum accounts to invest, operate or even modify specific variables on specific assets.

Third layer is the presentation layer (3) and connection with the users allowing the transactions, authorization, tracking and ban of Ethereum Accounts from the database KYC/AML smart-contract are deployed on the Test Ethereum network. Consequently, our crypto Real estate platform have various forms: two-sided marketplace or tokenization platforms. One allows users to sell assets and others to buy participation in those assets, the other allows users to create tokens linked to their specific asset. Basic roles and permissions will give the logic CRUD access on the different variables stored in the storage part. In a more detailed manner, the storage part will be divided into several smart contracts. For every Real estate asset sold through the Artefact, the solution provides one storage smart contract holding essential asset variables such as Name, Value, Location, and other important information. In this manner, the Thesis is using the prototype development based on the Swiss Realty platform / Steiner AG to build the Smart Contracts as described later in this chapter and a front-end Javascript web application. On behalf of Swiss Realty platform, it provides open Real estate Commercial ecosystem grouping together buyers, sellers and investors are created on behalf of the ERC Ethereum 777 protocol on Github.

4.5.3. Application of the ADSR Methodology –Implementation (3c prototype development)

Disclaimer: As noted in page VI of this thesis, the source code used in this study is the intellectual property of Swiss Realty, a private commercial real estate entity, the code is not disclosed in this thesis. The code base is available on the GitHub weblink and can be accessed upon permission of the founder.

Problem formulation: The prototype development for this research focused on the single asset buildings shopping name “Les Accacias” for simplicity reasons to demonstrate the Artefact Proof of Concept / Prototype utility. Since the scenario for the Ph.D. was clearly

chosen to take one building for the tokenisation, the “Les Accacias” shopping mall is deployed on the Ethereum Smart Contract and named as Token “ACCAS” (token name).

Artefact Creation: In this sense, the research artefact prototype development (Artefact 3c) how to use the codification potential of blockchain technology into technical information system architecture, particularly, the ability to translate the paper-based real estate contract into the algorithmic blockchain protocol to establish a decentralised infrastructure, to ensure consistency of the separate ledgers of buyer, seller, notary, land registry, housing authority and provide a key-value database as an end-to-end database. For instance, such database could be established on the common agreed database e.g. Google Cloud, Amazon Web or Microsoft Azure, application server e.g. Live Web as outlined in the Figure 4-18.

Figure 4-18: Artefact 3c- Prototype solution architecture (Implementation phase)

In DSR, an artefact is defined as “the new insight...artefact built and evaluated in every ADR cycle” (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019, p.3). In this instance, the underlying Ph.D. research applies the ADR stage and creates new conceptual model (1) and new prototype development (2) designed to address specific problems or improve processes within a given domain.

Organisation and structure of the prototype: Crowdsale contrac based ERC777

ERC-777, which stands for "Ethereum Request for Comments 777," was created by Jacques Dafflon, Jordi Baylina, and Thomas Shabibi in 2017. The standard adds several advanced features for fungible tokens' interaction to improve ERC-20, one of the most widely used tokenization standards (see illustrative example in Figure 4-19).

Figure 4-19: Standard ERC-777

Choice for the Ethereum Blockchain (Largest Chain): The Ethereum blockchain is most validated blockchain and the smart contract platform with the most users and applications. Its community is vibrant and allows for knowledge exchange on a scale other chain could not achieve (see Figures 4-20, 4-21, and 4-22).

Figure 4-20: Architecture - Layer structure (source: Dafflon, 2024)

Figure 4-21: Smart Contract ERC777 (Token structure) (source: Dafflon, 2024)

Security: By relying on existing established players (Google, MetaMask) we ensure maximum security for our users

Transparency: token will respect ERC777, meaning that it is registered on a central token index allowing people to check our protocol.

Modern User Interface: The web framework used are widely supported by the community and are updated regularly to support the latest security threats.

Figure 4-22: Customising ERC777- Asset sale for Swiss commercial contract (Gross, 2024)

Authorization: The asset sale contract is the only contract authorizing sales of our token. Upon receipt of funds, it will perform the necessary checks to determine if the account is authorized to purchase on Swiss Realty or not

Asset based sale: The asset sale contract is designed to be linked to a specific asset and defines the rate at which investors will purchase the tokens (rate is stored in the Storage contract)

Flexibility: The contract allows asset sale, adapt the rate of the token or increase/decrease the number of tokens at any moment in time

Validation: By calling `_prevalidatePurchase(_ben, _am)`, the Asset Sale contract triggers three checks:

- The beneficiary of the transaction should never be address '0x0'.
- The amount should be superior to zero.
- The beneficiary and sender must have passed the KYC/AML procedure.

Governance & Compliance: KYC/AML Central repository

Allowing the authorization, tracking and ban of Ethereum Accounts proposal KYC/AML smart-contract are deployed on the Test Ethereum network are being integrated in the test platform to further testing. KYC/AML storage contract will have different behaviors based on the role assigned to the account: user, viewer, operator, owner.

Figure 4-23: Swiss Realty - Customizing ERC777- KYC/AML repository (Gross, 2024)

The research demonstrates the inherent optimal properties of an artefact or provides optimality bounds on artefact behaviour. Every stakeholder is possible to access to the data storage and allow a new contract, effectively making the transaction immutable. Blockchain immutability is considered as one of the major advantages of blockchain technology. The transaction records and inserted data are irrevocable and immutable and creates trust. The optimisation process will be analysed precisely under the section implementation of the smart contract in the results.

1. Token contracts define the logic of transactions and user management.
2. Storage contracts use to store variables, maps and functions settings the variables.
3. Helper libraries to perform certain actions on the blockchain.
4. Token contract fetches and changes data on the data storage.
5. Interfaces allow the coder to check if the protocol is correctly implemented.

In the prototype, yield distribution and advanced KYC/AML will not be included for the sake of simplicity, but it instead will be focused at providing a clear, open and automated trading environment for investors, buyers and sellers of real estate. Benefits and feasibility in Real World of such solutions and designs will be enabled through the prototype.

The prototype development aims to setup a legally viable and regulatory approved blockchain-based real estate tokenization platform.

1. Issue tokens publicly to Swiss nationals.
2. Issue tokens privately to family, friends and founders that are EU citizens.
3. Establish entities that protect software and other IP, and manage asset cash flows
4. Protect services legally with low-cost crypto licenses.
5. Validate and apply lessons learned to the core legal structure of the first STO.
6. Involve regulators early on to guarantee approval.

4.6. Application of the ADSR Methodology – Artefact 4- Evolution of the prototype

The aim of the evolution phase entails prototype testing (4a) and prototype statistics (4b). In this sense, the prototype smart contract is developed on the Ethereum Blockchain (Github) and tested on various operational scenarios (sender-receiver relations) to determine the proof-of-use and demonstrate the prototype utility and process efficiencies (4a prototype testing) see Figure 4-24). Parallely, the prototype proof of value is determined by the analytical statistics which is carried out by empirical market survey (N=700) participants to investigate whether a

prototype solution can create value (4b prototype statistics - proof of value). As the thesis follows the structured ADSR research approach (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019), the next iterative cycle continues with the design phase.

Figure 4-24: Combination of Action Design Research (ADR) principles with the project stages

In this sense, the implementation phase undergoes an iterative cycle of problem formulation (1), Artefact development (2), reflection and evaluation (3) and formalization of learnings (4) as illustrated in Figure 4.25.

Figure 4-25: Artefact 2- “To-Be” model (old design) - Stages of the Design Phase

4.6.1. Application of the ADSR Methodology – Artefact 4a prototype testing

Problem Formulation: The evaluation of the prototype development is conducted by means of prototype testing with computer simulated tests and end-to-end user testings. The PhD experiment is a Smart Contract within a controlled environment on the local Ethereum machine (coding related tests) and relevant testing scenarios. According to ADSR research, the evaluation of the prototype should rely on the prototype testing to demonstrate its worth with evidence addressing criteria such as validity, utility, quality, and efficacy of the Prototype development (Gregor and Hevner, 2004). In this research, the evaluation of the prototype rely on development tests which have been performed using solidity and the truffle framework as

it provide an accurate Ethereum blockchain replica in order to test smart contract deployment, gas cost of doing so and provides an interface on which specific transactions can be accurately tested and measured.

Artefact Development: To test the prototype, efforts have been focused on two fronts: Testing logic accuracy and testing deployment processes and automation as it can be an essential part of a smooth blockchain run fund or real estate transaction. To do so, scripts that run specific assets deployments one contract after the other have been deployed. On the asset smart contracts for example the deployment of our three smart contracts layer with each layer being accurately parametered automatically with output from the previous one has been automated as outlined in Figure 4-26.

Figure 4-26: Artefact 4a - Prototype testing (Evolution phase)

The tests have been performed using solidity and the truffle framework as it provides an accurate Ethereum blockchain replica to test smart contract deployment and it provides an interface on which specific transactions can be accurately tested and measured (see Table 4-2).

Table 4-2: Prototype testing of the smart real estate contract

Test	Description	Before State	After State	Status
<i>Transfer KYC</i>	Transfer 10 Tokens from a verified account to another verified account	Account A: 10 Tokens	Account A: 0 Tokens	Ok
		Account B: 0 Token	Account B: 10 Token	Ok
<i>Transfer No KYC</i>	Transfer 10 Tokens from a verified account to an unverified account	Account A: 10 Tokens	Account A: 10 Tokens	Ok
		Account B: 0 Token	Account B: 0 Token	
<i>Purchase KYC</i>	Purchase 1 ETH worth of Tokens from the Crowdsale contract with verified account (KYC)	Account A: 0 Tokens	Account A: 1ETH*token rate Tokens	Ok
<i>Purchase No KYC</i>	Purchase 1 ETH worth of Tokens from the Crowdsale contract with unverified account (KYC)	Account A: 0 Tokens	Account A: 0 Tokens	Ok
<i>Purchase No balance</i>	Purchase 1 ETH worth of Tokens from the Crowdsale contract with account with no balance	Account A: 0 Tokens	Account A: 0 Tokens	Ok
<i>Owner KYC Registration</i>	Account is verified/unverified by the Swiss Realty ETH account	Account A: returns false when checked against KYC	Account A: returns true when checked against KYC	Ok
<i>Owner Operator Registration</i>	Operator is verified/unverified by the Swiss Realty ETH account	Account A: returns false when checked against KYC	Account A: returns true when checked against KYC	Ok
<i>Third party KYC Registration</i>	Account is verified by a Third Party ETH account	Account A: returns false when checked against KYC	Account A: returns true when checked against KYC	Ok
<i>TransferFrom KYC</i>	Transfer token from one account to the other being an allowed account	Account A: 10 Tokens	Account A: 0 Tokens	Ok
		Account B: 0 Token	Account B: 10 Token	Ok
<i>TransferFrom no-KYC</i>	Transfer token from one account to the other being an allowed account	Account A: 10 Tokens	Account A: 10 Tokens	Ok
		Account B: 0 Token	Account B: 0 Token	Ok
<i>Set token rate from owner</i>	Set a new rate to our token on the asset sale contract	Rate: 1CHF = 100 tokens	Rate: 1CHF = 150 tokens	Ok
<i>Set token rate from non-owner</i>	Set a new rate to our token on the asset sale contract	Rate: 1CHF = 100 tokens	Rate: 1CHF = 100 tokens	Ok
<i>Link contracts together / unlink</i>	Set links and authorizations between smart contracts	Contract A linked/unlinked to Contract B	Contract A linked/unlinked to Contract B	Ok

Source: Steiner AG based on Dafflon, Jacques “ERC777 Token Standard” (Github, 2020)

The learning stage allows to observe pilot prototype behaviour effect and extended statistical OLS regression analysis based on extended quantitative market survey results of the market survey of 1000 participants will provide supporting or against arguments for the evolution knowledge outcomes by discerning why an artefact works or not and provide future research considerations (Vaishnavi and Kuechler, 2004). The paper uses information from the knowledge base (e.g., relevant research) to build a convincing argument for the Artefact’s utility. This Ph.D. study sets a clear structure based on Hevner’s (2004) ADSR framework to design and evaluate artefacts that address inefficiencies and transparency issues in commercial real estate contract management. It also adheres to Hevner’s ADSR framework, emphasizing the relevance cycle, design cycle, and rigor cycle.

- **Relevance Cycle:** Defines the problem of inefficiencies in real estate contracts and identifies industry requirements.

- **Design Cycle:** Iteratively develops the conceptual model and blockchain prototype.
- **Rigor Cycle:** Incorporates established knowledge and rigorous evaluation methods.

Evaluation and Reflection: The conceptual model and prototype development presented were based on the expert panel interviews as seen earlier. To build a reflection around the prototype, it is useful to provide the reader a mapping of which points derived from the expert panel were considered in the prototype. Such an endeavour will also prove useful at the time of understanding which effects blockchain technologies bring on our conceptual model and how the prototype has been adapted to fit blockchain specific criteria and constraints.

As a reminder, the experts interviews brought six main points on which the conceptual model was built. Those points evolved around: skills, cost, compliance, governance, adoption and security, points which were addressed and served as a basis to the conceptual model presented earlier. As a reminder, the conceptual model is presented as a three layers model (Actors and Roles, Business Processes and Databases) and includes three main actors (Real estate Owners, Buyers, Investors), on business process (Framework) and two databases (Property Info, KYC/AML).

The prototype is composed, as described earlier, of a series of smart contracts. The minimum structure that would be viable is composed of the KYC/AML smart contracts (database and logic) and the Asset smart contracts (database, logic and sales). The smart contracts evolving around databases would be the one presented in the conceptual model on the database layer, holding the values and balances essential to the prototype such as a specific account balance on its participation on a specific asset, the asset name and asset identification number at the land registry or whether a specific account is authorized or not to participate in transactions. Those database smart contracts are then supported by our business process (framework). This would be the logic smart contracts, smart contracts handling the security of transactions and governance of users.

As indicated by evaluation and reflection phases of our ADSR are continuous cycles for reflection and learning. In the context of the PhD prototype design and built-implementation, key lessons have been learnt and major six points are derived to evaluate and reflect upon the prototype development. During the ongoing reflection and evaluation, important issues were discovered, reflected, and acted upon during the pilot, such as decisions about the following related attributes should be considered:

Adoption and Skills: Those principles governed the choice of the blockchain itself. A blockchain with already a high number of users and a valid cryptocurrency was required and one that has many developers and people working with it daily. As such the prototype was developed on Ethereum.

Governance: The focus on governance here lies in the organization needed to manage account authorized to perform transactions. The prototyped KYX/AML smart contract hold at its core mechanisms to manage efficiently authorizations. Those mechanisms permit several behaviours such as: third-party authorizations of accounts, ability for own accounts to check whether they are authorized, ability for external accounts to audit the accounts authorized. Consequently, the prototype now holds the capabilities of fulfilling a large amount of interest on all aspects of the project. Sellers will be able to receive transactions from audited accounts, third-party AML/KYC providers will be able to continue doing their job and directly record on a blockchain the account statuses and a government or audit agency will be able to check which account has performed which transactions and if it is authorized in real time and at any time.

Compliance: As outlined by the experts, the compliance principle is probably the toughest and hardest point to include in the prototype. The compliance aspect of the project mostly passes through the implementation of offline corporate structures, production of legal and financial documents and the notification to regulatory bodies of the activities performed on such a platform. Although those points and necessary processes were identified, it was decided for the sake of simplification to let those crucial aspect out of the prototype. Although one could argue that the KYC/AML contracts are in fact an effort towards including this principle, in practice the KYC/AML contracts only provide a repository of authorized address, and the actual implementation process would be much longer to implement with a lot of offline bank and checks.

Cost: The cost attribute of the prototype is rooted into the use of the Ethereum blockchain. As described earlier the Ethereum blockchain runs on an essential crypto currency which is ETH. In the Ethereum blockchain ETH serves to provide incentives to the participants to mine transactions. Consequently, there is two moments in which Costs enter in play. The first one is when a smart contract is deployed, and the second one is when a transaction occurs. In both moments, the cost element is paramount as it is one of the main measures of performance. Although costs are reflected to a certain extent and must be considered when evaluating the prototype, it is important to notice that many costs points are left out of the evaluation such as lawyer fees needed to produce legal documents, corporate registration

costs and the cost of developers needed in the process. However, those costs could be considered as a first time, unique investments and as such should not be considered in the evaluation and reflection around the prototype.

Security: Security has been included in the prototype by implementing the recommendations from the community and following the ERC777 standard but also by implementing the Logic/Storage structure that allows the developers to update and patch existing threats in their smart contract implementations. One can easily check on the blockchain actual transactions that happened within our smart contracts and check the relative benefit of the solution from a transaction cost and time management perspective. For example, a transaction of 0.16 ETH which at the time of the transaction represent approximately a transaction of 21.5 EUR took less than 30 seconds for completion and with a cost of 0.000105431 ETH which represents approximately 0.01 EUR to be processed. The great thing about cost of gas is that it is not correlated to the value of the transaction but to the complexity of it relative to the amount of transactions issues. It must be noted that those costs are recorded on the Rinkeby testnet and that, as such, the protocol used is less costly in terms of ETH and EUR. As such, it could be that significant differences will happen in a real-life scenario. Measuring costs on a test network is however a good source of information for the project. It shows that, although variables the costs are minimal and can have a substantial impact on a Real estate transaction especially on the buyer side.

Risks: Potential risks were identified, and mitigation measures developed. The apparent simplicity of such a transaction should not be taken as granted as for it to happen, offline conditions need to be met. A thorough KTC/AML check needs to be performed on the investor before letting the transaction happen, those checks are highly relying on humans and as such are costly to perform. It was also stated earlier that corporate structures would have to be created for this project to see light and that can be costly. It is also essential that specific securitization occurs and for that to happen one looks at least 30 thousand Euros in lawyer fees.

4.6.2. Application of the ADSR Methodology – Artefact 4b prototype statistics

Problem Formulation: Consistent with the theoretical framework (Chapter 3) and Research Artefacts (Chapter 4 – Concept and Pilot) of this thesis, a quantitative study is used to further elaborate on the practical usability and relevance of the developed and prototypically tested concepts. The evolution phase in the ADSR context thus is conducted by means of a market

survey carried out related to. The underlying problem of the evolution stage in the ADSR approach is to evaluate how the Prototype (Artefact 4) is instantiated and to understand whether it solves the problems identified during the development of the conceptual model or not. The evolution stage additionally provides explanation for changed/demanded improvements of the solution.

On the one hand, the internal validity are the previous expert interviews (qualitative research) whose answers gave a solid baseline for the conceptual model. After the prototype solution is developed and implemented, the quality of collecting and analysing empirical data need to be causal explained. Gregor and Hevner (2004) as well as ADSR methodology based on Mullarkey and Hevner (2018). On the other hand, an artificial evaluation may involve simulations, laboratory experiments, theoretical arguments, criteria-based analysis, and mathematical proofs (Venable et al., 2016; Pries-Heje et al., 2008). Peffers et al. 2008 proposes various artefact evaluation and validation techniques which include demonstration, simulation, experimentation (lab or case study), using metrics, benchmarking, logic reasoning, mathematical proofs, field studies, dynamic analysis, expert evaluation, functional testing, action research among others. During the empirical study of the data-intensive survey (N= 700,) the output and input are measured of the respondents and the data is used to understand the relations, causalities and determine the utility and relation function by the regression analysis. and test validity, utility, quality, and efficacy of the prototype development.

In the context of the thesis research problems (RQ01 and RQ02), previous Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact II (Prototype) are examined to test the empirical evidence of the hypothesis (H01 and H02) by conducting the analytical statistical test to derive interrelation between various market participant behaviour tendencies in a wider (regional) area. Specifically, the evaluation method is defined as quantitative analysis which allows to detect potential correlation between factors that could explain if our experts' insights, collected during our qualitative, are relevant and provide supporting evidence to nuance the Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) in conjunction with various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc (Zhang et. Al, 2011).

On this behalf, the thesis cannot be backed by secondary statistics and needs to be extended with the primary data for evaluating the prototype statistics (Artefact 4b) that fits the same asset class and conditions. For that reason, the empirical study/ data insights are derived from the

indirect empirical evaluation of the market participants to test Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) on the prescribed regression analysis conditions. Building on the example of a Commercial real estate property, which was executed on Ethereum blockchain via a smart contract application, the empirical evaluation of the market participants allows to verify the confidence degree of the smart contract product. The degree of confidence will be based on an online survey conducted by the researcher. Empirical evaluation approaches may include observational methods (case studies, field studies); analytical methods (static analysis, dynamic analysis); experimental methods (experiments, simulations); testing (functional, structural); or descriptive methods (informed arguments, scenarios) (Hevner et al, 2004).

Artefact Creation: The components of the design process are kernel theories, design methods and testable design process hypotheses (Zhang et. Al, 2011). An important aspect is the use of the term kernel theory which refers to the behavioural theory that forms the core of a design theory. There is a broad consensus that kernel theories are theories from natural or social sciences and serve as a foundation for artefact construction (Walls et al. 1992, p. 42). In the thesis, kernel theory is applied to derive market behaviour from statistical analysis. Subsequently, the statistical analysis provides a solution for meta-design a class of artefacts conceptual model (Design) and prototype development (Implementation), validates the Artefact construction and provide the evidence whether the prototype development fulfils the criteria of the set out research questions (RQ1, RQ2) and further design process hypotheses (H1,H2) by distilling /extracting insights based on diagnostic accuracy of qualitative structured interviews and quantitative method of regression analysis (Zhang et. Al, 2011).

Figure 4-27: Artefact 4b - Prototype statistics (Evolution phase)

Main Hypothesis based on Research Question 1:

H0: Smart contract on the blockchain technology for the commercial real estate have effect on speed (fast and frictionless), transparency, security, quality (error resistance/stability), validity, utility, trust and reduction of transaction cost, efficacy/efficiency.

H1: Smart contract on the blockchain technology for the commercial real estate have no effect on speed (fast and frictionless), transparency, security, quality (error resistance/stability), validity, utility, trust and reduction of transaction cost, and efficacy/efficiency.

Main Hypothesis based on Research Question 2:

H0: Tokenized real estate investments have effect on the asset liquidity, remove market barriers, create shared accessibility, and generate a widespread funding from multiple sources and leverage return on investment.

H1: Tokenized real estate investments do not have effect on the asset liquidity, remove market barriers, create shared accessibility, and generate a widespread funding from multiple sources and leverage return on investment.

These hypotheses, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, that numbered data can be analysed using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2009, p. 31), especially validity criteria for the regression statistics.

Evaluation and Reflection: To test the product and process design of the “Smart Contract ACCAS”, statistical regression analysis is used to identify what relations/parameters exist in general crypto investment in Real estate and how strong is the impact of each parameter on our base hypotheses as defined later in this chapter. The thesis studies deeper relationships between Research Artefact 1 (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) developed in Chapter 4 and investigates evaluation methods in relation to the Design Science Research (DSR) as described in Table 4-3. The thesis goes one step further and provides transparent evaluation, reflection and learning along the selected process kernel theories for design methods and proposes to test product as well as design process hypothesis with various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc (Zhang et. al, 2011).

Concretely, the hypotheses are applied to measure statistical significance of both main hypothesis H1: “Smart Contract ACCAS” and H02: “Tokenized Investments” fulfilling various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc. The regression analysis is applied to evaluate expected and unexpected (undesirable) casualties of the Artefact “for other (undesirable) impacts’ (Venable, 2006), otherwise known

as side effects” if any. In his article, Koppenhagen et al. (2011) recommends carrying out both, qualitative and quantitative study based on qualitative use cases and derived conceptual models in the field studies for evaluations. The evaluation methods in DSR studies are described in the Table 4-3 below.

Table 4-3 Action Design Research (ADR) Evolution – Empirical Survey, SPSS Variables

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label	Values	Missing	Columns	Align	Measure	Role
1	ID	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
2	Gender	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
3	Age	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
4	Relationship_status	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
5	Children	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
6	Income	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
7	Career	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
8	Education_level	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
9	Employment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
10	Region	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
11	Blockchain_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
12	Cryptoart	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
13	Realestate_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
14	Financial_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
15	Investment_appetite	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
16	Return_to_invest	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
17	Crypto_favorable	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
18	Difficulty_in_investing	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
19	Governance	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
20	Regu_chall	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
21	Speed_sc	Numeric	8	2		None	None	13	Right	Ordinal	Input
22	Transparency_role	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
23	Main_sec_challenge	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
24	Trad_errors_resolved	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
25	Transac_cost_influence	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
26	Trust_investment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
27	RQ_Speed	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
28	RQ_Transparency	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
29	RQ_Security	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
30	RQ_Quality	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
31	RQ_Validity	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
32	RQ_Utility	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
33	RQ_Trust	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
34	RQ_Cost	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
35	RQ_Efficiency	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
36	RQ_Smart_contract_option	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
37	RQ_Tokenised_investment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
38											
39											

Source: SPSS analysis

Learning

The triangulation in research means using multiple datasets, methods, theories and/or investigators to address a research question. The aim of the triangulation strategy is therefore to enhance the validity and credibility of the respective findings of the Ph.D. research. This study adopts a mixed methods approach for the purpose of methodological triangulation. The Artefact is evaluated to demonstrate its worth with evidence addressing criteria such as architecture, optimization, informed argument, scenarios, and testing.

As seen previously, blockchain technologies provide a clear case when it comes to transactions cost and speed. However, especially in the real estate industry, regulations specific to jurisdictions and financial regulations would render such projects costly. However,

as stated earlier, the costs related to first time investments should not be considered when evaluating the prototype because the same investments are required for a company willing to conduct a large real estate transaction anyway. One should mostly focus on the reduced transaction costs and speed at which the transaction happens which would mean a significant reduction in costs when compared to a traditional transaction that would require crafting contracts with specialized lawyers, go through a transaction through several banks probably taking between 2-5 days to clear and then waiting for confirmation from the Real estate owner. The blockchain transaction in other hand took less than 30 seconds to complete.

One cost that should also be considered is the cost of transactions relative to the complexity of mining increasing over time as more transactions are being processed. The fear is that, under the current Ethereum blockchain, the difficulty of processing a transaction would become so high that transactions and smart contract deployment would be worth 100s of EUR. This poses the threat of scalability of such solutions in the future. However, as mentioned by one of our interviewees, the Ethereum community is working on a migration towards a lighter, more scalable protocol that will mean less decentralization but more speed and ultimately less costs.

The focus however should be turned from cost to adoption. Adoption, as mentioned by the interviewees is the single most important factor when it comes to blockchain technologies. Not only from an end user point of view, but also on the legislative side. Laws and regulations have a deep impact on blockchain technologies because of their geographic, closed and centralized nature. Contrary to the blockchains which are evolutive, open sourced and decentralized in nature. This dichotomy poses a threat to the adoption of such a model since it does not allow blockchain projects to be free of innovation. Many roadblocks will be on the road of such implementations in the future such as investment management, securitization, and regulators' audit. The apparent simplicity of the solution when it comes strictly to blockchain should not be taken for granted as real-life implementations would be much more difficult to realize.

The prototype development (Proof of Concept) demonstrated by comparing the traditional process in line with the recent Swiss Federal Council Blockchain Law, allowing P2P (P2P) global investments in real estate tokens. On the one hand, the equivalent for measurement has been set such as Swiss Franc (CHF) for the real estate price traditional bank and Gas fee for the Ethereum contract. The transaction could be performed with the Smart Contract on Ethereum resulting in the total cost of 0.00019879 Ether which is equivalent to 2. Cents CHF. On the other hand, the asset price was fragmented into tokens of the quotation 1CHF = 1 Token and allowed to attract global revenue streams.

5. EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF RESEARCH ARTEFACTS

5.1. Overview

Consistent with the theoretical framework (Chapter 3) and Research Artefacts (Chapter 4 – Concept and Pilot) of this thesis, a quantitative study is used to further elaborate on the practical usability and relevance of the developed and prototypically tested concepts. Therefore, a statistically representative sample of the population across a variety of georegions is used. The evolution phase in the DSRM context thus is conducted by means of a market survey carried out related to Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) (Venable, 2006).

The analytical regression is designed to empirically evaluate Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) and to identify whether the prototype can contribute to an improvement in comparison to the traditional commercial real estate contract and determine impact on the return on investment for the investor by using tokenized investment scheme. Therefore, the analytical regression is used to show what are the relations of parameters for a crypto investment in real estate and how strong is the impact of each parameter on the investment decision. In this sense, the regression analysis is applied to evaluate expected and unexpected (undesirable) causalities of the Artefact “for other (undesirable) impacts’ (Venable, 2006), otherwise known as side effects” if any. In his article, Koppenhagen et al. (2011) recommends carrying out a quantitative study based on qualitative field studies for evaluations; data gathering via un-structured, semi-structured interviews, transcription and coding, semi-experimental setup, semi-quantitative pre-study.

While the transcription and coding structured interviews have been applied in the Chapter 4, the Chapter 5 applies a technique of quantitative market study. By using the quantitative technique, the thesis studies deeper relationships between the conceptual model developed in Chapter 4, the real estate investment platform prototype developed in Chapter 4 and the likelihood that the public will eventually be inclined to use such a service.

To test the product and process design of the “Smart Contract ACCAS”, statistical regression analysis is used to identify what relations/parameters exist in general crypto investment in Real estate and how strong is the impact of each parameter on our base hypotheses as defined later in this chapter. The thesis studies deeper relationships between Research Artefact I

(Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) developed in Chapter 4 and investigates evaluation methods in relation to the DSR.

The thesis goes one step further and provides transparent evaluation, reflection and learning along the selected process kernel theories for design methods and proposes to test product as well as design process hypothesis with various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc (Zhang et. Al., 2011).

The components of the design process are kernel theories, design methods and testable design process hypotheses (Zhang et. al, 2011). An important aspect is the use of the term kernel theory which refers to the behavioural theory that forms the core of a design theory. There is a broad consensus that kernel theories are theories from natural or social sciences and serve as a foundation for Artefact construction (Walls et al. 1992). In the thesis, kernel theory is applied to derive market behaviour from statistical analysis. Subsequently, the statistical analysis provides a solution for meta-design a class of artefacts Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype), validates the Artefact construction and provide the evidence whether the Research Artefact 2 fulfils the criteria of the set out research questions (RQ1 and RQ2) and further design process hypotheses (H1 and H2) by distilling /extracting insights based on diagnostic accuracy of qualitative structured interviews and quantitative method of regression analysis (Zhang et. Al, 2011) In this sense, the thesis provides the test of Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) in terms of product as well as design process hypothesis with various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc (Zhang et. al, 2011).

Concretely, the hypotheses are applied to measure statistical significance of both main Research Question RQ1: "Smart Contract" and RQ2: "Tokenized Investments" fulfilling various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc. The regression analysis is applied to evaluate expected and unexpected (undesirable) casualties of the Artefact "for other (undesirable) impacts' (Venable, 2006), otherwise known as side effects" if any. In his article, Koppenhagen et al. (2011) recommends carrying out both, qualitative and quantitative study based on qualitative use cases and derived conceptual models in the field studies for evaluations. The evaluation methods in Design Science Research (DSR) works are described below (table 16).

Table 16: Evaluation methods in related DSR works

Authors	Evaluation Method
Gass et al. (2001)	1) Evaluation scenario was derived base on initially defined persona and use-case, for two design principles: seamless integration with web services and with local services in a lab experiment with end-performance measurement for a particular set of tasks 2) The different conditions included the availability or the absence of the integration service for the predefined tasks
Gregor and Jones (2007)	Simplified structure with six core components (1–6) and two additional components (7, 8): (1) Purpose and scope, (2) constructs, (3) principles of form and function, (4) Artefact mutability, (5) testable propositions, (6) justificatory knowledge, (7) principles of implementation, and (8) expository instantiation
Gurzick and Lutters (2009)	1) Use the possibility of the artefact for collection of usage data and pre-/post surveys with design-oriented questions conducted online with the community members 2) Results of usage data collections and surveys proved the validity of DDs and DPs
Kopenhagen et al. (2011)	1) Early evaluation of design principles and decisions via persona descriptions, use-cases, concept models, visual designs, ACV and later (planned) APV 2) Qualitative field studies for evaluations; data gathering via un-structured, semi-structured interviews, transcription and coding, semi-experimental setup, semi-quantitative pre-study
Walls et al (1992)	components of a design product are (1) a class of requirements (“meta-requirements”), (2) a class of Artefacts hypothesized to meet the “meta-requirements” (“meta-design”), (3) theories from natural or social sciences governing design requirements (“kernel theories”), and (4) testable design product hypotheses used to test whether the “meta-design” satisfies the “meta-requirements”; those of a design process are (1) a design method describing procedures for Artefact construction, (2) kernel theories, and (3) testable design process hypotheses
Zhang et al. (2011)	1) Transparent evaluation, reflection and learning along the selected process kernel theories for design methods 2) Test of design product as well as design process hypothesis with various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc.

Subsequently, the thesis uses two approaches as evaluation methods of innovation product in Commercial real estate in their interconnectedness with other influencing variables and thus derive an answer to the research question of this thesis. On one hand a transparent evaluation, reflection and learning along the selected process kernel theories for design methods Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and on the other hand the design product Prototype development “Smart Contract ACCAS” artefact Research Artefact 2 (Prototype). The Research Artefact II (Prototype development) is evaluated to demonstrate its worth with evidence addressing criteria such as validity, utility, quality, and efficacy which are statistically tested based on the design testing hypothesis based on the Research Questions (RQ01, RQ02) of the Thesis.

Practically, the hypotheses are applied to measure statistical significance of both main hypothesis RQ1: “Smart Contract” and RQ2: “Tokenized Investments” fulfilling various statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc. The regression analysis is applied to evaluate expected and unexpected (undesirable) casualties of the Artefact “for other (undesirable) impacts’ (Venable, 2006). The thesis studies deeper loop of practical relevance and rigorously conducted design research and specifically in the Chapter 5 to identify the relationships between Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model)

and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) developed in chapter 4 and investigates evaluation methods in related Design Science Research (DSR). For the inductive as well as for the deductive steps qualitative or quantitative rigorous research methods must be applied for data gathering and analysis in context of the evaluations and subsequent agile development and prototyping methods in the artefact build activities.

5.2. Research Artefact- Artefact

The underlying research artefact Empirical survey is to evaluate how the Research Artefact II (Prototype) is instantiated and to understand whether it solves the problems identified during the development of the conceptual model Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) or not. The evolution stage additionally provides explanation for changed/demanded improvements of the solution. In the context of the thesis research problems (RQ01 and RQ02), previous Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact II (Prototype) are examined to test the empirical evidence of the previous aims and objectives as defined in the Chapter 1 of the research.

On the one hand, the empirical survey of the RQ 01 “Smart Contract” is required to confirm or reject previous expert semi-structured interviews and identify the relevant factors for improvements of the digital Commercial Real estate transaction and show on behalf of the regression equation the key potentials towards traditional paper-based contract with human-based interactions (Research Artefact 1 – Conceptual Model). On the other hand, the empirical survey of the RQ 02 “Tokenised Investments” is required to confirm or reject previous expert semi-structured interviews to measure the utility of the prototype development implementation (Research Artefact 2- Prototype) for the Smart Contract on ERC777 based on the Web Application server and connection with interexchange Online Browser Metamask and reflect with a large-scale quantitative survey empirical results in order to derive interrelation between various market participant behaviour tendencies in a wider geographical area. Concretely, the thesis provides a larger empirical survey which includes many platform participants (N=1000) different roles, responsibilities, geo-regions, ages, gender and various ethical and professional backgrounds to achieve most of utilization and data independency.

Specifically, the evaluation method is defined as quantitative analysis which allows to detect potential correlation between factors that could explain if our experts' insights, collected during our qualitative, are relevant and provide supporting evidence to nuance the Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) in conjunction with various

statistical methods like linear regression, online surveys for pre- and post-test, scatter plots etc (Zhang et. Al, 2011). On this behalf, the thesis cannot be backed by secondary statistics and needs to be extended with the primary data for evaluating the Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) that fits the same asset class and conditions. For that reason, the empirical study/ data insights are derived from the indirect empirical evaluation of the market participants to test Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) on the prescribed regression analysis conditions. Building on the example of a commercial real estate property, which was executed on Ethereum blockchain via a smart contract application, the empirical evaluation of the market participants allows to verify the confidence degree of the “smart contract” product.

The degree of confidence will be based on an online survey conducted by the researcher. Empirical evaluation approaches may include observational methods (case studies, field studies); analytical methods (static analysis, dynamic analysis); experimental methods (controlled experiments, simulations); testing (functional, structural); or descriptive methods (informed arguments, scenarios) (Hevner et al, 2004). Thus, the design of the Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) is based on the previously reviewed literature which supported the development of the comprehensive Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and is illustrated in the Figure 5-1 and 5-2 below.

Figure 5-1. Design of the Conceptual Model – Status Quo vs. New Approach

Figure 5-2. Artefact – Prototype Conceptual Model

5.3. Linkage to the Research Artefacts

The Conceptual model (Research Artefact 1) has been developed based on the Action Design Research design principles where each phase was elaborated with multiple intervention cycles based on the observation from industry experts. The qualitative method of content analysis of the expert interviews provided the baseline for identification of transcription parameters to design and build an appropriate platform for the commercial real estate contract and create an open real estate commercial contract eco-system by using the permissionless Ethereum for buyer, seller, notary, land registry, housing authority.

The prototype solution (Research Artefact 2) was based on the literature review diagnosis and collected feedback from the explorative expert interviews as previously mentioned in the conceptual model for the commercial real estate smart contract. The Prototype solution was to develop a fictional Ethereum blockchain smart contract application rendering possible the sale of a Real estate asset (ex. A shopping mall) which application is based on the Ethereum Contract protocol (ERC 820/777) that is widely recommended by the open source Ethereum organization.

The tests demonstrated that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract and performed on a blockchain with reliability and efficiency. The Ph.D. thesis provided the prototype for the smart contract on the ERC 820/777 using tools and

frameworks such as the “Truffle Framework”, the solidity programming language and cloud based virtual machines. The implementation phase was integrated into the contract development a) develop and program Smart Contract on Solidity as a programming language and use text editor Visual Basic Studio for coding activities and b) globally test the results by using the “Truffle Framework” to generate virtual blockchains and simulate transactions – essentially Ganache was used to run local Ethereum Blockchains and Truffle to compile and deploy smart contracts from the command line and launch Truffle tests on the global blockchain <https://www.trufflesuite.com/>. In order to test the prototype solution (Research Artefact 2), the researcher makes use of the Web3.js protocol and tests – 1) smart contract deployment, 2) gas cost of doing so and provides an interface on which specific transactions can be accurately tested and measured and 3) account balances – every account has a balance of the Ethereum blockchain in the form of a native cryptocurrency called Ether. Once the tests have been performed, the front-end development has been performed with Web3.js (a library allowing connection to Ethereum Blockchains) for the user interface. By using the Web3.js, it is possible to retrieve the balance of an account at a given block using its API and perform other transactions on such platforms.

The process starts with empirical evaluation of the questions and data collection activities of raw data which gives a baseline for construction of data parameters and later execution of the descriptive and analytical statistical tests for hypothesis testing. Following the empirical process, the following hypothesis will be designed to evaluate the Research Artefact 1 (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) and identify customer behaviour on crypto investment for the developed prototype solution and need to evaluate supporting evidence from the market survey.

The research questions of this thesis are linked to the statistical parameters which will be measured by the regression equation by the univariate nature (1:1 relation) or multivariate relation , where multiple independent variables may explain the dependent variable such as financial services, blockchain and real estate knowledge will not increase your crypto investments: multi variable hypothesis in order to see the correlation between knowledge of those very specific areas and the likelihood to invest in real estate via the blockchain. Furthermore, the findings are linked to the main research questions of this thesis in multiple ways and deliver empirical evidence for several related questions. In this sense, the thesis shows two main hypotheses to answer the research questions which are measured, typically

on instruments, that numbered data can be analysed using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2009), specifically validity criteria for the regression statistics (Pfahler, 2020).

5.4. Preparation for the Empirical Evaluation Process

5.4.1. Discovery Phase - Data Design

According to Mullarkey and Hevner (2018), the ADR process model is recommended to be conducted with multiple research entry points in order to provide a level of face validity to our proposed elaborated ADR process model, the Thesis initially studied a selected set of individual variables (univariate) on their correlations (Iteration 1) during the (Development-Centered) and derived the baseline factors for the multivariate regression analysis through the observation during the (Iteration 2) of the strongest correlations factors (Observation-Centered). In the context of the iterative approach of the ADSR method, this thesis first analysed individual factors for their correlations, for which we formulated so-called sub hypotheses. To thoroughly understand such correlations and to craft the best regression line with the most explicative power, these supportive sub-hypotheses are analysed below. On this basis, the main hypotheses of this work are developed in the following section. They are based on the unity matrix derived from this section and focus on the strongest correlations between the independent variables. For this reason, a multivariate regression equation is developed and the respective prerequisites (such as descriptive statistics and analytical statistics such as Correlations (Pearson, Kendal-Tau, Linear and Multivariate Regression, Tests on Normality (Shapiro Wilk), Linearity (RESET), Multicollinearity Diagnostics (VIF), Homo vs. Heteroscedasticity (Breusch Pagan, White Test) and Autocorrelation (Durbin Watson) need to be fulfilled. As illustrated in the Figure 5-3, the ADR method is recognised to approach the research problems, defined earlier, from multiple entry points which are tackled successively in an agile perspective how effective and efficient the ensembled artefact demonstrates the factors which are most significantly causal to explain the efficacy of the Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) (iteration 1, sub-hypothesis testing, and 2, main hypothesis testing).

Figure 5-3. Possible entry points for the study (Source: Mullarkey and Hevner, 2018, p. 7)

5.4.2. Exploration Phase - Data Collection

Previous expert semi-structured interviews need to be explored to refine the conceptual model and prototype, which were subsequently evaluated through the survey. Consequently, the thesis presents a comprehensive examination of cryptocurrency investment in real estate through an empirical online market survey conducted in July 2020. Previous research questions need to be mapped to the statistical parameters to be able to derive the factor relation by the regression equation for each Research Question RQ.1 and RQ.2.

In this context, the empirical survey data utilised a sample of 1000 respondents, statistical analysis was employed to investigate the factors influencing investments in tokenized real estate. Given the absence of primary studies providing datasets on this topic, the survey design was informed by previous conceptual models and prototype development. Expert input was solicited to refine the conceptual model and prototype, which were subsequently evaluated through the survey. The sample encompassed diverse demographics, including individuals from six geographical regions and various socio-economic backgrounds of the smart contract on the blockchain technology (RQ.1) and understand the tokenised Investments cryptocurrency investment in real estate by providing empirical insights into the factors shaping investment decisions (RQ.2). Through a rigorous survey methodology and analysis, this research endeavours to conduct empirical survey to derive valid key message for the investors, policymakers, and researchers about the opportunities and challenges in this evolving investment landscape to ensure robustness and independence in the analysis.

After successful completion of the semi-structured interviews, the PhD thesis integrated the factors for the new design for the Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and build the development for the Research Artefact 2 (Prototype). However, the expert interviews had only a limited representation (20 expert interviews) and need to be further evaluated by a larger

sample of demographic parameters to validate previous findings on smart contracts and tokenised investments of the cryptocurrency investment in real estate.

For this reason, expert-interviews were mapped from the source of the legacy old process (AS-IS- Design) to the new decentralised process (Conceptual Model) and built development (Prototype) which covered the business requirements (features) mapped as 37 SPSS variables- including age, geographic region, education, income, financial literacy, and investment experience, the study aims to ensure the independence of these parameters. The thesis provides a comprehensive analysis of each variable, examining their definitions and implications for the survey design. By structuring the parameters systematically, the research contributes to a nuanced understanding of the factors shaping cryptocurrency investment behaviour in the real estate sector. Those parameters are represented as SPSS Variables (37 variables) which are used in the survey. These are defined and explained in Table 5-1.

Table 5-1. ADR Evolution – Empirical Survey, SPSS Variables (Source: SPSS analysis)

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label	Values	Missing	Columns	Align	Measure	Role
1	ID	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
2	Gender	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
3	Age	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
4	Relationship_status	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
5	Children	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
6	Income	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Scale	Input
7	Career	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
8	Education_level	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
9	Employment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
10	Region	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
11	Blockchain_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
12	Cryptoart	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
13	Realestate_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
14	Financial_literacy	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
15	Investment_appetite	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
16	Return_to_invest	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
17	Crypto_favorable	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
18	Difficulty_in_investing	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
19	Governance	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
20	Regu_chall	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
21	Speed_sc	Numeric	8	2		None	None	13	Right	Ordinal	Input
22	Transparency_role	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
23	Main_sec_challenge	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
24	Trad_errors_resolved	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
25	Transac_cost_influence	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
26	Trust_investment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
27	RQ_Speed	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
28	RQ_Transparency	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
29	RQ_Security	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
30	RQ_Quality	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
31	RQ_Validity	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
32	RQ_Utility	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
33	RQ_Trust	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
34	RQ_Cost	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
35	RQ_Efficiency	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Nominal	Input
36	RQ_Smart_contract_option	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
37	RQ_Tokenised_investment	Numeric	8	2		None	None	8	Right	Ordinal	Input
38											
39											

This study investigates the external validation of a conceptual model and prototype through a survey of 1,000 respondents representing diverse demographics and backgrounds. The study

engages experts in the development process to refine the prototype from its original conceptualization. The survey encompasses six geographical regions and various participant groups, including students, experts, and non-experts, across different ages and backgrounds. The aim is to ensure a robust evaluation framework that accounts for the independence of potentially influential factors. The parameters of respondents (Wu, Zhao and Fils-Aime, 2022) is listed in Table 5-2 below.

Table 5-2: Survey Parameters

#	Parameter Name	Description
1	ID	Used to register and identify the participant.
2	Gender	Tests if gender can be a significant factor in being more inclined or not to invest in real estate through crypto currencies. The assumption would be that males, because of sociological factors, would be more prone to invest in real estate.
3	Age	Tests if age has an impact on the crypto awareness but also on how people will perceive our project and its capabilities.
4	Relationship_status	Tests the respondent's relationship status as it might have an impact on investment and risk taking.
5	Dependants	Demographic variable describing the respondent's number of children as it might have an impact on capital available and risk taking.
6	Income	This places the respondents within a socioeconomic tranche.
7	Career	Variable allowing the respondent to describe their career.
8	Level of Education	Establishes the education level of the respondent.
9	Employment Status	Establishes the respondent's employment status.
10	Region	Tests if crypto currencies and even more investing in crypto currencies is a geographical phenomenon. It is to be tested whether investing in the prototype developed will be correlated to regional factors.
11	Blockchain Literacy	Tests whether the respondents are knowledgeable in blockchain or are not to see if this concept is only attractable to people with a strong knowledge of the core technology. This variable will be able to tell if the concept developed can ultimately reach a large cohort of people.
12	Cryptoart	Tests if respondents were already active or not in the field of cryptocurrencies, this would most likely be a significant factor in their involvement with a project like the one described in our Artefacts.
13	Real_Estate_Literracy	Tests the knowledge level of the respondents regarding the real estate industry.
14	Financial_Literracy	Tests the knowledge level of the respondents regarding the financial services industry.

15	Investment Appetite	Tests if the respondents are currently involved in any kind of other investment activities to check if people that have already crossed the path from non-investor to investors would be interested in the concept and the prototype developed earlier.
16	Return_on_Invest	Tests if the return expected from this kind of investment is aligned to the kind of return investing in real estate can provide. It is common awareness that most crypto investors do so because they believe blockchain will provide them with higher return.
17	Crypto_Favorable	Checks the respondents' opinion on crypto currencies. This variable will be used to see if it could have an impact on the prototype adoption.
18	Difficulty_in_Investing	Checks how difficult, if at all, it is for people to invest online in the real estate industry. In fact, the prototypes directly address this issue, and it could be a good factor to see if such a concept makes sense in the first place.
19	Governance	Tests the perceived level of governance that respondents believe is necessary to organize real estate investments.
20	Regu_chall	Tests what is the opinion of the respondents on the level of regulation that should be involved in the Real estate investments.
21	Speed_sc	Tests the speed factor of smart contracts in the opinion of respondents.
22	Transparency	Tests how important transparency would be for the respondents in the smart contracts. As blockchain application would render transactions transparent, the thesis needs to check if that would be a factor influencing the real estate investment.
23	Main_sec_challenge	Tests if the respondent sees any security challenges that can be resolved or tackled with the blockchain technology.
24	Trad_errors_resolved	Tests the respondent's opinion on errors within the traditional real estate transactions that could be resolved with a blockchain system.
25	Transac_cost_influence	Tests if the transactional cost lowered by blockchain technology is a significant factor for our respondent.
26	Trust_investment	Tests if the trust factor is influencing the respondent opinion of the blockchain based transactions.

The eleven factors that formed the multiple-choice questions are listed in Table 5-3 below. These replies are used to verify if any factor would be more important than the other in the context of blockchain-based real estate transactions.

Table 5-3: Factors used in the multiple-choice questions

#	Factor
1	RQ_Speed

2	RQ_Transparency
3	RQ_Security
4	RQ_Quality
5	RQ_Validity
6	RQ_Utility
7	RQ_Trust
8	RQ_Cost
9	RQ_Efficiency
10	RQ_Smart_contract_option
11	RQ_Tokenised_investment

Thus, the factors are summarised on the previously reviewed literature which supported the development of the comprehensive Research Artefact I (Conceptual Model) and The Prototype solution (Research Artefact 2). In doing so, all the described parameters listed previously are used for testing the hypothesis as mentioned.

5.5. Realization of the Statistical Data Analysis and Testing

5.5.1. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics are used throughout data analysis. The tables below (see Tables 5-4 and 5-5) shows the relation of variables regarding to means, standard deviations, ranges and standard errors of valid cases of one variable for multivariate regression analysis.

RQ.1: What is the impact of the smart contracts on the blockchain technology in the context of commercial real estates? This question examines the impact on speed (fast and frictionless), transparency, security, quality (error resistance/stability), validity, utility, trust and reduction of transaction cost, and efficacy and efficiency.

Table 5-4: SPSS Descriptive Statistics for the Hypothesis based on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Main_sec_challenge	3.0986	1.35754	700
Speed_sc	3.2000	1.41825	700
Transparency_role	3.0257	1.27905	700
Trad_errors_resolved	3.1400	1.30163	700
Trust_investment	3.4957	1.33886	700

RQ.2: What is the impact of the tokenized real estate investments? The question examines the impact on asset liquidity, removal of market barriers, accessibility and the generation of funding from multiple sources and to leverage the return on investment.

Table 5-5: SPSS Descriptive Statistics for the Hypothesis based on RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Return_to_invest	3.0600	1.76092	700
Realestate_litteracy	1.8357	.99362	700
Financial_litteracy	1.7471	.97188	700
Investment_appetite	3.1229	1.42802	700
Crypto_favorable	3.6900	1.54833	700

5.5.2. Analytical Statistics - Test on Correlations

The correlation test is a procedure for testing whether two or more variables are dependent among each other. While the Pearson correlation coefficient is suitable for normally distributed scale variables such as age and income, the Spearman rank correlation coefficient accommodates ordinal and non-normally distributed variables like behaviour and trust. Both coefficients measure the correlation relation and can measure a range from -1 to +1, with -1 indicating a perfect negative correlation, +1 indicating a perfect positive correlation, and 0 indicating no correlation at all. The results and findings are derived from the Table 5-6 below, both coefficients (Pearson and Spearman) have been conducted for the simulation involving 1000 market participants and effectively show each factors relation for the RQ01 Smart Contract - Speed_sc (0.6), Transparency_role (0.5), Number of errors Trad_errors_resolved (0.5), and Trust_investment (0.5).

Table 5-6. SPSS Coefficients of Regression on RQ1 – Smart Contract (Source: SPSS Calculation of Customer Survey Data)

- y = score of **Main_Sec_Challenges**
- x1 = score of **Speed**
- x2 = score of **Transparency**
- x3 = score of **Quality (Number of Errors)**
- x4 = score of **Trust**

Pearson Correlations for Rang variables (Ordinal variables)

		Main_sec_c hallenge	Spee d_sc	Transpare ncy_role	Trad_errors resolved	Trust_inv estment
Pears on Correl ation	Main_sec_c hallenge	1.000	.647	.515	.538	.551
	Speed_sc	.647	1.000	.451	.506	.492
	Transparenc y_role	.515	.451	1.000	.447	.412
	Trad_errors resolved	.538	.506	.447	1.000	.520
	Trust_invest ment	.551	.492	.412	.520	1.000
Sig. (1- tailed)	Main_sec_c hallenge	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Speed_sc	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	Transparenc y_role	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	Trad_errors resolved	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	Trust_invest ment	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	Main_sec_c hallenge	700	700	700	700	700
	Speed_sc	700	700	700	700	700
	Transparenc y_role	700	700	700	700	700
	Trad_errors resolved	700	700	700	700	700
	Trust_invest ment	700	700	700	700	700

The results and findings are derived from Table 5-7 below, both coefficients (Pearson and Spearman) have been conducted for the simulation involving 700 participants and effectively show each factors relation for the RQ.2 Tokenised Investments - Return_to_invest (1), Realestate_litteracy (2), Financial_litteracy (3), Investment_appetite (4), Crypto_favorable (5).

Table 5-7. SPSS Coefficients of Regression Analysis on RQ2 – Return of Tokenized Investments.

y = score of **Return_to_invest**
x1 = score of **Realestate_litteracy**
x2 = score of **Financial_litteracy**
x3 = score of **Investment_appetite**
x4 = score of **Crypto_favorable**

Pearson Correlations for Rang variables (Ordinal variables)

	Return_to invest	Realestate_l itteracy	Finance_lit teracy	Investment_ appetite	Crypto_fav orable
Return_to_in vest	1.000	.251	.280	.373	.399

Pearson Correlation	Realestate_litteracy	.251	1.000	.407	.251	.254
	Financial_litteracy	.280	.407	1.000	.279	.283
	Investment_appetite	.373	.251	.279	1.000	.354
	Crypto_favorable	.399	.254	.283	.354	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Return_to_invest	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Realestate_litteracy	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	Financial_litteracy	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	Investment_appetite	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	Crypto_favorable	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	Return_to_invest	700	700	700	700	700
	Realestate_litteracy	700	700	700	700	700
	Financial_litteracy	700	700	700	700	700
	Investment_appetite	700	700	700	700	700
	Crypto_favorable	700	700	700	700	700

Both coefficients measure the correlation relation and can measure a range from -1 to +1, with -1 indicating a perfect negative correlation, +1 indicating a perfect positive correlation, and 0 indicating no correlation at all. Both coefficients (Pearson and Spearman) have been conducted for the simulation involving 1000 market participants and effectively show each factors relation for the RQ.2 Tokenised Investments - Realestate_litteracy (0.3), Financial_litteracy (0.3), Investment_appetite (0.4), Crypto_favorable (0.4).

5.5.3. Test on Freedom-Statistics (F-Test)

This study used Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and F-tests to assess the significance of independent variables in predicting cryptocurrency investment outcomes. The F-test is used to determine whether the R^2 regression coefficient is significantly greater than zero, indicating the significance of the regression model. The Anova F-Test is a test of whether R^2 regression coefficient is significantly greater than zero.

Table 5-8. SPSS Coefficients of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the Hypothesis based on RQ.1 – Smart Contract

F (Regression, Residual) = F Value

F (4, 695) = 204.664, where $p < 0.005$

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	696.719	4	174.180	204.664	.000 ^b
	Residual	591.480	695	.851		
	Total	1288.199	699			

a. Dependent Variable: Main_sec_challenge

b. Predictors: (Constant), Trust_investment, Transparency_role, Speed_sc, Trad_errors_resolved

Source: SPSS Calculation of Customer Survey Data

In the case of the RQ.1 Smart Contract, the R² is significantly greater than zero and therefore our predictors can account for a significant amount of variance of the dependent variables: Main_sec_challenge (H01) and Return_to_invest (H02). On the one hand, this means that all the predictors' Trust_investment, Transparency_role, Speed_sc, Trad_errors_resolved predict Main_sec_challenge (H01) significantly.

Table 5-9. SPSS Coefficients of Regression analysis for the Hypothesis based RQ.2 – Return of tokenized Investments

F (Regression, Residual) = F Value

F (4, 525) = 55.405, where $p < 0.005$

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	524.053	4	131.013	55.405	.000 ^b
	Residual	1643.427	695	2.365		
	Total	2167.480	699			

a. Dependent Variable: Return_to_invest

b. Predictors: (Constant), Crypto_favorable, Realestate_literacy, Investment_appetite, Financial_literacy

On the other hand, this means that all the predictors' Crypto_favorable, Realestate_literacy, Investment_appetite, Financial_literacy predict Return_to_invest (H02) significantly. Consequently, the thesis indicates that the amount of unique variance (unique to itself) of predictors account for statistically significant explanation of the dependant variables, which illustrates that in our both cases Main_sec_challenge (H01) and Return_to_invest (H02) could be uniquely explained by significant number of variances of below mentioned predictors.

The findings of Freedom Statistics (F-Test) evaluated linearity and normal distribution through the examination of classes of independent variables and calculation of mean with standard deviation, however the study does not validate significance of the independent variables. Both research questions pass the criteria of the independent variables indicates different classes and the calculation of mean with standard deviation of RQ01 Smart Contract and RQ02 Tokenised Investment P-Value (Sig.) less than 0.05 of both tests for the parameters for the RQ.1 and RQ.2 are valid, and the regression model is significant.

5.5.4. Test on Significance T-Test (T-Value interpretation)

Next step is to perform the Significance Test (T-Test) that should contribute to a better understanding of the factors influencing cryptocurrency investment decisions and analysis of Smart Contract (RQ01) and Tokenised Investments (RQ02) predictors can account for a significant amount of variance in the dependent variables for each of the regression equation of RQ.1 and RQ.2.

Through T-test derivation for the slope, hypothesis testing, and analysis of mean differences, the study evaluates the impact of these variables on smart contract behavior and return on investment. The findings (see Table 5-10) provide insights into the level of dependency between independent and dependent variables, aiding decision-making processes for investors and policymakers in the cryptocurrency market. In this context, the thesis needs to identify the significance linear relationship between an independent variable speed_sc, transparency_role, trad_errors_resolved, trust_investments and a dependent variable RQ1 Smart Contracts behaviour. Thus, the thesis carries out t-test derivation for the slope by calculating the p-value and analysing it with the predicted level of significance test measurement. Subsequently, the hypothesis H Main_sec_challenge and Return_to_invest are tested on the significance level of variances Finally, the t-value provides the decision-making process whether, the thesis rejects the null hypothesis (H0) or to accept the alternative hypothesis (H1).

Table 5-10.SPSS Sample Test (T-Test) for the Hypothesis based on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Partial	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	.090	.115		.783	.434	-.135	.315					
Speed_sc	.368	.031	.384	11.903	.000	.307	.428	.647	.412	.306	.634	1.576
Transparency_role	.201	.032	.190	6.239	.000	.138	.265	.515	.230	.160	.714	1.401
Trad errors resolved	.159	.034	.152	4.650	.000	.092	.226	.538	.174	.120	.616	1.622
Trust_investment	.207	.033	.204	6.372	.000	.143	.271	.551	.235	.164	.642	1.557

a. Dependent Variable: Main_sec_challenge

The Sample T-Test illustrates each pair dependent variables for the highest T-Values and mean differences. On the one hand, the Smart Contract variable “speed_sc” indicates the lowest mean difference of which means equal-independency for the Main_sec_challenge – (H01). On the other hand, the Real estate “crypto favourable” variable indicates the lowest mean difference of which means equal-independency for the Return to Investment (H02).

Table 5-11. SPSS Sample Test (T-Test) for the Hypothesis based RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Coefficients												
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Partial	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	.457	.185		2.465	.014	.093	.821					
Realestate literacy	.146	.065	.082	2.233	.026	.018	.274	.251	.084	.074	.802	1.247
Financial literacy	.194	.068	.107	2.867	.004	.061	.327	.280	.108	.095	.782	1.278
Investment appetite	.280	.045	.227	6.266	.000	.193	.368	.373	.231	.207	.828	1.207
Crypto favorable	.304	.041	.267	7.344	.000	.222	.385	.399	.268	.243	.826	1.211

a. Dependent Variable: Return_to_invest

5.5.5. Test of Normality (Kolmogorov and Shapiro Wilk-Test)

This PhD thesis delves into the assessment of normality distribution in research data, employing the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. The Test of Normality was firstly mentioned by Shapiro and Wilk (1968) when they have simulated data with a maximum sample of fifty respondents (Shapiro and Wilk and Chen, 1968, pp. 1343–1372). Originating from Shapiro and Wilk's seminal work in 1968, these tests have been instrumental in determining the normality of data sets, with particular importance for small sample sizes. Using SPSS, the thesis analyses the p-values obtained from these tests and evaluates their significance in relation to the alpha level (See table 5-12).

Table 5-12. SPSS Test on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Frequency distribution for uhat4, obs 1-700

number of bins = 27, mean = 1.567e-016, sd = 0.922524

interval	midpt	frequency	rel.	cum.
< -3.1271	-3.2386	1	0.14%	0.14%
-3.1271 - -2.9040	-3.0155	0	0.00%	0.14%
-2.9040 - -2.6810	-2.7925	2	0.29%	0.43%
-2.6810 - -2.4579	-2.5694	6	0.86%	1.29%
-2.4579 - -2.2348	-2.3464	7	1.00%	2.29%
-2.2348 - -2.0118	-2.1233	8	1.14%	3.43%
-2.0118 - -1.7887	-1.9003	14	2.00%	5.43%
-1.7887 - -1.5657	-1.6772	12	1.71%	7.14%
-1.5657 - -1.3426	-1.4542	15	2.14%	9.29%
-1.3426 - -1.1196	-1.2311	15	2.14%	11.43%
-1.1196 - -0.89652	-1.0080	25	3.57%	15.00% *
-0.89652 - -0.67347	-0.78500	29	4.14%	19.14% *
-0.67347 - -0.45041	-0.56194	44	6.29%	25.43% **
-0.45041 - -0.22736	-0.33889	40	5.71%	31.14% **
-0.22736 - -0.0043041	-0.11583	103	14.71%	45.86% *****
-0.0043041 - 0.21875	0.10722	85	12.14%	58.00% ****
0.21875 - 0.44180	0.33028	103	14.71%	72.71% *****
0.44180 - 0.66486	0.55333	50	7.14%	79.86% **
0.66486 - 0.88791	0.77639	39	5.57%	85.43% **
0.88791 - 1.1110	0.99944	38	5.43%	90.86% *
1.1110 - 1.3340	1.2225	26	3.71%	94.57% *
1.3340 - 1.5571	1.4456	17	2.43%	97.00%
1.5571 - 1.7801	1.6686	7	1.00%	98.00%
1.7801 - 2.0032	1.8917	8	1.14%	99.14%
2.0032 - 2.2262	2.1147	2	0.29%	99.43%
2.2262 - 2.4493	2.3378	3	0.43%	99.86%
>= 2.4493	2.5608	1	0.14%	100.00%

Test for null hypothesis of normal distribution:

Chi-square(2) = 33.930 with p-value 0.00000 Source: Gretl

The findings underscore the criticality of adhering to normality assumptions for drawing accurate conclusions from research outcomes. Moreover, the thesis discusses the challenges posed by non-normal distributions, especially in larger sample sizes, and the implications for hypothesis interpretation. In this context, it is SPSS the p-value is represented by a column asymptotic significance and indicates a p value of 0.000 (Sig.) which is less than alpha of 0.05. However, for the sample of 700 respondents, the sample parameters became more restrictive, and the hypothesis is harder to be interpreted rather than the data are normally distributed. Table 5-13 presents the results from two well-known tests of normality, namely the

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test and the Shapiro-Wilk Test. In this context, the table shows that there is no normal distribution of the data.

Table 5-13. SPSS Test on Normality for the RQ2 – Return of tokenized investments.

Frequency distribution for uhat3, obs 1-700
number of bins = 27, mean = 0, sd = 1.53774

interval	midpt	frequency	rel.	cum.
< -3.0641	-3.2147	2	0.29%	0.29%
-3.0641 - -2.7628	-2.9134	8	1.14%	1.43%
-2.7628 - -2.4615	-2.6121	15	2.14%	3.57%
-2.4615 - -2.1602	-2.3108	10	1.43%	5.00%
-2.1602 - -1.8589	-2.0095	37	5.29%	10.29% *
-1.8589 - -1.5576	-1.7083	48	6.86%	17.14% **
-1.5576 - -1.2563	-1.4070	42	6.00%	23.14% **
-1.2563 - -0.95503	-1.1057	38	5.43%	28.57% *
-0.95503 - -0.65374	-0.80439	65	9.29%	37.86% ***
-0.65374 - -0.35246	-0.50310	60	8.57%	46.43% ***
-0.35246 - -0.051167	-0.20181	44	6.29%	52.71% **
-0.051167 - 0.25012	0.099477	48	6.86%	59.57% **
0.25012 - 0.55141	0.40077	44	6.29%	65.86% **
0.55141 - 0.85270	0.70205	42	6.00%	71.86% **
0.85270 - 1.1540	1.0033	44	6.29%	78.14% **
1.1540 - 1.4553	1.3046	32	4.57%	82.71% *
1.4553 - 1.7566	1.6059	22	3.14%	85.86% *
1.7566 - 2.0579	1.9072	17	2.43%	88.29%
2.0579 - 2.3591	2.2085	27	3.86%	92.14% *
2.3591 - 2.6604	2.5098	16	2.29%	94.43%
2.6604 - 2.9617	2.8111	6	0.86%	95.29%
2.9617 - 3.2630	3.1124	13	1.86%	97.14%
3.2630 - 3.5643	3.4137	6	0.86%	98.00%
3.5643 - 3.8656	3.7149	12	1.71%	99.71%
3.8656 - 4.1669	4.0162	1	0.14%	99.86%
4.1669 - 4.4682	4.3175	0	0.00%	99.86%
>= 4.4682	4.6188	1	0.14%	100.00%

Test for null hypothesis of normal distribution:
Chi-square(2) = 36.748 with p-value 0.00000
Source: Gretl

However, the Central limit theorem (see Bárány, Van, 2007) implies that the normal distribution is to be confirmed due to many observations (in this PhD- 700 respondents) which conclude that each observation is being randomly generated and does not depend on the values of the other observations.

5.5.6. Ramsey Regression Specification Test (RESET Test)

This study applies the Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test (RESET) as a diagnostic tool for detecting misspecification in regression models. Introduced by Ramsey in 1969, the RESET test evaluates whether non-linear combinations of explanatory variables adequately explain the dependent variable, thereby identifying potential model misspecification. By analysing the relationship between predictors and fitted values, the test helps researchers determine if important explanatory variables are missing or if there exists a non-linear relationship between variables. The thesis explored the theoretical underpinnings of the RESET test, its practical implementation, and its implications for regression analysis for RQ01 Smart Contract and RQ02 Tokenised Investments (see Table 5-14).

Table 5-14. SPSS Ramsey Regression (RESET test) for the Hypothesis based on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Auxiliary regression for RESET specification test
 OLS, using observations 1-700
 Dependent variable: Main_sec_challenge

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.300017	0.234680	1.278	0.2015
Trust_investment	0.169451	0.0490678	3.453	0.0006 ***
Transparency_role	0.160730	0.0511256	3.144	0.0017 ***
Speed_sc	0.295559	0.0767288	3.852	0.0001 ***
Trad_errors_reso~	0.128563	0.0450706	2.852	0.0045 ***
yhat^2	0.0349550	0.0340454	1.027	0.3049

Test statistic: $F = 1.054147$,

with $p\text{-value} = P(F(1,694) > 1.05415) = 0.305$

The P-Value is large 0.305 (greater than the normal level of significance 0.05).

In this case, the Thesis does not reject the H0 Hypothesis and this indicates no signs of the model misspecification, particularly nonlinearity in the data

Table 5-15.SPSS Ramsey (RESET test) for the Hypothesis based on RQ2 – Return on Investments

Auxiliary regression for RESET specification test
 OLS, using observations 1-700
 Dependent variable: Return_to_invest

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.516313	0.435841	1.185	0.2366
Realestate_litte~	0.136151	0.0926025	1.470	0.1419
Financial_litter~	0.179776	0.116468	1.544	0.1231
Investment_appet~	0.262009	0.130768	2.004	0.0455 **
Crypto_favorable	0.285233	0.129359	2.205	0.0278 **
yhat^2	0.0107725	0.0719448	0.1497	0.8810

Test statistic: $F = 0.022420$,

with $p\text{-value} = P(F(1,694) > 0.0224198) = 0.881$

In this sense, the Ramsey test is suitable for discovery of misspecification (non-linearity) of the data model that is constructed by a polynomial or another non-linear functional form. The Ramsey test proves whether non-linear combinations of the fitted values can explain the dependant variable. Specifically, the idea of the Ramsey test is to provide insights if non-linear combinations of the explanatory variables have any power in explaining the dependent variable. In this PhD Research both RQ01 and RQ02 pass the criteria as the P-Value is very large 0.881 (greater than the normal level of significance 0.05). The reasons for such misspecification can be either missing important explanatory variables or a non-linear relationship between dependent and independent variables. The Ramsey regression test analyses the explanation of the predictors by the fitted values of extended regression model and in the model which indicates about the misspecification and the Null hypothesis (H0) must be accepted (Ramsey, 1969, pp. 350-371). In this case, the Thesis does not reject the H0 Hypothesis, and this indicates no signs of the model misspecification, particularly nonlinearity in the data → Ramsey Test RESET TEST on Linearity is passed.

5.5.7. Multicollinearity Test (Collinearity Matrix and VIF-Test)

This study also tested for multicollinearity (see Table 5-16), a common issue in regression analysis, which arises when independent variables exhibit high correlation with each other. Multicollinearity can distort regression results and undermine the reliability of coefficient estimates. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) serves as a diagnostic tool to assess the severity of multicollinearity in regression models. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) measures the impact of collinearity among the variables in a regression model. Based on the statistical guidelines, the VIF factor should be between the following ranges:

Variance inflation factor (VIF) = $VIF(i) = \frac{1}{1-R_i^2}$

VIF = 1	Not correlated
1 < VIF < 5	Moderately correlated
VIF > 5 to 10	Highly correlated

Table 5-16. SPSS Coefficients Multicollinearity Test for RQ1 – Smart Contract

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations	Zero-order	Partial	Partial	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound					Upper Bound	Tolerance
1 (Constant)	.090	.115		.783	.434	-.135	.315						
Speed_sc	.368	.031	.384	11.903	.000	.307	.428	.647	.412	.306		.634	1.576
Transparency_role	.201	.032	.190	6.239	.000	.138	.265	.515	.230	.160		.714	1.401
Trad_errors_resolved	.159	.034	.152	4.650	.000	.092	.226	.538	.174	.120		.616	1.622
Trust_investment	.207	.033	.204	6.372	.000	.143	.271	.551	.235	.164		.642	1.557

a. Dependent Variable: Main_sec_challenge

For RQ.1, this study measured the impact of collinearity among the following variables such as Speed_sc, Transparency_role, Trad_errors_resolved, Trust_investment. In this thesis, in case of of RQ1 – Smart Contract behaviour VIF 1.576, VIF 1.401, VIF 1.622, VIF 1.557. In this context, the regression analysis shows no multicollinearity which provides reliable empirical results. Multicollinearity Test is passed (see Table 5-17).

Table 5-17. SPSS Coefficients Multicollinearity Test for RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations	Zero-order	Partial	Partial	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound					Upper Bound	Tolerance
1 (Constant)	.457	.185		2.465	.014	.093	.821						
Realestate literacy	.146	.065	.082	2.233	.026	.018	.274	.251	.084	.074		.802	1.247
Financial literacy	.194	.068	.107	2.867	.004	.061	.327	.280	.108	.095		.782	1.278
Investment appetite	.280	.045	.227	6.266	.000	.193	.368	.373	.231	.207		.828	1.207
Crypto favorable	.304	.041	.267	7.344	.000	.222	.385	.399	.268	.243		.826	1.211

a. Dependent Variable: Return_to_invest

Source: SPSS and Excel Calculation of Customer Survey Data

For RQ.2 Tokenised Investments, the thesis measured the impact of collinearity among the following variables such as Realestate_literacy, Financial_literacy, Investment_appetite, and Crypto_favorable. In the case of RQ.2- Crypto-Investment degree, VIF 1.247, VIF 1.278, VIF 1.207, VIF 1.211. In this context, the regression analysis shows no multicollinearity which

provides reliable empirical results. Multicollinearity Test is passed.

5.5.8. Heteroscedasticity /- Homoscedasticity Test (Breusch Pagan Test)

This study also tested for the presence of heteroscedasticity in regression models using the Breusch-Pagan test (see Table 5-18 and 5-19). Heteroscedasticity refers to the violation of the assumption of constant variance of residuals in regression analysis, which can lead to biased parameter estimates and incorrect inference. For this reason, the Breusch-Pagan is used to diagnosis heteroscedasticity, assuming normally distributed residuals. The Breusch-Pagan test is applied to test the Heteroscedasticity /- Homoscedasticity relation and assumes the residuals to be normally distributed in accordance with Hayes (2007).

Table 5-18. SPSS Coefficients Heteroscedasticity for the RQ1 – Smart Contract

Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity^{a,b,c}

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
1.414	1	.234

a. Dependent variable: Main_sec_challenge
 b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
 c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + Speed_sc + Transparency_role + Trad_errors_resolved + Trust_investment

Table 5-19. SPSS Coefficients Heteroscedasticity for the RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity^{a,b,c}

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
3.913	1	.048

a. Dependent variable: Return_to_invest
 b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
 c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + Realestate_litteracy + Financial_litteracy + Investment_appetite + Crypto_favorable

By using survey data analysis, the thesis demonstrated how the Breusch-Pagan calculated test statistics and p-values exceeding the significance level, the thesis concluded that heteroscedasticity is not present, and homoscedasticity can be assumed. The results of the Breusch Pagan test 0.234 and 0.048 is higher than Sig of 0.05 (our P Values). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) indicates that heteroscedasticity presence is to be rejected, and homoscedasticity is to be accepted. The data is distributed in a homoscedastic manner which indicates a statistically significant result → Breusch-Pagan test is passed.

5.5.9. Autocorrelation Test (Durbin-Watson Test)

The main drawback of the Breusch-Pagan test is that the residuals of the origin regression must be normally distributed. This study tested for the detection of autocorrelation in regression analysis using the Durbin-Watson (DW) test and the Dickey-Fuller test (see Table 5-20). The Autocorrelation, a common issue in regression analysis, arises when errors in a regression model are correlated with each other over time or across observations. The DW test assesses autocorrelation in the residuals of a regression model based on the least squares method, while the Dickey-Fuller test is applied in time series analysis to detect autocorrelation in non-stationary data. The thesis investigates the theoretical foundations of these tests, their application in regression analysis, and their implications for interpreting regression results. The Autocorrelation can be measured with Durbin Watson Test (Least Square Method) and Dickie Fuller Tests (Time Series analysis). Durbin Watson (DW) investigates autocorrelation coefficients and can be measured by the distance between the positive and negative series of data points of the linear equation based on the least square model and indicates the closeness of the randomly distributed points to the linear trend equation (Durbin and Watson, 1950, pp. 409-428). Generally: $DW = 0, r = 1$, the DW assumes perfectly positive autocorrelation, $DW < 2, r = 0.$, $DW > 4, r = -1$ = the DW assumes perfectly negative autocorrelation.

Table 5-20. SPSS Autocorrelation Test for the Hypothesis based on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Model Summary ^b					Change Statistics					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
1	.735 ^a	.541	.538	.92252	.541	204.664	4	695	.000	1.983

a. Predictors: (Constant), Trust investment, Transparency role, Speed sc, Trad errors resolved
 b. Dependent Variable: Main_sec_challenge

Autocorrelations can either be done on neighboring residuals (autocorrelation first order) or even with "distant" With autocorrelation, the correlation between two consecutive Residual sizes denoted. The Durbin-Watson tests the first-order autocorrelation by using the Comparing residuals of two neighbouring observations u_t and u_{t-1} (r here denotes the correlation of two neighbouring residuals): The null hypothesis is: There is no first-order autocorrelation. Low values of DW therefore indicate positive autocorrelation (see Table 5-21).

Table 5-21. SPSS Autocorrelation Test for the Hypothesis based on RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investents

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.492 ^a	.242	.237	1.53774	.242	55.405	4	6	.000	1.958

a. Predictors: (Constant), Crypto_favorable, Realestate_literacy, Investment_appetite, Financial_literacy

b. Dependent Variable: Return_to_invest

Source: SPSS and Excel Calculation of Customer Survey Data

The effect of Autocorrelation typically occurs when a relevant regressor is not considered in the model (mis-specification), the functional form of a regressor is specified incorrectly (nonlinearity), the dependent variable is autocorrelated in a way that is determined by the systematic part of the model is not adequately represented. The case for Autocorrelation is often associated with longitudinal market regression with capital market data but it is also spatial autocorrelation in cross-sectional data possible.

In this study, the survey was performed only once at the time of the online survey without the time jumps which might potentially lead in residuals to a large DW coefficient for the Commercial Real estate transaction RQ.1 smart contract and RQ.2 tokenised investments which is equal to 1.983 and 1.1958 and indicates no autocorrelation → Autocorrelation Test is passed.

5.5.10. Residuals Statistics

Previous tests have analysed the regression implications of these findings, along with the limitations of the Breusch-Pagan test and which requires also to validate the importance of normally distributed residuals statistics. This study investigated the validation of model assumptions in regression analysis, focusing on normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, and independence of residuals (see Table 5-22). Residuals, defined as the differences between observed and predicted responses, are analysed to assess whether these assumptions are met. The remaining output is concerned with checking the model assumptions of normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and independence of the residuals. Residuals are the differences between the observed and predicted responses.

Table 5-22. SPSS analysis of Residual Statistics for the Hypothesis based on RQ1 – Smart Contract

Residuals Statistics ^a					
Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	

Predicted Value	1.0248	4.7650	3.0986	.99837	700
Residual	-3.23860	2.56082	.00000	.91988	700
Std. Predicted Value	-2.077	1.669	.000	1.000	700
Std. Residual	-3.511	2.776	.000	.997	700

a. Dependent Variable: Main_sec_challenge

Table 38 SPSS analysis of Residual Statistics for the Hypothesis based on RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.3812	5.0405	3.0600	.86586	700
Residual	-3.21470	4.61881	.00000	1.53333	700
Std. Predicted Value	-1.939	2.287	.000	1.000	700
Std. Residual	-2.091	3.004	.000	.997	700

a. Dependent Variable: Return_to_invest

Source: Field research- Customer Survey Data

The above table summarises the predicted values and residuals in unstandardised and standardised forms. It is usual practice to consider standardised residuals due to their ease of interpretation. For instance, outliers (observations that do not appear to fit the model that well) can be identified as those observations with standardised residual values above 3 (or less than -3). From the above we can see that we do not appear to have any outliers. Finally, the thesis emphasized the importance of checking residual scatterplots to evaluate the distribution, linearity, and variance of residuals around predicted responses. Through visual inspection and statistical tests, the thesis aims to validate the significance of normally distributed residuals and to ensure the robustness of regression models. The previous section of the “Residual Statistics” shows the residual distribution, however, it does not show the form of the distribution (e.g. normality, linearity and homoscedasticity). Consequently, this study endeavours deep analytics on validating model assumptions in regression analysis through residual analysis techniques. The three main assumptions of normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity are examined to ensure the robustness of regression models. Residuals, defined as the differences between observed and predicted responses, are analysed using histograms and scatterplots to assess these assumptions.

Histogram

The thesis emphasizes the importance of symmetry in residual distributions for normality, the presence of a straight-line relationship for linearity, and consistent variance across predicted responses for homoscedasticity. Through visual inspection and statistical tests, the thesis aims to provide insights into the validity of model assumptions and their implications for regression analysis. The histogram (Figure 5-5) shows the frequencies / probability per expression of a continuous variable and allows to check potential asymmetries in the distribution of the residuals whereby the symmetry tends to indicate a normal distribution.

Figure 5-4.SPSS analysis of Histogram for the RQ1 – Smart Contract

Figure 5-5 is a check on normality - the histogram shows a normal distribution.

In a population with a mean of 0, possible samples are scattered. A difference of 3 is very rare per illustration. Finally, the plot of the standardised residuals versus predicted Y customer behaviour. The pattern shown in Figure 5-6 indicates that there are no problems with the assumption that the residuals are normally distributed at each level of Y and constant in variance across levels of Y.

Figure 5-5. SPSS analysis of Histogram for the RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Source: SPSS and Excel Calculation of Customer Survey Data

Scatterplot

This study investigated the linearity assumption in regression analysis through scatterplot analysis of residuals. The relationship between standardized predicted values and standardized residuals is examined to assess the linearity of the regression model. In this study, the scatterplots (see Figures 5-7, 5-8) show a constant relationship of residuals between standardized predicted value and standardized residual by checking the relationship on linearity assumptions. The points should have the same dispersion about this line over the predicted value range. In this sense, the thesis emphasizes the importance of consistent dispersion of residuals around the zero line across the range of predicted values. Through visual inspection and interpretation of scatterplots, it shows that tokenised investments have a constant validity of the linearity factors assumption and its implications for regression analysis.

Figure 5-6. SPSS analysis of Scatterplot for the RQ1 – Smart Contract

Figure 5-7.SPSS analysis of Scatterplot for the RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Source: SPSS and Excel Calculation of Customer Survey Data

Subsequently, this study explored the assessment of normality and homoscedasticity in regression analysis through the regression of standardized residuals. The plot serves as a diagnostic tool to examine the relationship between residuals and predicted values, providing insights into the assumptions of linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity. Through visual inspection and interpretation of the plot, the thesis aims to identify patterns and deviations from these assumptions, and their implications for the validity of the regression model.

Normality: The regression of standardised residuals (see Figures 5-9, 5-10) show a plot is a check on normality and homoscedasticity. Therefore, we can see a clear relationship between the residuals and the predicted values which is not consistent with the assumption of linearity. The dispersion of residuals over the predicted value range between -1 and 1 looks constant, for predicted values below -1 there is too few points to provide evidence against a change in variability.

Figure 5-8. Regression Standardized Residual for the RQ1 – Smart Contract

Source: SPSS and Excel Calculation of Customer Survey Data

Figure 5-9. Regression Standardized Residual for the RQ2 – Return of tokenized Investments

Finally, the results and findings of the Residual statistics are clearly interpreted from both points normality homoscedasticity. By analysing the plotted points and their relationship to the diagonal line, the thesis assesses whether the residuals are normally

distributed about the predicted responses and whether the variance of the residuals is consistent across predicted responses. Through visual inspection and interpretation, the thesis aims to provide evidence supporting the validity of these assumptions in regression models.

6. DISCUSSION, CONTRIBUTION, LIMITATIONS, FUTURE

This ADSR study developed a class of problems which adds depth and understanding of the research validity where the prototype triangulating, the global survey participants are asked to pragmatically validate the proposed model shopping mall on real estate smart contract ERC777 for the purpose of the empirical data analysis. Key results and findings of the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) and Prototype development (Research Artefact 2) were presented. Reflections on the implications to distil learnings for a digitally transformed commercial real estate transaction process of intermediaries. The study answers the hypothesis of previous research questions – such as human interactions by novel, mathematical algorithms based on Ethereum blockchain technology (Research Question 1) and identifies customer behaviour for the crypto investments based on the supporting evidence from the market survey (Research Question 2).

Finally, the empirical process, the data insights provide a foundation for future research on commercial real estate. It also contributes to the knowledge base for research and the practice of the real estate sector. In this context, the thesis starts with the identification of current problems in commercial real estate (relevance) and provides both Artefacts, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) and the Prototype development (Research Artefact 2), to contribute to the further advancement of the academic debate. Albeit this practical starting point, the thesis is following the standards and norms of scientific research (rigor) specifically reflected in the ADSR approach. In the frame of the selection of the tailored methodology, in behavioural science, methodologies are typically rooted in data collection and empirical analysis techniques. Rigorous evaluation methods are extremely difficult to apply in design-science research (Zelkowitz and Wallace, 1998). For example, the use of a design Artefact on a single project may not generalise to different environments (Markus, Majchrzak and Gasser, 2002). Concretely, the Chapter 6 selects ADSR approach due to on the one hand, the Relevancy principle (1) is achieved when the thesis set out the objective of design-science research and aim of developing a technology-based solution to important and relevant business problems such as traditional commercial real estate market where the digital innovation process is inevitable fact. On the other hand, the principle of rigor (2) is achieved by appropriately applying existing foundations and methodologies.

6.1. Reflections on the ADSR Study

6.1.1. Explaining the problem existence and significance towards motivation to identify the research problem and specify old design Status Quo (AS-IS) on behalf of the thematic and systematic literature review and to distil a prior design (Pre-Design).

In the context of the Conceptual Model, the thesis identified that the traditional Real estate model has been outdated, and the technology innovation is inevitable factor when it comes to establishing secured and compliant modern commercial real estate transactions in an economically and timely interesting way.

1. Problem of established obsolete business models due to rise of blockchain technology and decentralised technology.
2. Problem of asymmetric information – hidden information problem of separate ledgers record keeping.
3. Problem of errors due to the practice of paper-based recording.
4. Problem of high-cost administrative burden for property transactions.
5. Problem of legal barriers towards market regulation.

These problems have been analysed during the diagnosis phase, i.e. the background and systematic literature review and to address the research gaps. For the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), the four previously identified research gaps need to be revisited: First, the rise of bitcoin brought first ideas on blockchain in 2008 when a group of programmers known under the name of Satoshi Nakamoto presented the idea of P-2-P Electronic system (Zoli lo Prinzi, 2017) and (Paesani, 2020). Since the publication of Satoshi Nakamoto (2008), the revolution of Bitcoin and blockchain, has recently emerged as a disruptive innovation with a wide range of applications, potentially able to redesign established real estate business models by means of decentralised technology which can manage social interactions of the real estate stakeholders and dismiss traditional central authorities. More than ten years have passed since Nakamoto's Bitcoin Whitepaper (2008) and the blockchain technology for real estate transaction purpose (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019; Konashevych, 2020c), whereby blockchain technology bring added value for commercial real estate contract by faster delivery at a lower cost to ensure an autonomous and "once consensus-achieved" accounting of bitcoin transactions performed on the decentralised database.

During the diagnosis phase, the literature review identified four key topics that are in the focus of the academic debate around the acquisition process in commercial real estate. These are

(1) Technology, (2) real estate Process (3) transaction costs, and (4) legal aspects. These were used as a basis for the questions asked in the qualitative data collection during the design phase to verify the literature diagnosis assumptions with regards to their relevance and topicality for business practice. Most of the key literature points are verified by the experts, however some new, additional aspects are discovered during the carrying out of qualitative content analysis such as (1) adoption 2) process, (3) transaction costs, (4) governance and compliance (5) security and trust and (6) skills.

6.1.2. Identifying the key design principles by conducting qualitative expert semi-structured interviews and map the factors into the conceptual model “building blocks”.

Adoption: The real estate adoption transformation started with the new era of publications (Firica, 2017; Swan, 2018) where companies and business environment were challenged by a disruptive technology of the blockchain technology. The adoption cycle started with the definition of the blockchain technology and specific applications that highlight the potential economic benefits of digital ledgers such as digital asset registries, blockchains as leapfrog technology for global financial inclusion, long-tail personalised economic services, and net settlement payment channels. According to Swan (2018), the economic benefits of blockchain distributed ledgers technology (DLT) outweigh the potential risks, since the day-to-day business relies more and more on the digital coins (e.g. Bitcoin, Ethereum), crypto-assets, decentralised finance via blockchain-based distributed network ledgers with cryptographic security of the DLT technology and ability to distribute efficiently an asset to multiple parties as mentioned by (Firica, 2017) and (Swan, 2018)). In this context, the literature review shed light on the adoption of the logistics of end-to-end blockchain enabled supply chain process of the real estate logistics services instead of simple real estate leasing by (Li, Shen and Huang, 2019).

First, the adoption factor is a fundamental baseline factor and explains the key findings and contributions to knowledge of this thesis and considers the technological inevitability of the blockchain technology in general and applies the DLT to resolve the problem statement of the research. Specifically, the researcher adopts smart contract on the blockchain technology for the real estate old-fashioned centralised transaction process and finds an innovative approach of the decentralised technology which ensures the immutable block registration resulting into the unique agreement fulfilment and increases trust, which, in turn results into digital asset registries (Swan, 2018) and more efficient contract execution, because it makes transactions safer, more transparent, traceable and efficient (Aste, Tasca and Di Matteo, 2017), (Kshetri,

2018) as shown in the South African example where real estate investment trusts are examined for adoption of legislation on firm growth and firm value (Carstens and Wesson, 2019).

When both of the party's buyer or seller of the property enter into the encoded smart contract, they automatically are exposed to legal binding terms and conditions of the property contract and creates new trust opportunities for the socially handicapped audience in order to provide services to persons with severe disabilities such features such as contract settlement, legal and tax facilitation (Morena *et al.*, 2020) and generates higher credibility for the seller or buyer trust due to decentralised ledger technology (Blockchain) supply chain traceability (Biswas, Muthukkumarasamy and Lum, 2017).

Second, the cumbersome real estate contract imposed an adoption problem when it comes to the asymmetric information and intended to digitally facilitate, verify, or enforce the negotiation or performance of a contract application (Vidhyalakshmi, Geetha and Sobitha Ahila, 2019). A large scale study of traditional real estate purchasing process in South Africa showed evidence of inefficiency due to heavy reliance on multiple third parties due to the fact that technology is an inevitable fact and a "game-changer" which replaces the human-based process reliance on third parties and manual processes by a predefined algorithmic blockchain-based transactions by providing more data stability, security, immutability of each transaction block and efficiency gains for the Real estate (Krupa and Akhil, 2019). According to Vidhyalakshmi, Geetha and Sobitha Ahila (2019), the smart contract is able to enforce the conditions of a real estate contract digitally with no middleman required. the smart contract of the real estate property consists of rules, list of participating entities, and generates a transaction which is designed to resolve the problem of decentralised property record keeping by codification potentials of blockchain technology as provided on the employees impact study by (Peisl and Shah, 2019).

The global real estate market developments are accompanied by the rapid technological shifts in the core of the real estate models and old paper-based contracts get obsolete. in this context, the new transaction process of an office building is technological possible to conduct a smart contract, improve data quality, create market transparency as shown on the Netherlands example by Wouda and Opdenakker (2019) or save time by multiple process steps as shown by (Thota, 2019).

The adoption of blockchain technology for the real estate market comes into applicational use case due to inability of the current system to connect stakeholders such as buyers, tenants,

owners, and investors the current cumbersome human-based system (Latifi, Zhang and Cheng, 2019). A study by Latifi et al (2019) focused on the employment of blockchain in Real estate market that this is possible to provide liquidity remove middlemen and provide the liquidity (Zhang and Li, 2021) and the linkage to the real estate market (Latifi, Zhang and Cheng, 2019). The new adoption is characterised by a digital adoption where each user (buyer or seller) can send his crypto cash through a smart contract which access the user input address (user wallet account) and the transaction rate (e.g. Ethereum Gas Fee). The system then updates the accrued balance, generates the rate of interest for each member. In this manner, adoption is an important parameter that really affect, how such blockchain based systems are be implemented within the blockchain technology revolution which is based on smart contract prerequisites such as decentralisation, transparency and immutability making the logistics of the real estate process more robust compared to the traditional paper-based human acted process as mentioned by (Mehendale, Masurekar and Patil, 2019). However, certain risks remain persistent such as market risk of platform failure, credit risk of default or liquidity (Giri and Manohar, 2023) or a recent social study on the factors influencing the decision to adopt the blockchain technology in real estate transactions in Kosovo (Hoxha and Sadiku, 2019). The redesign of the old Real estate process demonstrates that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract. The conceptual model (artefact 1) identifies the potential for a higher auditability, immutability and transparency where specific assets mistakes will be encoded on the smart contract and decrease the chance of mistake from paper-based recording practice by increasing the quality of the data. In this manner, the smart contracts address asymmetric information through automation, transparency and security that underpin the symmetry in the consensus between parties in the process. Finally, the adoption of smart contract decreases the risk of interpreting contractual conditions to one's benefit of buyer or seller by assuring the trust and long-term relation. Moreover, in case of a breach, the property data can be compared in line with the immutable blockchain smart contract original protocol and the algorithms can be tampered through privacy breaches and can also be set to automatically oblige the party responsible for the breach to pay penalties which can serve as a further buyer or seller protection as mentioned (Kumar, Talasila and Pasumarthy, 2021).

Process: According Hoxha (Hoxha and Sadiku, 2019), the traditional real estate purchasing process has been described as inefficient and identified inflexibility and process human actions prone to errors and posed certain risks as due to extensive manual review and verification of financial and legal documents as well as manually updating multiple systems with redundant information or heavy reliance on multiple third parties which results in high transaction cost.

Those transaction costs account for a significant proportion of each new or refurbished facility at least 50 % and could be reduced by eliminating the need for intermediaries to build trust as a prerequisite for successfully executed agreements on the decentralised algorithmic protocol as mentioned by (Dakhli, Lafhaj and Mossman, 2019). Krupa and Akhil, (2019) highlight that the current real estate transaction process is characterised by cumbersome roadblocks of the transaction process between the seller and buyer in terms of asymmetric information, imperfect market knowledge, complex regulations which makes the commercial real estate process inefficient, in transparent, non-inclusive, prone to errors resulting into high transaction costs. In contrast to the status quo process old-fashioned transaction process, the new process contributes to the main findings of Thota (2019), commercial real estate workflow (Wouda and Opendakker, 2019) and process for the land registry (Konashevych, 2021).

Looking at these above-mentioned process models, one aspect that seems to be surprisingly often overlooked is the combination of business concept, implementation and practical applicability of the blockchain technology in the real estate industry. In this thesis, the blockchain technology generates a novel process solution including the implementation and finds a practical implication in the real estate industry at Steiner AG in Switzerland as a Prototype to ensure a simplified asset buy/sale Real estate process with fewer and lower transaction fees. The simplified smart contract without intermediaries allows the realisation of simplified administrative process compared to existing term-securitisation schemes (Thota, 2019) or recent research from real estate tokenised property process (Konashevych, 2020c). In this context, the research papers of Thota (2019) process steps model, Wouda 2019 (smart contract office building) and Konashevych 2020 (real estate tokens) build the fundamental for the redesigned process of the commercial real estate smart contract of this thesis and contributes to the thesis Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), by applying the standard smart contract ERC 777 and adding the extra component of the KYC/AML for the investor protection based on ERC 777 on Github (Dafflon, 2024).

The new process of the enhanced smart contract ERC 777 Github (Dafflon, 2024) provides a new perspective in this thesis which is based on the blockchain technology to represent real estate tokens based on the fundamental model from Konashevych technological token concept (Konashevych, 2020c). The real estate tokens concept is a technological concept which is similar to the legal concept of titles, because it provides for evidence of ownership and can be transferred from one address to another, while giving exclusive access to such an address to the owner (Konashevych, 2020c).

The real estate tokenised property approach was developed during the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) which allows to build up a lean process of P2P interactions of tokenised pool of properties where third party intermediaries are eliminated (“cut the middleman”) by the algorithmic mechanism of smart contract. The smart contract on the blockchain technology could reduce the odds of mortgage fraud, enable a simple transaction process, help with traceability of the servicing process by tracking payments, enables the transparency on the secondary market, where commercial is packaged into security backed assets (Security asset tokenisation). Finally, blockchain technology foster innovation for new business models for the real estate due to commodification of business models in the real estate market and would see lower transaction costs closing costs. The blockchain-based process of the smart contract allows to automatically and securely execute transactions of a commercial real estate contract global wide without the support of a centralised execution authority as mentioned by (Abdelhamid and Hassan, 2019). Empirical evidence provided by Montgomery et al., (2018) showed a big potential of process redesign and Blockchain Technology within the real estate crowdfunding models (RECF) in the real estate finance industry, assessing whether RECF constitutes a potentially disruptive innovation to the real estate finance industry. The study provided supporting evidence for a process improvements, higher accessibility and affordability of real estate finance, thereby helping to address the problem of shortage of real estate project finance. The thesis reflects on the RECF and enhanced the original idea of the smart contract by the extension of the tokenised investment platform and provides scientific progress in the real estate project finance (Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018)

In this new process model of the enhanced smart contract ERC 777 (Github, 2021), the process starts with a public open property marketplace, where the Buyer and the Seller have both user IDs at the portal marketplace where verified information about the property is available to everyone transparently, including owners’ details, geo-location, chain of custody, the area covered. The marketplace is integrated with the government systems and land registries to ensure the authenticity of the asset information. Second, the identity verification step is performed where the smart contract ensures that verification solution is integrated with the marketplace based on the KYC/AML protocol. Blockchain technology facilitates the involvement of third-party verification companies, government agencies, banks, investors and validate the information on the public ledger (e.g. Ethereum public protocol)

Third, the contract agreement is executed on the blockchain technology, which allows to save all terms and conditions of the contract agreement in the smart contract by using the algorithmic functions (ERC720). As a result, the immutable block is securely saved on the

chain and generates a direct contact between buyer and seller which is backed by an immutable block on the blockchain as a trusted time-stamped signature and serves a proof of the transaction and pre-requisite for the ownership transfer (e.g. Ethereum Community). Once the contract agreement has been set on the smart contract, the operational process and cash management process is ensured by the usage of the shared blockchain technology infrastructure network and replace separate ledgers of between buyer, seller, municipality, notary, land registry create redundancies in operational asset maintained. The blockchain technology allows to transfer all the required automatic payments via the smart contract and use the “get balance” functions to debit or credited in the respective Ethereum wallet accounts. Finally, all the data is be recorded on blockchain with the time-stamp and can be utilised for real-time data based on ERC 777 on Github (Dafflon, 2024).

This is a new innovative process approach for commercial real estate contracts where the fractioned tokens could be collected globally to finance diversified project portfolio investment which is evidence for disruptive innovation to the real estate industry.

Real Estate Business Model (Canvas) / Transaction Costs

Modern business models of real estate offer a huge value proposition in terms of economics models such as crypto-currencies economies of scale for the crypto-currencies, new the DLT Tokenomics (Ducrée *et al.*, 2021) and transformation of Business Model through Blockchain Technology as mentioned by (Chowdhury, 2019). Concretely for this PhD, the “Osterwald Pigneur metrics (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013) summarised the measurement scale and extended by (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019) who tested the metrics of the blockchain technology success based on the collected development start-ups in Europe, North America, and South Africa via public information from the startup firms’ websites, as well as news articles, press releases, and other sources.

The conceptual model (Research Artefact 1) of the thesis contributes to the academic debate by consolidating previous research on the generic business model Canvas Morkunas and Osterwalder (2019) in the context of novel approaches for Commercial real estate. It provides a comprehensive framework of the interdependence of the following canvas factors such as key partnerships (1), key customer segments/ distribution channels (2), efficient usage of resources/activities (3), new revenue opportunities (4) and optimised cost structures (5) where, the factors can be interconnected and especially impact on the transaction cost structure.

Within the business model canvas for real estate, this thesis contributes especially to the cards transaction costs key partnerships, key resources, new customer segments, revenue streams and transaction costs. In the context of the conceptual model (Research Artefact 1), the thesis provides a new perspective on the new customer segments. The unique feature of blockchain technology is a P2P network which helps to find new customers and access a new customer segment which was not possible earlier and as result to generate new business with potential network clients and suppliers (Larios-Hernández, 2017). On the one hand, the key partnerships are defined as “the network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013), p.38), it is about the relations between the suppliers and partners such as strategic alliances, joint ventures, or buyer-supplier relationships to ensure reliable supplies. On the other hand, Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013, p. 20) highlight the necessity for the key customer segments and distribution channels as “the different groups of people or organisations that an enterprise aims to reach and serve.” The key customer channels building block “describes how a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013, p. 26). Furthermore, Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013, p. 34) define key resources as “the most important assets required to make a business model work.” According to Morkunas (2019), (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019), the resources have the nature of financial, material, intellectual, or human and are essential to build a business value proposition.

As a result, blockchain technology allows to create P2P key partnerships for business network where customers could operate on the blockchain platform to buy or sell real estate and could already gain from the blockchain technology by testing pilot projects to purchase or sell homes powered by Chroma Way in Sweden or Crowdhouse in Switzerland (Morkunas, 2019, p. 298), (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019). Previous real estate models included various roadblocks such as high market barriers to enter the market, which was not attractive to investors before the blockchain technology. Through simplification of P2P key partnerships on the blockchain technology, the new distribution channels for the token holders are generated, which are established by the decentralized storage of the blockchain technology.

As part of the systematic literature review (SLR), the thesis identified two key factors out of the business model canvas for real estate, which contributes especially to the cards revenue and transaction costs and build the biggest potential categories for the real estate smart contract commercial exploitation (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019). In the thesis conceptual model (Research Artefact 1), the revenue streams have been adopted and additionally the focus on the global revenue streams has been added. Concretely, the real estate commercial contract

is provided on the marketplace to a buyer or seller which generate new values streams enabled by the blockchain technology from one-time payments and recurring revenues resulting from ongoing payments or even post-purchase customer support.

According to Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013), the idea of the new revenue streams is such as initial coin offerings and respective tokens. Initially, blockchain tokens could be described as 'digital coin shares' and is subject to a different character such as currencies, securities, utilities, properties, loyalty points, and gift certificates (Buterin, 2015). Furthermore, the tokens could be exchanged – buy and sell on the common platform between parties without the involvement of a central authority and can be traded globally on the digital crypto-currency platforms (Chen, 2021; 2019). In accordance with the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), the most viable factor which contributes to the findings of (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019) are the optimised cost structures and savings of the transaction costs.

Following Morkuna's (2019) specific application of blockchain technology could reduce transaction costs such as negotiation costs and search costs and eliminate the costs of intermediaries. While the blockchain architecture demonstrates various use cases for the financial services industry, the innovation of the smart contract on Ethereum provides a unique opportunity of the traditional real estate market by introducing an almost fully liquid real estate investment product that has significantly cheaper entry and operational costs as previously mentioned by (Firica, 2017). Furthermore, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) includes the argument of economy of scale (Montecchi, Plangger and Etter, 2019), which could be achieved if the fix costs will be reduced by deploying multiple stakeholders on the sharing infrastructure. The transaction cost savings are achieved by removing the requirements for time and personnel required to complete a validity check or a transaction. The thesis demonstrates a smart contract on the Ethereum blockchain technology permission less access of all the stakeholders which allows additional synergies by sharing common code of the Ethereum Github community (e.g. Smart Contract ERC 777). This provides evidence of how the decentralised blockchain network could entail the disintermediation of traditional intermediaries (e.g. banks, notaries, currency exchanges, land registry, municipal bank).

Additionally, the use of blockchain can also enable the addition of new partners in commercial real estate such as technology companies that develop application programming interfaces (APIs) and software development kits (SDKs), and maintain the transactional algorithms, therefore strengthening and extending supply chains– in this instance, the real estate supply chain (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019).

The conceptual model (Research Artefact 1) demonstrates a clear argument of the redesign of the decentralised smart real estate contract which gives the potential to reduce the transaction costs by omitting the redundancy skills of the so called 'middleman' stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring direct interaction between buyer/borrower and seller.

Finally, blockchain technology offers new opportunities of the smart contract to self-execute and eliminate the problem of intermediary third-party middleman which would eliminate the redundancies and require less transaction costs. The existing system consists of employing a broker or a middleman to perform transaction of assets. The solution of the conceptual model (Research Artefact 1) lies in the help of smart contracts, a "computerised transaction protocol that executes the terms of a contract", the smart contract is able to enforce the conditions of a contract digitally with no middleman required (Kumar et al., 2020; Vidhyalakshmi, Geetha and Sobitha Ahila, 2019; Vidhyalakshmi and Geetha, 2019, p. 616). This was also supported by the statement of the interviewees who made a compelling case that costs are very important in respect to Ethereum transactions. There is a large consensus amongst experts that cost is in practice lower in blockchain based transactions than in real world processes. The smart contract for the real estate provides lower transaction costs to revolutionise the real estate market.

Governance and Compliance

A pioneer of the legal aspect of recording property titles on blockchain technology was the Spielman (2016) who compared the benefits and limitations of a blockchain with those of the current paper-based record keeping system. While the previous discussion/ reflection of the papers resulted in the simplified model on the blockchain technology by Thota (2019) and blockchain metrics by Morkunas, Paschen and Boon (2019) derived from Osterwalder and Pigneur (2013) the governance and compliance interviews mentioned the blockchain technology functionality to cover the governance dimension to manage a complex governance processes with gatekeepers, votes and escrow accounts. Respondents shared that a project needs to gain speed in the market, it will need to have the support of an appropriate legal framework. The governance and compliance allow to perform asset sale including the authorised address in the KYC and AML contract even if buying for another Smart Contract account and implemented at low costs.

On the one hand, the Governance/ Compliance (KYC/AML) brings the new dimension of the revolutionary topics of the Smart contract utilisation for the cybersecurity, Internet of Things

(IoT), where the Minimum investment amount is always dictated by KYC costs Cloud Storage as provided by (Yeasmin and Baig, 2019). The KYC/AML on the blockchain technology revolutionised the world of traditional governance/ compliance and brings the new component of algorithm-based security based on the public smart contract (e.g. ERC 777 protocol). The public or permissionless smart contract leads to publicly accessible registries such as facilitating access to land information, improving effectiveness of land registration sector and even introducing possibilities to dispose of the ownership of land electronically by developing electronic conveyancing mechanisms (Kaczorowska, 2019) The KYC/AML procedures allow the authorization, tracking and ban of Ethereum Accounts on our platform and from our investment proposal.

On the other hand, the thesis reflected Governance/ Compliance (KYC/AML) on the use of a securitised investment note, the tokenisation platform allows to conduct a regulated and real estate backed asset-token smart contract. The token will be available to any eligible crypto investor, using an Ethereum ERC 777 protocol-based token, tradable for and with existing tokens and cryptocurrencies. prolonging of the time in which property transactions are completed in, prone to error and fraudulent activities. Blockchain technology presents an opportunity for the real estate sector as it has the potential to bring about more efficiency and reduce reliance on third parties and manual processes (Tilbury, De La Rey and Van Der Schyff, 2019). Finally, related to the above points of governance /compliance regarding the cybersecurity Yeasmin and Baig (2019) and regulated real-estate backed asset-token (Tilbury, De La Rey and Van Der Schyff, 2019) the new perspective is extended by the Ethereum ERC 777 protocol for the token distribution is adopted from and extended of the tokenized property pool (Konashevych, 2020a).

In this thesis, the tokenised property pool adds additionally the use of a securitised investment note, which allows the tokenisation platform to be synchronised with the regulatory authority and backed by real estate security title right. The tokenised property pool is any eligible crypto investor, using an Ethereum ERC777 based token, tradable for and with existing tokens and cryptocurrencies. Due to the unique and revolutionary use of the blockchain technology, the smart contract disrupts the traditional real estate market by introducing an almost fully liquid real estate investment product that has significantly cheaper entry and operational costs depending on various transfers types (title deeds, smart contracts with property rights, etc.) and eventually deactivating the token in case if it ceases to represent any value (Konashevych, 2020c).

In this context, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) contributes to the findings of Konashevych (2020a; 2020b; 2020c) adds scientific progress by a practical case for the commercial real estate processes which is encoded as an ERC777 smart contract on Ethereum and lead to the reduction of transaction costs. Concretely, the asset price was fragmented into tokens of the quotation 1CHF = 1 Token and allowed to perform cost-efficient marketing and attract global revenue streams. Based on Steiner AG Prototype asset ACCAS commercial property mall, the transaction costs were significantly reduced making a use case to an international use case in the commercial real estate. However, recording transactions on the blockchain will depend on the notarised legal acts and regulation in the future by a larger and deeper change in Swiss regulations of FINMA (FINMA, 2021, see chapter Limitations).

In the thesis Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), the governance and compliance factors have been adopted and additionally the focus on the KYC and AML approaches have been added. The real estate commercial contract is provided on the marketplace by a security token offering which is backed by the algorithmic KYC/AML consensus mechanism by the Property DNA and follow back to the immutable and time-stamp authenticated block either to the original ownership token holder or the secondary market transactions where each buyer/seller/investor must undergo the KYC/AML procedure before the transaction process.

This study uses the KYC mechanism for tokens transferred to wallets of customers inside and outside of the whitelist which are permissioned to access the financial services (ex. voting, liquidation, returns, etc.) provided by Smart Contract ERC777 subroutines. All the investors (token holders) are subject to KYC and AML screening, in accordance with relevant FINMA regulations. Consequently, the token holders can only access, purchase and sell the token if they adhere to the KYC and AML requirements as set forth by regulations and the company policy. Not adhering to these requirements prohibits legitimate access to ownership of the token and its financial benefits, including that of the usufruct of the asset underlying it. The asset transaction process is connected to the Smart contract authorising sales of the token after successful test of the KYC/AML. Upon receipt of funds, it will perform the necessary checks to determine if the account is authorised. (KYC- Know Your Customer) and fulfils with the legal requirements of the AML laws to ensure compliance (Konashevych, 2020a, 2020c).

In this context, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) contributes to the digital governance and compliance (KYC/AML) of (Konashevych, 2020; 2020a; 2020c) which is enhanced with a new set of smart contracts which allows to authorise/revoke access to specific Ethereum accounts based on whether the user using this account has been effectively

onboarded in our structure via KYC/AML procedures. Furthermore, the KYC/AML procedures allow the authorisation, tracking and ban of Ethereum accounts on the platform and from the investment proposal. Subsequently, the thesis novel solution gives the possibility to continue to monitor all irregular registration and trading behaviour relative to the token issuance and registration platform which is based on FINMA world-wide database. FINMA is the Swiss securities regulatory body and issues regulations to manage and direct the issuance of securities within Switzerland and by international organisations. Finally, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) contributes to the findings of Konashevych (2020) by adding insights on the property DNA which enables a real time monitoring of the property and all data about a property is backed up and stored decentralised which provides a sound investment decision based on complete and validated property data.

Security and Trust

The DLT blockchain technology is a security consensus of replicated, shared, digital database and has two types private (permissioned) or public (permissionless) that can be stored in the open and closed environment, by meaning who is able to write data onto that blockchain or onto that ledger. The Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) uses the permissionless nature of the blockchain technology which offers a potential to generate and encode information in the way that is equivalently available to buyers and sellers, removing the need for brokers as well as legal intermediaries. The permissionless smart contract gives full transparency to the track and trace each block on the chain and decrease the chance of mistake by increasing the quality of the data. In this manner, the permissionless Smart contracts address asymmetric information through automation, transparency and security that underpin consensus between parties in the process (Morabito, 2017).

This study applied DLT to show security and trust how stakeholders of the transaction on the shared ledger for distributed transactional ownership ledgers could interact more efficiently by omitting the redundancy processes of the 'middleman' stakeholders such as land registry, housing authority, appraiser and notary office and bring a higher security and trust for the interaction between buyer/borrower and seller (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019) and create new synergies and economies of scale in a shared economy as part of Industry 4.0. New economies of scale are emerging for health information exchange that makes the management of electronic records easier while eliminating fictions and costs associated with current intermediaries (Epiphaniou, Daly and Al-Khateeb, 2019). The smart contract architecture on the blockchain technology can have two types (permissioned and permissionless) that can be stored in the open and closed environment, by meaning who is able to write data onto that

blockchain or onto that ledger. The question of open versus closed brings into consideration which member can read that data. Therefore, there is a matrix to understand all the possible scenarios of public vs. private and open versus closed networks (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021).

In this scope, the future of the blockchain is debated with emphasis on the key limitations of public (permissionless or private- permissioned) implementations and on certificate and reputation management, and message forwarding promotion In the context of the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), the process of the blockchain technology that traditional commercial real estate process has a diminished need for human-operated brick-and-mortar institutions such as third parties (e.g. notary, municipality, house banks) and resulted into the human based property risky exposures due to human mistakes for both sides buyer and seller of real estate transactions (Ciatto *et al.*, 2019).

Social implication of widespread blockchain adoption is that the institutional structure of society could shift to the applications such as asset registries, global real estate financial inclusion, contribute to the long-tail user experience, open new payment channels (Swan, 2017) resolve cumbersome, paper-based, time-consuming system of ownership. While the traditional real estate contract is accompanied by the asymmetric information where each party, either seller or buyer are blocked – the seller is nervous to transfer the ownership of the property before receiving funds, and the buyer is exposed to a credit risk to send money before receiving the property, the new smart contract model on the blockchain provides each block of information can be as digitised information and hosted as decentralised database of records on distributed systems with lesser incidence of fraud and inaccuracies (Krupa and Akhil, 2019). Smart contracts enabled both parties as well as further third parties (e.g. notary, municipality, house banks) and remove the inefficiency and minimise the administrative burden of the transaction by structuring physical and contractual information in one place and guarantees the quality of the data by using the blockchain mechanisms (Wouda and Opdenakker, 2019).

In this study, security was followed by the concepts of the (Xu *et al.*, 2020) to role-based access control (RBAC), the security is assured by the permission control, and gasless mechanism enhances security and reliability. The smart contract allows users to publish their assets and use cryptocurrency to trade online, while preventing the users from risks such as Ethereum gas-related attacks and malicious API invoked. The smart contract on Ethereum security protocol is resistant to modification of data and considered a secured system because of the high amount of cryptography real estate allows to create a property "D.N.A." and "building passport" which needs to be stored and updated throughout the life cycle of a building (Ganter

and Lützkendorf, 2019). The high transparency of the Smart Contract is considered for the election process (Awalu, Kook and Lim, 2019). Smart contracts on blockchain technology are used to store as well as verify data and also applies the trusted mechanism for synchronisation of changes in data in order to possibly create a tamper-proof digital platform for sharing as well as storing data (Soni and Bhushan, 2019) and trust creates a sustainable relation between the investors (Ganter and Lützkendorf, 2019). However, the security debate is still ongoing on the type of the permission – permission less or permissioned network of peers. Both blockchain types can be stored in the open and closed environment, by meaning who is able to write data onto that blockchain or onto that ledger. Therefore, there is a matrix to understand the possible scenarios of public vs. private and open vs. closed networks (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021).

Social implications (Human skills)

The main roadblock is the human factor, people not willing to change and embrace the technology. There is a lot of fear with a lot of people who do not understand technology and as for any new technology, the availability of a skilled workforce is scarce and expensive. As a result, the transaction costs for the real estate contract might reduce since there is a diminished need for human-operated tasks. The application of the blockchain technology brings new possibilities of mutual delusion and concealment during the sale, rental, and lease processes can be eliminated, thus achieving digitisation of real estate ownership (Krupa and Akhil, 2019) and achieve efficiency gains for the real estate and keeping security (Hoxha and Sadiku, 2019). The key social implication of blockchain technology is to transfer the knowledge to the public and shared social environment such as new ecosystem. The ecosystem is designed that allows mutually unknown individuals and institutions to share data in a reliable ledger and carry out all kinds of P2P transactions, which indicates how blockchain works and the use cases for application and threats and will offer a few ideas for prospective expansion of this technology in the real estate industry by (Vokerla *et al.*, 2019).

Previously, traditional real estate contracts were asset illiquid and imposed high market barriers which hindered people and organisations from conducting real estate investments. By using the example of smart contracts in real estate transactions, skills such as human capital (e.g., knowledge, skills, experience) and physical capital (assets) are provided by the transacting parties while blockchain technologies facilitate the P2P exchange of these resources (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2013; Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019). In the thesis Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1), the Skills were adopted from various examples of social studies of real estate based on examples such as Walmart and IBM partnership which showed that smart contracts and cryptocurrencies can disrupt the way suppliers, shippers,

retailers, and customers trust each other and interact. The Blockchain technology allows to enable the security that could change the state of a transaction and show that decentralisation through algorithm-based consensus providing a reliable ecosystem in which real estate transactions can be safely preserved on the blockchain protocol. The empirical evidence is provided by such by global studies as of (Kalyuzhnova, 2018) essence of the blockchain as a value-communication technology that allows transferring not only information, but also value using mobile networks, Internet of Things (IoT) and the Industry 4.0.

As a result, the decentralised blockchain technology can foster social investment and of an individual or a group of people for the innovative entrepreneurship, while reducing investor risk appetite by storing the investment funds more secured in asset-backed regulated “Security Tokens”. In this context, the skills people are crucial factor for a successful execution of the transaction and prevent fraud deterrence in this new crypto-asset market and ensure appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental or illegal access (Konashevych and Poblet, 2019). The transparency and traceability of blockchain technology demonstrated and discussed in this thesis also makes a significant contribution to increased transparency and inclusivity in the field of commercial real estate investment and thus allows new target groups to participate in such forms of capital assets.

6.1.3. Conceptualising the design for the new design by conducting qualitative expert semi structured interviews and map the factors into the conceptual model “building blocks”.

On the one hand, the principle of relevancy is achieved when the thesis set out the objective of design-science research and aim of developing a technology-based solution to important and relevant business problems such as traditional commercial real estate market where the digital innovation process is inevitable fact. On the other hand, the principle of rigor is achieved by appropriately applying existing foundations and methodologies. In behavioural science, methodologies are typically rooted in data collection and empirical analysis techniques. Rigorous evaluation methods are extremely difficult to apply in DSR (Zelkowitz and Wallace, 1998). For example, the use of a design Artefact on a single project may not generalise to different environments (Markus, Majchrzak and Gasser, 2002). For this reason, this study designed and developed a class of problems which adds depth and understanding of the research validity. Finally, the empirical process, the data insights build the foundation for the impact on the future research of commercial real estate and PhD contributes originality knowledge for the academic society and professional Real estate community.

In this context, the thesis starts with the identification of current problems in Commercial real estate (relevance) and provides both Artefacts, the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) and the Prototype development (Research Artefact 2), to contribute to the further advancement of the academic debate. Albeit this practical starting point, the thesis is following the standards and norms of scientific research (rigor) specifically reflected in the ADSR approach.

In the context of the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the social acceptance in the market of the solution can only be achieved if the Real estate community achieves in-depth industry experiences as well as cutting-edge research and analytical skills to apply the smart contracts within real estate. The smart contract prototype development (Research Artefact 2) could become a white labelled novel solution and can be used for several investment structures within the and blockchain based ecosystems generate a high level of trust since the stakeholders can rely on the decentralised stored real estate property information on the blockchain.

1. Blockchain based solutions (tokens) offer advantages due to a higher liquidity, tradability / fungibility and automatization of the investment processes.
2. Blockchain based ecosystems generate a high level of trust – in addition, they can be implemented and replicated at moderate costs.
3. Besides the development fee, an additional fee for the investment structure can be implemented, offering an additional income for the Steiner AG.
4. The solutions are white labelled and can be used for several investment structures within the Steiner portfolio (also via a different name).
5. Real estate developments offer a targeting possibility for the implementation.
6. The Steiner AG can be among the first companies offering these solutions for national and international investors, resulting in reputation and innovation.
7. The solutions offer huge investment possibilities worldwide.

During the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the process of choosing the appropriate multi-layer architecture. The development of the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) is based on the practical example of commercial real estate Contract which tries to address the issue of multi-layer connection between actors, roles, business processes and database the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) is enhanced to increase the transparency, governance, security, and compliance consideration to increase the high value to the current Standard ERC 20 Ethereum Code.

6.1.4. Applying the ADSR results and findings of the thesis – Apply the Conceptual Model for the Prototype Development such as Architecture, database, Business Process (Web Application Server) incl. Business Process - Smart Contract (Implementation) and User experience (Actors and Roles (Owner and Users))

Architecture: To provide a new perspective on the architecture problems of KYC/AML as highlighted by Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi (2018) the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) consists of a set of smart contracts with one overarching Smart Contract holding variables shared by the asset sale smart contract and the asset logic smart contract. The KYC/AML smart contracts are added as a separate structure with which the asset sales contracts can safely communicate to check permissions given to Ethereum accounts to invest, operate or even modify specific variables on specific real estate assets. Specifically, to the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), this study identified that the real estate industry has a challenge when it comes to establishing secure and compliant commercial real estate transactions in an economical and timely manner. There is a large optimisation opportunity of the Karamitsos (2018) model on the process side and cost side.

By applying the Karamitsos (2018) model, the thesis tackles three dimensions of the multilayer architecture (Actors/Roles, Business Processes, Database) for the solution implementation and designs a system that could, ultimately, increase the overall real estate industry efficiency. To evolve from the Karamitsos (2018) model, the practical approach of multi-layer architecture was considered. After careful evaluation of the ERC 777 protocol based on the Ethereum Blockchain platform, the ERC 777 fungibility and inherent security must be adapted to fit our use case. The Ethereum community is vibrant and allows for knowledge exchange on a scale other chain could not achieve. In order to demonstrate the transparency, our experiment token will respect ERC820 meaning that it is registered on a central token index allowing investors to check the transactions protocol (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

Additional smart contracts ensure KYC/AML capabilities and allow investors to get the Yield generated by an asset in an automated and secure way within a trust-less environment. This smart contract infrastructure is accessed and used by end users through a web interface that would allow investors to easily interact with smart contracts deployed on the blockchain. This multilayer structure of Smart Contracts (Data Storage, Data Logic and KYC/AML) allows for additional mechanisms that better fit the Real estate transaction use case when compared to (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

Database: During the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the process of choosing the appropriate database is a fundamental step to ensure that several actors: Regulators, auditors, investors and real estate owners use the same set of information. Thus, the section follows a recommendation of the concrete publication “Blockchain Layer Approach” of (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018). The “Blockchain Layer Approach” outlines the solution architecture of the Prototype development (Research Artefact 2) which includes database (network layer), application layer, trust layer, blockchain layer, transaction layer which are embedded in the blockchain as a Service (BaaS) solution.

During the Prototype Development (Research Artefact 2), the database of the blockchain smart contracts is more prone to store efficiently account transactions and perform the actual transactions. Traditional databases are more efficient compared to smart contracts for storing things like images or long strings. For data security reasons, the data base development was implemented according to ERC777 protection mechanisms based on community wide agreed protocol (<https://eips.ethereum.org/erc>) implementing best practices and protecting users against security threats. Finally, the data updatability is ensured by implementing a similar structure as the one found under the EIP-1504 (<https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-1504>). Basic roles and permissions will give the logic for the smart contract access on the different variables stored in the storage part. In a more detailed manner, the storage part will be divided into several smart contracts. For every real estate asset sold through the artefact, the solution provides one storage smart contract holding essential asset variables (e.g., name, value, location).

The storage element tackles the task of storing its databases, variables and any other value that will be used in the future and that should not be strictly local. The logic part will handle all the process and business logic, meaning that it will hold functions, succession of actions and the ability to write on the storage part. Each of these layers has different properties and characteristics are included in the prototype development (Research Artefact 2).

The database layer, as seen on above, is therefore composed of two types of databases. The first one being a “traditional” database is stored in a traditional server and could be of any type (SQL, noSQL, etc.). This database would serve to store information that is expensive to store on a blockchain such as pictures, long strings, and other information about non-chain related assets. The second type of databases would be the blockchain smart contract holding balances and essential asset information. This information would be stored in the data storage

smart contract and will be usable by users on the web-app available through a browser. By combining those two-database type, the Artefact developed can be 1) compliant regarding the law with strict “centralised” mechanisms and 2) fully automated, fast, and borderless by implementing a blockchain database and logic.

Business Process (Web Application Server): As previously mentioned in the above factors the adoption of the blockchain technology started since the application of wireless real estate by Bartolomeu and Ferreira (2018) and application of blockchain by Ciatto *et al.*, (2019) resulting into the business logic rethinking of the blockchain technology. The innovative blockchain technology allows to reshape the business logic for the finance and business processes and generate financial benefits for token holders ensuring technological and financial security where real estate transformation is highlighted by Firica (2017) and was robustly measured using real estate blockchain matrix elements (Morkunas, Paschen and Boon, 2019).

The business logic in the artefact developed for the thesis is a hybrid blockchain/traditional system leveraging on the best of both technologies to provide the actors a platform that can perform investments in a seamless and user-friendly way. The researcher chose to develop a hybrid system for its inherent strength in processing transactions and account-based investment (Ethereum) and the user friendliness and ease of use (browser web apps). Indeed, the challenge when building a blockchain application is to make it easy enough for users to use. As one does not have an easy way to connect to a blockchain (this requires having substantial computing power and deep technical knowledge) the researcher had to find a way to make it easy for potential investors to connect, clear the KYC/AML procedures and then invest in the financial products held on the blockchain. While the literature review shed the light on the innovative finance and investment- collaborative housing and blockchain by Nasarre-Aznar (2018) and search for a favourable location by Kumar, Talasila and Pasumarthy (2021) the business logic became embedded in the smart contract supported by BaaS solution (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018).

The new BaaS solution allows automatic investment, portfolio management and provided for the users to buy a stake directly online for a seamless experience and FIAT investing through bank transfers (Abdelhamid and Hassan, 2019; Montgomery, Squires and Syed, 2018). In a hybrid system, the artefact comprises a web-based interface allowing the user to connect, upload the necessary documents for its clearing and invest on the specific products held on the blockchain. The platform would take care of retrieving information from the blockchain such

as asset name, location, and financial components of it (price and quantity available). The relevant information such as smart contract number and other blockchain related information needed to retrieve and perform transactions are stored in a typical noSQL database that allows the platform to be fast and responsive to the user command. The blockchain related information and processes are indeed slower than a typical application as they require clearance from the network to be processed. This being done through the proof of work can take a few seconds to clear and being processed by the specific node connected to our application. As those waiting times are usually not user friendly the Artefact proved to have the need to be based on a hybrid structure. Finally, the hybrid structure allows to develop a cross-blockchain protocol for public registries where real estate property titles are converted into tokens and further academic research needs to be conducted regarding blockchain anchoring of public registries: options and challenges as mentioned by (Konashevych, 2020b).

The thesis shows that the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) business logic proves to be an easy and seamless experience with a transaction costing only a few cents and being processed in 30-40 seconds on average. The complexity of the financial product does not make this process harder as the Ethereum has all its rules embedded in the code itself.

During the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the thesis considered to choose the Web Live App for the appropriate business process. This decision was made in favour of automatic investment and portfolio management and priority for users to buy a stake of fractionalised token asset directly online for a seamless experience FIAT investing through bank transfers. For those who will not trust cryptos or simply do not want to go through the process of buying some online, we will enable bank payment directly to our corporate bank account thus allowing them to receive their stake as soon as we receive the FIAT checks directly on it. In the thesis prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the modern real-time live Web-app covers the business process logic consisting of web application server WEB3.js, Angular Web App and Metamask to build a prototype for the Smart Contract on ERC777 (Artefact 2) and enable a live-connection with Web Application server and connection with interexchange like online browser where Metamask extension is integrated for transaction operations is conducted.

Business Process - Smart Contract (Implementation)

During the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the smart contract implementation of the blockchain smart contracts built on previous research by Karamitsos (2018; 2022) to

demonstrate how to improve the efficiency of the current processes, however, the cost/benefits analysis was not considered, and the KYC/AML process has not been included in the model.

Actors and Roles (Owner and Users): The actors are all part of the same blockchain ecosystem and perform different actions on the platform based on the information systems-design by Wouda and Opdenakker (2019) transaction process and a role model revolutionary smart contract for the commercial real estate by Krupa and Akhil (2019) which was depicted previously modern scientific real estate process by the actors and roles blockchain technology implementation for the real estate tenant model by (Karamitsos *et al.*, 2022)

First, the users can check live their balance and decide if they want to transfer it to another account or keep it in their Ethereum account. The user accounts are tracked by the KYC/AMC procedures order to have a compliant platform, we will perform the preliminary KYC/AML by pushing all the back end of a private equity directly on to the users. As such, users have complete freedom when managing their account information and keeping it up to date. The roles can perform the following actions. Investors can gather token information that effectively provides information on the piece of real estate represented on the blockchain. Based on this information, they are free to invest or pass on a certain asset. They also have the clearance to register their account on the KYC/AML registration process. Auditors and regulators have very similar actions available; they will be essentially added to the platform to control the accounts active and get their KYC/AML clearance as well as means invested. As such, they will be able to make sure that no account that shouldn't be cleared is performing transactions or that no money in provenance of illicit activities is effectively finding its way into a regulated financial product. Operators are part of the ecosystem and have special accounts that have the clearance to register or de-register accounts on the KYC/AML smart contracts. Real estate owners play a more passive role in the ecosystem by simply having access to the investment information and possibly being able to repay dividends to the investors in the specific project.

The prototype development (Research Artefact 2) outlines a deeper understanding of roles and actions embedded directly in the infrastructure of the blockchain. The major difference between a Blockchain and a classical IT project is the fact that account-based authentication is embeded in the blockchain and as such makes data protection by default very easy to implement. For example, it is trivial to implement data privacy on a smart contract as you could for example setup a variable called "authorisedAccount" which contains the unique ethereum account and then protect all your data retrieval functions with the condition that the "request account number" equals the "authorisedAccount". As there is no password, no central user

management, and no login interface in a blockchain, getting access to a specific account is only possible by stealing a private key. Essentially, the Ethereum Smart Contract is a private by default, and all the data that a developer decides to share is a choice made, which greatly improves privacy and robustness of such applications.

Consequently, for a financial system around investment in highly regulated assets, one could choose to share information about its investors in a completely public and open way or to limit the access to data to specific Ethereum accounts that would be held by the regulators. This could mean complete privacy, data protection but also an easy, open and automated way for regulators to make sure certain Ethereum accounts are not trading higher volumes than what they could in real life. This would prove much simpler than current checks performed by banks as the rules for blockchain accounts could be automated in a central protocol oriented blockchain. From the investor perspective, having access to its data from a privately focused blockchain and a unique user account allowing it to perform transactions on a cent basis with extremely low fees is a freedom never experienced until today. Essentially, such an Artefact provides the user a robustly protected system to perform tasks on behalf of a bank or private equity. Such an artefact would give investors freedom and empowerment on a financial level far superior and less risky than the ones currently available on the market. Although the scientific discussion of systems theory is linked to Krupa (2019), that the real estate industry would benefit from the blockchain technology regarding the improvements in database management, information management and efficiency, no specific architecture is demonstrated in the literature, rather than, the real estate information will be put into the smart contract and distributed among the nodes of the network (Krupa and Akhil, 2019)

Actors/ Roles - Legal perspective (Governance and Compliance): During the prototype development (Research Artefact 2), the Actors/Roles layer build the Legal Perspective and provides a new perspective on the KYC/AML problems which are not highlighted yet in the literature review. In order to respect current legislation and compliance rules of banking and investments, the simplified mentions of data encryption and data protection in (Krupa and Akhil, 2019) and (Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi, 2018) need to be extended. Consequently, the artefact had to include mechanisms to check if specific blockchain accounts were authorised to trade and purchase a specific Token (Asset). Additional mechanisms were implemented to authorise certain accounts as auditors and operators of such a KYC/AML contract to let external parties manage authorisation and clearing of accounts. Consequently, those operators can clear accounts but also ban specific accounts from trading such assets. The multilayer structure allows for strict linking of people and Ethereum accounts to ban people

and potential new accounts creation. The smart contract for the real estate aims also to revolutionise the real estate market from the legal perspective. Using a securitised investment note, the tokenisation platform will allow a regulated, and real estate backed asset-token. The token will be available to any eligible crypto investor, using an Ethereum ER20 based token, tradable for and with existing tokens and cryptocurrencies. Due to the unique and revolutionary use of the blockchain technology, the smart contract disrupts the traditional real estate market by introducing an almost fully liquid real estate investment product that has significantly cheaper entry and operational costs.

The results were shown to demonstrate that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract. One of the legal aspect pioneers of the Blockchain Technology model was originally designed by Karamitsos, Papadaki and Barghuthi (2018) to improve BaaS, whereby the proposed application provides a higher auditability, immutability, and transparency where specific assets mistakes will be encoded on the smart contract and decrease the chance of mistake from paper-based recording practice by increasing the quality of the data (Karamitsos, 2022). Smart contracts address asymmetric information through automation, transparency and security that underpin the symmetry in the consensus between parties in the process and highlighted more in details by the legal aspects in line with EU legislation by (Garcia-Teruel, 2020). Karamitsos (2018-2022) research added to the draft of the “multi-Layer approach” (Honar Pajooch *et al.*, 2021) (and that all the data should be encrypted to eliminate the manipulation with the digital data, thus enhancing fraud protection. However, the model proposed by Karamitsos (2018-2022) is lacking the governance and compliance components (KYC/AML) components which should ensure the immutability of the Blockchain received from the trusted authentic source. Finally, financial regulation/legal aspects aim to be enforcement binding viable and regulatory compliant, keeping into account limited liability of stakeholders and bankruptcy remoteness of the real estate tokenisation platform and highlighted upholding legal safeguards (KYC/AML), enforce correct policies and procedures, meeting legal and regulatory requirements confirming validity of future to-be model. The artefact development proved challenging not only from a technical perspective but also from a legal and compliance point of view. As a result, prototype development (Research Artefact) could further support the required KYC/AML checks needed to clear the accounts and limit access to certain assets according to location of the investors and legal checks on the amount invested versus liquidity amount and could create a trust legal instrument in the real estate ecosystem (Morena *et al.*, 2020).

6.1.5. *Potential Benefits of Blockchain*

Potential 1: Speed of Smart contract execution

Multi-layer blockchain model provides increased speed and accuracy as well as near real time smart contract operations such as paying rent (Honar Pajooch *et al.*, 2021). In this thesis, these findings can be verified as the prototype solutions indicate an increase of transaction speed. It was witnessed that instead of a transaction time of 2-5 days using classical intermediaries (e.g. bank, brokers) required for the transaction to clear, the blockchain transactions took in average only a couple of seconds (30-90 secs). Thus, this thesis shows that the Smart contract is run on a digital platform allowing for a drastically reduction of the transaction time. It advances the research by Karamitsos *et al.* (2022) where this study explicitly improves the frictionless transfer of the transaction and increases the speed closely real-time (30-90 sec) whereas Karamitsos *et al.* (2022) demonstrates only the renting Real estate. The speed potential increases the transaction efficiency gains for the commercial real estate and creates new opportunities across the world and without intervention from any intermediary/ or any middleman. Moreover, previous studies (e.g., Karamitsos *et al.*, 2018; 2022) did not discuss the potential benefits of using a blockchain for such transactions in the context of KYC and AML. However, it is important to highlight that a blockchain based transaction will always be clear if the rules programmed inside the application are respected (KYC/AML).

Potential 2: Transparency

Since the real estate market is becoming more open to the globalised investors, accordingly the supply chains have become longer and more complex which puts a challenge of traceability each real estate property contract and especially for the transparency in the developing countries to fight corruption (Milosavljević *et al.*, 2021). The hash demonstrates a unique and immutable transaction hash (Block) for the commercial real estate transaction which could enable various real estate stakeholders (e.g. buyer, seller, notary, bank, land registry, municipality) to trace back in real-time and improve the traceability of real estate portfolio products, which helps bring down costs by reducing excess inventory in order to demonstrate the transparency of a real estate blockchain transaction which is conducted on the smart contract prototype solution (Research Artefact 2).

As part of the developed prototype, the thesis conceptualised and embedded a real estate asset sale, with its compliance and regulatory checks, within a smart contract. This means that the entire process can be effectively digitised and decentralised to leverage the speed, robustness, traceability, and security of a typical blockchain application.

Potential 3: Data Quality and Trust

According to Konashevich (2020) the traditional real estate is prone to errors and that blockchain technology enables higher data quality by removing human mistakes by leveraging automated algorithms. The data quality means a resilient process in terms of identification, authentication, and authorisation of the transaction.

The prototype development (Research Artefact 2) uses permissionless blockchain records where the blockchain solution is applied for the pseudonymity nodes of owners (“miners”) and owners of blockchain addresses (“users”). Therefore, authentication requires a user’s public key which is the prerequisite for the contract execution after the successful verification of the peer-community. This simple authentication mechanism is not enough to bring trust to the end users of a blockchain and raises two issues: free access by anyone and anonymity of addresses (Konashevich, 2020). Therefore, when any data is published, no one knows who did that: an authorised officer or a hacker. Therefore, the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) for the commercial real estate is a multi-million business which is precisely supervised by financial authorities of respective countries. To tackle the previously mentioned issue, the decision was to enhance the smart contract ERC777 standard to include KYC/AMC checks enhancements. This allowed the prototype to function in trusted environments and identification, authorisation, and authentication with the component of trust. Moreover, if the private key to the blockchain address is stolen or compromised in another way, there is a need to have a procedure for a stop list such as PKI Database (Konashevich, 2020).

6.2. Conclusion

The study builds on the work of Hevner et al. (2004) and Sein et al. (2011) whereby practical utility is essential and ADSR is rigorously applied. This study investigated the existing design problems of commercial real estate transactions which is not fit-for-purposed to meeting complexity of requirements of real estate market in the 21st century. The thesis proposes a new design based on the given technological opportunities of smart contracts and proposes the conceptual model (Conceptual Model – Artefact 1) which helps to investigate the existing problem functionalities and understand the requirements for the new design innovation process and how to resolve the problems/disadvantages of the existing design within the commercial real estate contract (business operations) based on the expert interviews (internal validation) and later development of the system architecture and prototype development, system development itself and the instantiation of the prototype product (Prototype

development – Artefact 2) the evaluation of the market survey (external validity) and present the results to the academical audience as well as management-oriented practitioners

The key results of this thesis demonstrate that traditional commercial real estate processes can be encoded as an ERC777 smart contract, lead to the reduction of transaction costs, and a tokenisation-driven increases in revenues and profitability. Thereby, a variety of contributions both to the academic debate and to business practice can be derived. In the academic context, the thesis contributes by advancing the theoretical understanding of the use of blockchain technology and smart contracts in the context of innovative approaches to commercial real estate. By applying the principle of ADSR, the thesis provides a novel methodological approach for the exploration of this subject combining a systematic study of the literature, the subsequent development of a conceptual model, the practical application of the suggested model by the development of a prototype and the empirical evidence of both Artefacts in a qualitative and quantitative manner.

First, the thesis, distilled the main insights from the wide range of academic literature in the field deriving the current state of play with regards to the role of blockchain in commercial real estate. Second, the thesis developed a conceptual model on this basis delivering a theoretical foundation for the renewal of commercial real estate transaction processes from human, paper-based and prone to errors solutions towards fast, transparent, reliable, low cost, efficient and secure digital smart contracts. This can represent a key trust component for all the stakeholders. Third, the thesis transferred the insights gained by this model and developed a prototype to illustrate that the suggested approach for the application of blockchain technology for smart contracts in commercial real estate works in practice and yields advantages for both users and businesses. The thesis thereby contributes a practical use case demonstrating the formerly theoretically discussed potentials. Finally, the thesis embraces a triangulation approach using the ADSR methodology to frame a mixed-methods study. It combines qualitative, quantitative, and practical (coding) inquiries to the use of blockchain technology in the context commercial real estate contracts.

In the practical context, the thesis contributes by providing propositions and guidance for a potential application of smart contracts based on blockchain technology in the commercial real estate sector. Related to the first research question, three concrete contributions can be derived: First, faster speed was performed within seconds. Transaction execution was done faster than through bank transfers as the transaction clearing is performed on the chain itself with only a few seconds for execution. Second, lower transaction fees: low fees on transactions

nationally and internationally (a blockchain is borderless) proved handy to reduce impact on yield. Recording transactions on the blockchain will certainly make notarised legal acts redundant in the future. We can imagine that notaries will start to simply stamp Ethereum transactions directly on chain rather than producing lengthy paper documentation, but this must be accompanied by a industry-wide changes. The transaction cost paid during the experiment has amounted to 2 Euro Cents paid out in ETH during the execution of the Smart contract. Third, the regulation/compliance is backed up by the KYC/AML blockchain-enabled preselection of the appropriate legal buyers/sellers. In the system designed, the buyer identity is linked to the specific Ethereum account and therefore its stake is traceable throughout time. There is a greater control on who will ultimately own the share of investment since the ownership mechanisms are embedded in the token program itself. No shares can be held by an account uncleared on the KYC/AML contract, and the accounts are cleared and written on the KYC AML contract only by the contract owner (creator of the system) and authorised operators (regulators).

Moreover, by applying the Ethereum 20 and 777 token protocols to a real estate transaction in the context of the second research question, further insights for business practice can be identified. First, the new decentralised commercial real estate model leverages P2P fungible tokens networking of cryptographic tokens once consensus between the peer network nodes is achieved. In this context, blockchain technology allows to restructure the project funding model by crypto-business models (e.g. crypto-brokers, blockchain-applications) which are asset-backed by real estate's properties. Second, the user experience has significantly increased and gives more convenience for the user to perform the asset purchase/ asset sale. As a result, this could attract young professionals and new investors, interested in Real estate investing and portfolio diversifications, tech-acquainted and opt-in, opt-out at enabled trading on the chain. Third, the new business models could be reinvented and make Real estate contract more efficient and accessible for the broader target audience of investors. Fourth, distribution channel of new investors could revolutionise real estate in case smart contract could reach global networks of investors and leverage revenue streams and generate additional sales and be appropriate for potential project finance models (e.g. Token fundraising) (Bartoletti *et al.*, 2018).

In this thesis, the legal contracts difficulties are extended by introduction of tokenisation of the asset sale and further KYC/AML steps before the transaction execution (Treiblmaier, 2019). This might lead to higher quality of investor valuation (due diligence based on modern KYC/AML), lower the high real estate commercial contract barrier entry and still reduction of

transaction costs. The legal and compliance rules are subject to the KYC- know your customers and AML with specific set rules to authorise/revoke access to specific Ethereum accounts based on whether the user using this account has been effectively onboarded in the commercial real estate contract structure via KYC/AML procedures. The KYC/AML procedures allow the authorisation, tracking and ban of Ethereum Accounts on the decentralised platform. According to Treiblmaier (2019, p. 1) "so far no well-defined research agenda has emerged: research topics are scattered, and rigorous approaches are scarce...and discuss various types of case study research and how they can be useful for industry and academic research". In this context, the thesis has applied a novel approach of ADSR by Mullarkey and Hevner (2019) and added the qualitative thematic analysis structured interviews to identify the foundation factors to build the conceptual model (Research Artefact 1) and to build the prototype development (Research Artefact 2) and verify the results based on a large-market survey of 1000 participants (verified answers 700) and derive the answers of the research questions by a verification process (triangulation) to reflect the contributions in the discussion chapter.

6.3. Limitations

First, during the research in accordance with ADSR, several different methods of research were used (quantitative and qualitative analysis, surveys and interviews, statistical regressions, and empirical prototyping) which showed the potential of real estate investments through blockchain. However, the methods used pose limitations that can be described as follows. Second, the delineating constraints were to find a robust approach and reduce the complexity to resolve the research problem. In the thesis, both qualitative structured interviews to construct the Conceptual Model (Research Artefact 1) and a quantitative survey study to evaluate the significance of the derived factors have been used. Both have been applied in the context of ADSR to develop Artefacts, whereby iterative approaches supported the continuous development of new insights as well as the improvement of the quality of the results. Third, the key academic limitation envisaged on enhancing framework of the ADSR where the observation entry occurred at multiple iterations points in accordance with the ADSR guidelines (Mullarkey and Hevner, 2019) - starting from Diagnosis (Literature Review), then Build Artefacts (Conceptual Model Research Artefact 1) and (Prototype Development 2) followed by implementation of the real case prototype. However, the reflection phase experienced limitations as described in the strategy of asset class problems by Ivvari (2019). After careful utilisation of the ADSR methodology, the Artefacts were ready deployed as a Steiner AG/Swiss Realty solution to the whole real estate market.

The application of ADSR supported the structure of this thesis and provides the foundation for the guiding principles of relevance and rigour throughout the process of Artefact development and refinement. On the one hand, the relevancy principle (1) is achieved when the thesis set out the objective of design-science research and aim of developing a technology-based solution to important and relevant business problems such as traditional commercial real estate market where the digital innovation process is inevitable fact. On the other hand, the rigor principle (2) is achieved by appropriately applying existing foundations and methodologies. In behavioural science, methodologies are typically rooted in data collection and empirical analysis techniques.

In the context of the ADSR, both research artefacts are designed to simplify the challenging transaction process of a commercial real estate due to its cumbersome process structure consisting of several property brokers and legal structures illiquidity and heterogeneity and the lack of market transparency and evaluate the Research Artefact 1 (Conceptual Model) and Research Artefact 2 (Prototype) to apply under practical environment by analysing the customer behaviour on crypto investment for the developed prototype solution (1- Relevance) and addition of the new supporting evidence from the qualitative structured expert interviews based on transcription and coding and, as well as the quantitative empirical market survey based on the customer behaviour of the platform participants (2- Rigor).

After analysing the relevance principle (1) and rigor principle (2), the key limitation of the legal environment (3) was derived during the multi-entry points by iterative research. The limitation of the legal environment was to provide the proper mechanism of governance and compliance. In this context, the mechanisms developed assured that users of the artefact have access to their financial investment data and can perform relevant investment related actions when managing their account information and keeping their portfolio up to date as they wish. For that reason, the data managed by users' needs to be validated and cleared by internal processes before being inputted in a blockchain and allowing for users to trade tokens (Assets) as to have a compliant platform, it is required to perform the principles of KYC/AML procedures and regulations. As stated earlier, the data management process follows, similarly to the business logic, a hybrid structure.

Subsequently, the data necessary for the Prototype Development (Research Artefact 2) to deliver a successful user experience is stored on a traditional noSQL database while data essential for the transaction to be performed is usually stored on the blockchain for the automated transaction process and clearance. This second type of data could for example be

the KYC/AML check status used to clear an Ethereum account for transactions. To conclude, off-chain processes (KYC/AML) need to be completed in addition to the on-chain application for the concept proposed to be legally viable from a regulation point of view.

6.4. Future Research

Future research should be conducted in the field of DSRM where the blockchain use cases could shape future innovation research towards more industry relevant and knowledge rigorous blockchain case studies. The agenda of the future research is to publish on the one hand a first article for the conference paper and on other hand to find an appropriate peer-reviewed journal for the later publication.

The prototype solution developed in this thesis was based on the ERC-20 standard with later extension upgrade to the ERC-777 which offers a large investment possibility for the future and enables access to crowdfunding mechanisms for low-income target groups. It thus provides social participation in the real estate market in contrast to the traditional real estate contracts and transactions characterised by high market barriers, asset-illiquidity and exclusivity for only quality investors with high capital. However, future trends of the blockchain technology go beyond the tokenisation of the Real estate properties. The trend goes in the direction of “tokenomics” where any type of asset could be tokenised. As an example, the tokens could be a future concept for the Real estate eco-system where there could be cheaper access to capital for less demanding returns and on the other hand, it may provide a constant source of international capital for the general economy. The finance industry has been functioning with centralised exchanges for a very long time. Even when it comes to cryptocurrencies, the underlying models facilitating the functioning have been centralised for long.

The future trend goes in the direction of the Decentralised Finance (DeFi). In the context of informing business practice, further research could also elaborate on the investor protection and trust creation to identify the relevance of DLT for digital governments (Pignatelli, 2019). Furthermore, a wider approach to blockchain based solutions (tokens) could potentially unlock incremental advantages to existing processes due to their nature of higher liquidity, tradability/fungibility and automatization of the specified processes. One could argue that decentralisation should be embraced by institutions to give back the power and control to the people.

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